

Exploring the Experiences of Algerian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School Teachers in Teaching Learners with ADHD: Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

A Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements.
of the University of the West of Scotland
in the subject of Education
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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Declaration

Banner Number: B00376472

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work. I also certify that the thesis has not been previously and is not being currently submitted for any other degree at the University of West of Scotland and or any other institutions either in United Kingdom or out of it.

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Acknowledgment

In the name of God most gracious most merciful.

I'm grateful to God, who has granted me his countless blessing and provided me with the strength and health to successfully complete my study and patience to endure this journey of seeking knowledge.

First and foremost, I would like to thank my supervisors: Dr Steve Brown and Dr Xiao Qu for their guidance throughout writing this thesis. I would also like to extend my gratitude to my previous supervisor Professor Donald Gillies for all his insightful feedback and assistance. I'm incredibly fortunate to have such an inspirational supervisory team. I will always owe a great debt of gratitude for all what they have done to help me grow as a researcher.

A huge thank you goes to my participants for the privilege of allowing me in your lives and entrusting me with your stories. I would like to express my gratitude to the schools that granted me permission to recruit participants and to the dedicated staff members who generously devoted their time to assist me.

My sincere gratitude goes to the Algerian government for funding me throughout the PhD journey. I am grateful for the chance you have given me to pursue my dreams and ambitions.

Last but not least, thanks for the UWS staff for their assistance and professionalism. All my colleagues at J202 deserve special thanks for encouraging me throughout the research venture.

I thank you all for making this thesis possible.

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my late parents: Fatima-Zahra and Bouzid- to whom I promised to dedicate this thesis before they left our world. I deeply wish you were here by my side to celebrate this milestone with me. However, I find solace in knowing that you are watching over me and will forever be proud of your girl. My love for you knows no bounds. I love you, Mum, and Dad!

To my soulmate Hichem 'my inspiration and rock', thanks for your unstinting support, patience and understanding, thanks for being there for me and encouraging me when I needed it the most .

My heartfelt thanks to my family, my brothers 'Chafik, Mouhamed and Karim', and sisters 'Saida, and Meriem' for all the love and the support you provided. I also dedicate this work to my nieces, 'Asma', 'Razane' and 'Yara'.

I extend my gratitude to my best friend Hadjer, who attentively listened to my continuous complaints and provided unwavering support, motivating me to persevere during moments of overwhelming stress and anxiety.

Thank you all for believing in me.

Abstract

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a widely recognized and extensively discussed topic in the field of education, given its prevalence and the diverse perspectives surrounding its implications for students' learning and educational outcomes. It poses unique challenges in the schooling context, affecting students' attention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity, which can impact their academic performance and classroom behaviour. Teachers play an important role in the support, and inclusion of learners with ADHD. However, the behaviours associated with ADHD often challenge schoolteachers. This dissertation presents a study that used Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) to share accounts of participants' experiences with regard to teaching learners with ADHD in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, which revealed rich and worthwhile data. The following questions guided the research project: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD? How do different factors contribute to teachers' sense of challenge? How do they describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD? How do they describe the impact of their experiences? Individual interviews and group discussions were used to gather data from participants regarding their personal experience and reflections of teaching learners with ADHD. IPA informed the design of the study and provided a useful analytical tool that put the data under detailed scrutiny. Themes identified relate to the complex nature of ADHD, teachers' perceived challenges, emotions, and the impact of including these learners in the classroom. The findings are discussed in relation to the research questions, the theoretical work of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory (1990) and previous empirical literature on the subject. Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory, linked with phenomenology, was used to make sense of, and contextualise, the research findings in the context of a complex pattern of interrelationships. Thus, it helped to achieve a better understanding and interpret the data more holistically. By using this theory, the study sought to provide another alternative and accessible theoretical approach to frame teachers' development. The findings from this study show that both individual and environmental characteristics intertwine to affect teachers' experiences and development. Therefore, the overarching implication of the research project highlights a need to rethink the approaches of teachers' ongoing professional development to fully account for

individual as well as contextual features. The study hopes to inform educational practice by taking into account teachers' experiences and needs, in the context of the study.

Key words: Inclusion, EFL, ADHD, experiences, foreign language learning, bioecological theory.

List of Abbreviations

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder.....	(ADHD)
English as a Foreign Language.....	(EFL)
Inclusive Education.....	(IE)
American Psychiatric Association.....	(APA)
Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Health.....	(DSM)
Competency-Based Approach.....	(CBA)
Competency-based Language Teaching.....	(CBLT)
United Nations (UN).....	(UN)
Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.....	(CRPD)
General Comment 4.....	(GC4)
Biopsychosocial Model.....	(BPS)
World Health Organisation.....	(WHO)
Knowledge of Attention Deficit Disorders Scale.....	(KADDS)
Continuing Professional Development.....	(CPD)
Process Person Context Time.....	(PPCT)
Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.....	(IPA)
Semi-Structured Interviews	(SSI _s)
Focus Group Discussions.....	(FGD _s)
British Educational Research Association	(BERA)

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1. Chapter One: Introduction and Context of the Study

1.1. Introduction

This introductory chapter sets the scene for present study by presenting a short background on the research topic. It displays the researcher's interest in investigating Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of ADHD, highlighting the lacuna in previous scholarly articles. It outlines the research aims and objectives. It also presents the research questions that the study is set out to answer and highlights potential significance of the study. Finally, the general structure of the thesis is also provided so that the reader can get a general idea of its organisation.

1.2. Contextual background

Algeria is one of the three African-Maghrebi countries, along with Tunisia and Morocco. The country boasts a rich linguistic landscape, including Arabic as the official language, French which still plays a considerable role in the Algerian society, Tamazight, which became a national language in 2002, and has been incorporated into the school curriculum as an optional language to study (Ouahmiche, Beddiaf and Beddiaf, 2017).

Since independence, the educational system has undergone a number of reforms to restore its identity. After the colonial period, Algeria's first president Ahmed Ben Bella instituted a policy of 'Arabisation' under the hope of breaking free from the legacy of colonialism and uniting the nation under a single language and religion (Benkhaled and Vince, 2017). In essence, the policy sought to free the country from the shackles of colonialism that had oppressed its people for over a century.

Schools were seen as "a means to free the so-called benighted Algerians from the French assimilation" by promoting and disseminating the Arabic language (Maamri, 2009, p. 82). Despite considerable effort for de-Frenchification, French remained the language of economic and professional sector (Belmihoub, 2017). French or the "colonial heritage" as called by Bouherar (2020, p.3) has exerted an influence on the Algerian system (Benrabah, 2014). This suggests that the educational system in Algeria has been shaped by the legacy of French colonial rule. It also implies that aspects of the French colonial administration,

policies, or practices have left a lasting impact on how education is structured or conducted in Algeria.

Despite the fact that French held sway in Algeria, its dominance started to wane as English was also introduced in the educational system. Due to globalisation, the English language is gradually gaining ground in the Algerian context. Therefore, it has enjoyed tremendous recognition and favour among the Algerian population. In the educational sector, it has gained momentum in recent years through implementing a number of reforms to encourage the use of English, which was introduced in 1993 when fourth grade primary school learners were given the choice to choose English as a foreign language for the first time (Benrabah, 2007). However, efforts to introduce English as a second language in primary schools in Algeria during that period were unsuccessful, as only a small percentage of the population (15%) chose to learn English (Marouf and Moulay, 2017). It was until 2022 that it was included in primary schools alongside French (Haddam and Bouabdallah, 2022).

There is a noticeable trend of English gaining prominence in recent years, resulting in a decreased dominance of the French language to some extent. In addition, initiatives of academic programs led by the embassy of the United States in Algeria, such as the Fulbright program, and the British Council contributed to the spread of English (Belmihoub, 2015). Pennycook (2016) argues that the infusion of English has the potential to make Algerians see other alternatives to the French and Arabic. Belmihoub (2015) shares this view; he thinks that the English language would bring linguistic peace in Algeria. Indeed, English has contributed to the Algerian rich linguistic profile.

1.3 Background of the study

Inclusive Education (IE) has captured emerging attention in recent years. In a broad sense, it starts with the assumption that all children should be in the same educational setting (Adu and Mpu, 2021; Copley, 2018; Florian, Black-Hawkins and Rouse, 2017). It entails removing barriers for all learners. In a narrow sense and for the purpose of my study, it involves providing equal education to learners with special educational needs. ADHD is recognised as a special educational need as it affects learners' ability to function adequately in the classroom context and often requires an additional support (Mezzanotte, 2020). Inclusive education is a beneficial educational arrangement, particularly for students with specific

learning needs, where students with and without disabilities can learn together in a classroom setting, including subjects like English as a second language (ESL) (Kormos, 2020).

There have been many initiatives to support the right of education to all learners across the world. The Salamanca statement adopted a framework for action which calls for rethinking additional support needs education with the aim of informing policy to accommodate all children regardless of their needs and their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic conditions (UNESCO, 1990). It took the pledge and shared commitment to ensure the rights of all children to education and constitutes a milestone of inclusive education, with an emphasis on guaranteeing Education for All (Ainscow, 2021).

The publication of the Salamanca statement suggested a new direction in education where different countries shifted attention to Inclusive Education. In addition, Worldwide initiatives, the World Education for All (EFA) initiated in 1990 and reiterated in Dakar in 2000 are regarded as the most important framework in history that led to the development of Inclusive Education today (UNESCO, 2000). The World Education for All (EFA) started in 1990 as a movement to inclusion to assert the rights of all individuals to equal education. The Dakar forum served as a follow-up to the initial World Conference on Education for All in Jomtien. It aimed to assess progress made towards the Education for All goals set in Jomtien and to renew the commitment to achieving them by the year 2015. It resulted in the adoption of the Dakar Framework for Action, which outlined strategies and targets for improving access to quality education worldwide (UNESCO, 2000).

Recently, another framework for Action was launched in 2015 by the UNESCO together with the UNICEF, the world bank, UNFPA, UNDP, UN women and UNHCR 'Education 2030: Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action' (Ainscow, 2021). They expressed a vision for education toward 2030, reasserting the right of education and reassuring the fundamental role of education in transforming people's lives. They classified quality education as one of the 17 sustainable development goals for the next 15 years. The idea of including all children in mainstream schools became popular across the world (Singal et al., 2017). It has gained attention especially during the last 30 years (Ainscow, 2020).

If we are ever to achieve inclusive education, language used to describe this phenomenon should be clear and straightforward. Defining this concept has proven to be notably

challenging, and it has often been used interchangeably with the term “mainstreaming”, yet these terms are utterly different and mutually incompatible. Graham (2020) argued that mainstreaming is the same as integration which simply means placing learners with additional support needs in unreconstructed mainstream schools, asking them to adapt to the existing environment. However, inclusion means more than placing learners with additional support needs in mainstream schools, it involves a process of reform to the schools with the aim of ensuring an equal participation (Armstrong, Armstrong, and Barton, 2016). Therefore, it is the environment which adapts to ensure that all learners are treated fairly.

Mitchell (2015) views Inclusive Education (IE) as a multifaceted concept and explains that responsible inclusion occurs if legislation, policies, and regulations express a vision for inclusive education. This suggests that inclusive education happens through enacting a number of reforms and policies to revise the school system and make it more inclusive. In addition, different stakeholders including: the principal, head teachers, other senior members of the schools leadership, the school’s board governing body, the national, regional, local bodies responsible for education should express a commitment to inclusive education (Mitchell, 2015). The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) provides an impetus for inclusive agenda, specifically article 24 of the convention which stresses the human-right to education (Graham, 2020). General Comment 4 (GC4) which was adopted by the United Nations (UN) provides a more comprehensible definition of inclusion by viewing it as:

A process of systemic reform embodying changes and modifications in content, teaching methods, approaches, structure, and strategies in education to overcome barriers with a vision serving to provide all students of relevant age range with an equitable and participatory learning experience and environment that best corresponds to their requirement and preferences. (United Nations, 2016, paragraph 11)

The above excerpt implies that inclusive education involves a structural change to the education system according to learners’ needs, providing equal chances for learners to achieve and participate in their schools. In other words, inclusion entails reconsidering and revisiting the educational system to address the needs of those with special requirements.

In Algeria, there is currently no satisfactory definition for inclusive education, and there is often confusion regarding the terminology used. This confusion stems from the fact that there is still a tendency to mix up and use the terms inclusion and integration interchangeably, contributing to the existing ambiguity surrounding inclusive education in Algeria (UNESCO, 2020, United Nations, 2018). In Arabic language, different terms have been used to refer to inclusion ' AL-Damj' 'Al-Indemaj' and ' Al-Idmaj' (Khochen-Bagshaw, 2020). These terms can be translated into 'integration' in English.

It is worth mentioning that Algeria has ratified the UN nation Convention on the Rights of persons with disability in 2009 and different laws have been enacted regarding the education and the right of persons with physical disabilities. Article 5 of the UNCRPD, ratified by Algeria on 2nd of May 2009, sets out the principles of equality and non-discrimination. Among other things, the committee has restated its previous recommendations to ensure accessible curriculum and provide adequate training for mainstream schoolteachers. This underscores the significance of ensuring that educational materials and resources are designed to be accessible for all learners, regardless of their abilities. Furthermore, it highlights the need for teachers to receive specialized training that allows them to accommodate different needs and use more inclusive classroom strategies.

Article 14 of the Algerian constitution, for example, 08/04 assures the rights of persons with physical disability (UNESCO, 2020). Besides, Article 32 of the 2016 Algerian Constitution provides that: "All citizens are equal before the law' and no discrimination shall prevail by reason of birth, race, gender, opinion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance". Therefore, a premium is placed upon ensuring equal participation of people from different ethnic groups and with different physical, social, or mental condition. Equality represents a sacrosanct and an inviolable right for people of all backgrounds, as enshrined in the Algerian constitution. Furthermore, different legislations as: the Civil Code, the Criminal Code, the Code of Criminal Procedure, and the different specific codes are based on the fundamental touchstone of equality. It appears that Algeria has developed legislation and policies aimed to provide a welcoming environment for different people and to protect their human rights.

In the realm of inclusive education, Algeria shines a spotlight on the needs of people with additional support needs to be educated alongside their peers. From the 1970s, people with additional support needs started to be included in mainstream schools. It has ratified different legislations that aim to provide equal opportunities for persons with additional support needs. Although international organisations have spent a considerable effort to bridge the gap between theory and practice, there is still a disconnect between theoretical principles and practical implementation in the Algerian context (Bessai, 2018). The laws still include language that is insulting and offensive, such as the use of derogatory terms like 'imbecile' or 'incapable' (UN, 2018). In addition, literature indicates that there is a paucity of literature in relation to inclusive education in the Algerian schools (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018; Bouzid-Baa and Mekhoukh, 2016; Fekih, 2018; Rohwerder, 2018) in the Algerian context.

After providing an overview of inclusive education on a global scale and within the specific context of Algeria, I will now shift the focus towards the primary subject of the study, which is Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). Inclusive education also aims to maximise learning opportunities for children with additional support needs including learners with ADHD. The American Psychiatric Association (APA) defines as "a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that interferes with functioning or development" (2013, p. 61). Research has shown that about one student in every classroom may have ADHD (Anderson, 2020; Gaastra et al., 2019). This suggests that ADHD is a relatively common condition affecting a significant proportion of children in school settings.

ADHD impacts around 5% of children and teenagers worldwide (Sayal et al., 2018). In addition, the number of pupils diagnosed with ADHD has increased globally (Rigler et al., 2016; Thomas, et al., 2015). It is one of the most controversial topics which still captures a widespread controversy regarding its classification, causes and diagnosis (Kean, 2012). Teachers play an important role in supporting learners with ADHD (Moore et al., 2017; Russel, Moore, and Ford, 2016). In addition, they also have a critical role in providing support for learners with ADHD and have the responsibility of implementing Classroom Management Strategies (CMSs) to promote the emotional and social growth of learners within the school environment (Tompkins et al., 2015). They actively contribute to promoting the inclusion of learners with additional support needs (Brussino, 2021).

As stated earlier, teachers are tasked to implement school-based strategies to involve learners with ADHD and keep them engaged in the classroom. Despite the essential role teachers play in supporting learners with ADHD, evidence suggests that teachers may be unprepared to do this task effectively (Martinussen et al., 2011). It is important to highlight that teachers often find it challenging to include learners with ADHD due to their lack of knowledge and skills regarding management strategies (Gaastra et al., 2016). In addition, children showing behavioural attributes that are linked to ADHD present challenges for schools (Malmqvist and Nilholm, 2016).

Considering the demanding nature of teaching students with ADHD, it is crucial to amplify the voices of teachers and the challenges they face. In addition, given that children with ADHD spend a significant portion of their time in school, it is imperative to prioritize research on the school environment, with a particular emphasis on teachers. To foster inclusive education effectively, educators should be motivated to voice their requirements to create a learning environment that promotes inclusivity (Batstra, van Roy and Thoutenhoofd, 2022). Through adopting IPA as an approach to data collection (see chapter three, p.74), the present study motivates teachers to engage in self-reflection, share their challenges and requirements to propose potential solutions to advance the inclusive education of learners with ADHD.

1.4 Algerian educational system

From 2003 onwards, the structure of the educational system has changed from 6+3+3 to the 5+4+3 model (Rose, 2015). Arab (2017) and Djoudi (2018) explained that the educational system is divided into preparatory, basic (primary and middle), secondary, and higher education. Primary school education lasts five years, middle school education lasts four years, secondary school lasts three years and higher education lasts from three to five years. This study focuses on the middle school context. I will present a brief overview of the Algerian educational system, justifying my choice of the middle school context.

1.4.1 Primary school education

Children start enrolling in primary school at the age of 6 and sometimes 7. They start learning the basic skills needed: reading and writing. They are also introduced to other subjects including maths, geography, and French in their second grade. Recently, English has

been implemented in primary schools as a compulsory language (Haddam and Bouabdallah, 2022). At the end of year five, children are awarded a certificate of basic education after succeeding in the final exam which is their permit to middle school.

1.4.2 Middle school education

Pupils move to a different setting and start enrolling in middle school. Following the 2003 reform, middle school started to have a duration of four years where learners sit for a test called Brevet d'Enseignement Moyen (BEM) which was once called Brevet d'Enseignement Fondamentale (BEF) by the end of this academic level. Before 2021 reform, learners used to be introduced to the English language in the 1st grade of middle school.

Middle school are considered important foundation years for the development of the child academically, emotionally, and socially. Notably, the transition to middle schools represents a crucial time to support learners with ADHD before they move to high school (Smith *et al.*, 2015), yet many middle school teachers struggle with supporting learners with ADHD in mainstream schools (DuPaul and Jimerson, 2014; Lawrence, Estrada and McCormick, 2017). For the above reasons, I felt the need to focus research on this stage which is considered a focal point in the learners' academic life and a challenging period in teachers' pedagogical endeavour. Consequently, my research would be useful to both teachers and learners with ADHD who would benefit from teachers' increased awareness. My study focuses on the experience of middle school teachers in two middle schools located in an area in the east of Algeria. The choice of this stage was also influenced by my previous teaching experience (see section 1.7 for more details about my rationale).

1.4.3 Secondary school education

Pupils who successfully pass their BEM are eligible for secondary school studies. The first year includes all subjects before learners are given full freedom to choose among three branches (tronc-commun) the one that suits their preferences. Secondary education lasts three years and the grades are described as 1st to 3rd *Année Scolaire* (AS). High school culminates in the baccalaureate exam (BAC) and students who successfully pass their BAC are eligible for higher studies.

1.5 Identifying and supporting learners' needs.

Article 14 of Act No. 08/04 dated January 23, 2008, concerning national education, includes specific provisions regarding children with, what the document refers to as 'special needs'. It mandates compulsory education for children aged 6 to 16, extending this by an additional two years for children with disabilities. Additionally, Act No. 15-12, enacted on July 15, 2015, pertaining to child protection, affirms the rights of children with disabilities to protection, care, education, and rehabilitation, with a focus on promoting their autonomy and active engagement in economic, social, and cultural aspects of life." (Journal Official Algerie, 2015).

The support and education for children with disabilities is planned by a multidisciplinary team primarily composed of specialized educators, schoolteachers, social workers, and professionals such as psychologists, speech and language therapists, clinicians, and teachers (UNESCO, 2021). In addition, the ministry of national solidarity works to promote the inclusion of learners with disabilities (UN, 2015). However, the support of learners with special educational needs still lags behind (Bessai, 2019). In addition, there is insufficient engagement of pertinent stakeholders, such as school principals, parents, and students (UNESCO, 2014).

The school psychologist works to raise teachers' and parents' awareness of certain learning disabilities (Bessai, 2018). In Algerian middle schools, it is customary for school psychologists to evaluate and diagnose learners with ADHD. The school psychologist conducts interviews with parents and teachers ,with whom the child spends most of the time. These interviews aim to gather information about the child's behaviour in various contexts and their interactions with others (Oussedik, 2018). In the schools where my study took place the procedure was for psychologists to identify learners with ADHD and communicate this to teachers.

1.6 Educational reforms in Algeria

There have been a number of reforms in recent years to revitalise English language teaching. Broadly speaking, the Algerian Ministry of Education introduced the National Commission Reform for Education (NCRE) to monitor what is happening in schools and propose enhancements accordingly. It suggested the need to reform the educational system

to cope with the new global age and keep abreast of globalisation requirements (Ghezir, Naimie and Leng, 2022). Globalized requirements emphasize the need for education systems to equip individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary to participate in a globalized society, engage in international collaborations, and navigate the challenges and opportunities of a rapidly changing world.

The educational system underwent frequent reforms. Notably, Algeria has adopted the Competency-based (CB) curriculum across all subjects and all levels in 2003 to meet the requirements of globalisation via introducing the use of information and communication technology (ICT) (Boudouaia, 2021; Gherzouli, 2019). Competency-based Approach (CBA) is a learner-centred approach which views learners as active agents who are responsible for their own learning (Gasmi, 2020). CBA was also applied to language learning and teaching 'Competency-based Language Teaching' (CBLT), an approach that stresses the need to foster the learners' communicative competence and improve their speaking proficiency. The new educational framework in Algeria recognises English as one of the competencies learners should acquire through Competency-Based Education (CBE) (Djebbari, 2016).

This reform pays particular attention to developing learners' skills and knowledge, providing them with the opportunity to apply what they have learned in new situations so that they can be used ordinarily in everyday life (Adjeroud and Belouahem, 2020). CBLT or CBT in general requires learners to put into practice what they have learned, aiming to increase learners' autonomy and their higher order thinking through involving them in continuous problem-solving activities (Baghoussi and El-Ouchdi, 2019). Therefore, it appears that this reform aims to create autonomous learners who are responsible for their learning.

It seems that the teaching of English has gained traction in recent years with many reforms being implemented to promote the use of English across middle schools. The English syllabus in middle schools has undergone different changes to help learners to communicate effectively using the English language. The main premise behind this reform is to enable learners to mobilise knowledge and skills for real-life situations.

1.7 A critical examination of the current situation in Algerian middle schools

In an attempt to internalise the educational system, a number of reforms have been initiated which reflect the growing status of English in Algerian education. As previously

mentioned, (section 1.4), CBT- first generation curriculum came into vogue in the Algerian educational system in 2003. By implementing CBA, the Algerian educational system aimed to move from a teacher-centred to a learner-centred approach. In Algerian schools, the idea of the teacher as the sole knowledge provider has been challenged as learners are encouraged to take charge of their learning and construct their knowledge (Djerouane and Bensafi, 2022).

The second-generation National curriculum (also called CBA second-generation textbooks) was launched in 2016 as a response to the orientation law on National education No. 08-04 23 (January 2008) (Tahani, 2020) with the aim of developing learners' communicative competence and autonomous learning (Boudouaia et al., 2022, Derrahi, 2021).

The Algerian Ministry of Education (2016, p.3) commented on the new curriculum of English teaching:

Learning English in the middle school aims primarily at developing communicative competence in English. We are shifting from a paradigm of accumulation and transmission of linguistic knowledge and ideas to a paradigm of interaction and integration, all within a social constructivist view of learning. Focusing on the learner will enable him to be actively engaged in deeper cognition, acquisition of knowledge and development of a number of competencies.

As the above quotation suggests, the idea underlying this novel pedagogy works toward fostering learners' communicative competence. It implies a shift from accuracy to fluency or interactive features of language.

Although the Algerian policy makers have initiated a reform of national education in 2002 which is based on three different pillars including teacher training, pedagogical reform, and reorganisation of the educational system (Gasmi, 2020), most middle school teachers complain about the length of the new syllabus and the complexity of reforms in the Algerian middle schools (Benadla, 2013). In addition, they seem to struggle to apply the new approaches to teaching due to large class size (Belmihoub, 2015). Furthermore, CBA boils down to competence and developing learners 'how-to-do' and 'how-to-act' (Bouhadiba, 2015). This means that it requires skilful and competent teachers to help learners acquire competencies which would help them to communicate efficiently with the world.

CBLT aims to offer a plethora of opportunities for cooperation and learning (Choubane, 2019). Ideally, the teacher following CBLT is entitled to take on board learners' needs and preferences. However, little attention is paid to individual differences due to large class size (Bellour, 2017). Bouhadiba (2018) maintains that the new curriculum following CBT does not take learners' perspectives into account. Teachers in the Algerian context have a syllabus with clearly defined objectives to follow. In addition, the course book in Algerian middle schools prescribes a number of competencies (Bellour, 2017).

Kumaravadivelu (2006) claims that a theory of teaching should be chosen based on its applicability to real life. This principle, according to Kumaravadivelu, emphasises teachers' practical experience who are encouraged to use their previous knowledge to act autonomously. This according to Wallace and Bau (1991) fosters teachers' reflective thinking about their teaching practices. Prabhu (1990) also emphasised the fact that teachers' plausibility should be considered before choosing any method. This idea of plausibility, according to him, entails that teachers construct their theories of teaching through their own experiences and reflecting on their professional endeavours. Complementing what previous scholars have initiated, Ur (2015) put forth that methods restrict teachers' freedom. Oddly enough, teachers in the Algerian context are required and strictly enforced to comply with the national curricula and policy instructions (N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008, Article 20). Therefore, Algerian education is characterised by an authoritative top-down hierarchical management system. According to Gherzouli (2019), Algerian teachers are excluded from the planning of reforms, which may result in a lack of sense of ownership. This hierarchy of power which involves a top-down approach to curriculum development and implementation seems to leave no space for teachers' creativity (This aspect will be further discussed and expanded upon in chapter five, page 154).

Bouhaina (2019) concluded that the Algerian schools do not reflect the CBA teaching expectations. Correspondingly, Bouhadiba (2018) claims that CBLT has not reached its aims today. He verbalised his thoughts on different barriers to implementing CBA approach in Algeria including lack of teachers' preparation, overcrowded classes, disengaged pupils and lack of access to internet. Ironically, teachers in the Algerian context still undergo the sway of traditional methods as they prefer to cling tenaciously to the traditional methods of

teaching namely the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018). Methods were critiqued on different grounds and many scholars called the notion of method into question. Pennycook (1989) criticised the top-down approach of methods which aims to create “unequal power relations” (p.5). Kumaravadivelu (1994) joined this line of debate and views that methods are based on a rigid curriculum and fixed knowledge where learners’ needs and preferences as well as teachers’ voices, reflection and creativity were marginalised. In addition, Brown (2002) takes up Pennycook’s (1989) argument and confirms that methods target “the disempowered” (p.10). This stresses the need for a remedial work and shifting attention from traditional teaching methods, implementing more communicative and less prescribed methods.

The above discussion offered a brief overview of some important aspects of the current situation in the Algerian educational system. Efforts were made to encourage teachers’ and learners’ autonomy in ELT. However, classes are still teacher-centred with less emphasis on learners’ requirements (Bellour, 2017). This “one size fits all, cookie cutter approach [...] assumes a common clientele with common goals” (Kumaravadivelu, 1994, p.165). This might be a false conception as classes nowadays are highly heterogenous where students have different needs that one method such as GTM cannot account for. The one size fits all approach that is plaguing the educational system may cause some learners to fall behind. It may overlook or neglect the specific needs of certain learners, including those with disabilities and additional support needs. To ensure equitable and inclusive education, it is essential to design and implement flexible and differentiated curricula that can be adjusted to cater for the diverse needs of students. This approach recognizes and respects the individuality of students, including those with ADHD, and promotes their engagement, participation, and success in the learning process.

Despite the fact that the new reform is meant to remedy the deficiencies of traditional education, it seems that the wind of change in Algerian education is not blowing favourably, with less emphasis on learners’ needs and teachers’ active participation. Due to time constraints, teachers in Algeria face significant challenges in providing individualized attention to students, making it practically unfeasible (Bellour, 2017; Bouhadiba, 2018).

1.8 Language teacher education in Algeria

The Ministry of National Education serves as the designated entity to receive and approve training files for student-teachers. Before these training documents can be used, they must undergo endorsement and approval from the Ministry of National Education, which is accountable for upholding policies within the schools (including primary, middle, and secondary schools) where the training occurs. The majority of teachers selected for primary and lower secondary education possess a university degree. However, middle school educators are mandated to have completed a BA degree (BAC) plus four additional years of education (Ghedjghoudj, 2014). University graduates, holding the degree, are not necessarily trained to teach. However, they can only be appointed to a teaching position after participating in a national test based on specific criteria, including written and oral exams. Since 2015, teachers must undergo a six-week pedagogical training. The EFL Teacher Training Programs encompass the following modules and subjects: teaching methods, educational psychology, school regulations, professional ethics, educational media technology, classroom management, the Algerian education system, and pedagogical instruction design (Hadi, 2021).

Training is held at specific institutes known as "Instituts Technologiques de l'Éducation," aimed at preparing trainees for the teaching certificate known as "Certificat d'Aptitude Pédagogique". These institutions primarily focus on subject-matter and provide a limited coverage of pedagogy and instructional methods, lacking substantial influence on pedagogy and instructional methods. In terms of ongoing training and professional development of teachers, it has been largely confined to ad-hoc sessions organised by inspectors (teacher educators) of each grade or each subject. These training sessions vary in format, ranging from one-day seminars, conferences, and workshops to a few days during school breaks. They are usually delivered by an inspector who is responsible for organizing and designing the program for the seminar or workshop. This includes determining the scheduling, location, theme, and allocating various components of the chosen theme to the participating teachers (Nouri and Nouache, 2021). These events are often diverse and disjointed in their structure and content, leading teachers to perceive them as ineffective for enhancing teaching practices or advancing their professional growth (Ghedjghoudj,

2014). This is unsurprising given the fact that inspectors determine the content and teachers are passive recipients of knowledge.

Given the absence of initiatives to educate teachers on integrated or inclusive education for children with disabilities in 2014, a limited number of teachers and staff have received comprehensive training in inclusive education (UNESCO, 2021). In 2019, a training program was devised covering critical topics such as autism, mild learning disabilities, social support, and sign language (UNESCO, 2021). It is noteworthy that, up to the present time, there have been no training programs specifically focusing on ADHD in Algeria.

1.9 Thesis rationale

The catalyst for this study evolved from my early academic and professional experience. I developed an interest in ADHD via first-hand experience both professional and academic. This vested interest in the field of inclusive education was developed prior to my teaching experience when I was a student at the university located in my hometown. My master's thesis explored primary school teachers' experience of teaching children with elective mutism and yielded worthwhile data regarding their challenges with regard to teaching these learners, especially when it comes to encouraging these learners speak. I believe that focusing on teachers' experiences of teaching learners with additional support needs is crucial, especially in the Algerian context. By prioritizing this focus, the study would assist in advancing the inclusive agenda.

In addition to my academic experience, my teaching experience which dates back nearly five years motivated me to undertake this research. Once I entered the classroom as a new teacher in a middle school, located in an area in the east of the country, with feelings of fear and enthusiasm, I noticed the heterogeneity of the school context where learners have different learning needs. I realised that some pupils have difficulty staying on task and do things that made me feel stressed and anxious. As a new teacher, I lacked awareness of how to manage challenging behaviours displayed by learners with ADHD, and I struggled to identify and understand these behaviours. I observed that some learners' behaviour disrupted the classroom balance, and I faced numerous challenges in teaching them. It was a demanding task that required a considerable amount of effort, and I found myself considering solutions outside the educational context. I did not anticipate such challenges or

this level of heterogeneity in Algerian middle school classes before starting my job as a teacher, and this experience overwhelmed me.

Those experiences inspired me to undertake this study of Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. As a previous middle-school teacher, I possess some familiarity and comprehension of the situation, which aided me in drawing certain conclusions. My insider position made me a more effective qualitative researcher since my familiarity with the context and sharing experience with participants enabled me to achieve a more thorough and deep interpretation. Because of my background in EFL teaching, I could put myself into participants' shoes to work out the underlying meaning and understand their concerns in the present study. In addition, I have always engaged in much self-reflection. In other words, I used my knowledge of the context in the meaning-making process. My interpretative analysis drew on my own knowledge and experience of the research topic. This is where my own values and experience as an insider researcher came to the fore.

When I was conducting my data collection with teachers, I found that I sometimes shared opinions and perspectives with them and sometimes I did not. Such differences in opinions are to be expected in a group. Therefore, I need to acknowledge the potential conflict arising from my position as a doctoral researcher and my involvement in this particular context. Throughout the research process, I experienced a transition along the "insider-outsider continuum" proposed by Hellawell (2006, p.488). Initially, I was deeply engaged as an insider researcher, having close involvement and familiarity with the study participants. However, as the research progressed and I returned to the UK, my role shifted to encompass both insider and outsider perspectives. In this dual capacity, I approached the topic from the viewpoint of being a former teacher who possessed insider knowledge while also adopting the lens of a doctoral researcher who was no longer an active part of the context being studied. Therefore, my understanding was questioned as unanticipated findings surfaced, necessitating me to temporarily set aside my knowledge (for more details, see section 3.10). Inevitably, the study has changed my way of thinking due to some intriguing findings.

As a former middle school teacher, I share the challenge of teaching some learners and I see that teachers' voices need to be heard and implemented in decision-making. In addition, my

background involving a working experience as a middle school teacher and a former EFL learner influenced my choice of the EFL context. Besides, conducting such a study in the Algerian context might be worthwhile since the concept of ADHD lacks a thorough investigation. It would address a large gap in the literature since less is known about ADHD in the developing countries (Barkley, 2020).

To the best of my knowledge, this study is the first to explore Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. It would offer an in-depth understanding of ADHD in the context of the study and provide insight into what it means for teachers to have learners with ADHD inside the classroom. Consequently, this research would fill in this void and address the gap in the scholarly literature regarding the lack of qualitative research on the topic of ADHD, and it would also extend previous literature on teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD.

1.10 Research questions

The research questions are formulated to achieve the aim of the study, which is to develop an understanding of Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences, including their conceptualisations, feelings, and any challenges they might encounter, in addition to the perceived impact of those experiences. They were formulated to answer the big questions: what is it like to have a learner with ADHD inside the classroom.

Toward achieving this goal, the following questions were formulated:

1. How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD?

Prior to gathering information from teachers about their personal experiences, this question was designed to assess the extent of their familiarity with this condition and gauge their level of understanding of it. Understanding teachers' perceptions of students with ADHD can help us identify potential biases and stereotypes that may affect their interactions with these learners.

2. How do different factors contribute to Algerian EFL middle school teachers' sense of challenge?

The purpose of this question is to explore the various factors, including environmental ones, that may influence a teacher' sense of challenge in the classroom. By understanding these

factors, we can gain insight into the complex dynamics of teaching and identify potential areas for improvement.

3. How do they describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD?

This question aims to elicit information on the range of emotions that teachers may experience when working with students with ADHD, including frustration, empathy, patience, and support. By understanding these emotions, a more supportive environment can be created for teachers and all learners.

4. How do they describe the impact of their experience?

This question seeks to elicit information on the specific experiences that teachers have had with students with ADHD, and how these experiences have influenced their comprehension of the condition and their instructional approaches. By understanding how teachers' experiences influence them, we can identify potential areas for improvement in teacher training and support.

Overall, the above questions aim to delve deeper into the meaning Algerian EFL middle school teachers ascribe to their experience of educating learners with ADHD, so they are participant-laden with the aim of getting closer to teachers' subjective interpretations of their teaching journeys. The formulation of these questions was an ongoing process, refined through the course of the study. As I gained deeper insights and gathered more data, I iteratively modified and improved the questions to ensure they effectively captured the relevant information and addressed the research aim.

1.11 Research aims and objectives.

My study aims to explore the experiences of Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of working with learners with ADHD. Based on this aim, the following objectives were put in place:

- Review the literature.
- Construct and collect data surrounding teachers' experiences via adopting an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a methodology which emphasises the subjective experience of participants, using nine Semi-structured Interviews (SSIs) and two Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

- Examine different aspects of their experiences, including their emotions, challenges, and personal narratives. By analysing these elements, researchers can access the teachers' unique perspectives and gain a deeper understanding of their lived experiences.
- Analyse the data using Smith, Flowers, and Larkin's (2009) step-by-step analysis and report teachers' experience of working alongside learners with ADHD.
- Conduct a further review of the literature to compare the findings against it.

1.12 Potential contribution to knowledge

Overall, the study carries the potential for raising awareness of ADHD within the Algerian context. The study would be beneficial for a wide range of individuals and groups including teachers, parents, educational researchers, and policy makers. The study will help to raise awareness of the experiences of Algerian EFL middle school teachers including their struggles and needs. Parents will gain a deeper insight into the difficulties encountered by teachers who work with learners with ADHD so that they can work collaboratively with them and assist them in their journeys. This study also hopes to inform future research providing insights on ADHD in the Algerian context and more specifically the experiences of teachers.

The findings of this research can have the potential to aid in the reconstruction of school policies aimed at enhancing curricular accommodation for students with learning needs. Therefore, by using the findings from the research to inform policy, schools can better accommodate the needs of these students and provide more inclusive and fair educational opportunities for all learners. In addition, the study also hopes to raise awareness among policy makers of the significance of attending to the requirements of teachers who instruct learners with ADHD, and the potential benefits of investing in their education and support. The study can also be utilized by a variety of stakeholders, including educators, teachers, parents, administrators, experts, and psychologists, to collaborate and support students with additional support needs.

1.13 Thesis structure

The thesis is structured as follows:

- Chapter one sets the scene for the whole thesis and introduces the topic of ADHD and why it is worth investigating. It also describes personal motives in the area of concern and what drove this endeavour. This introductory chapter outlines the research aim, objectives and presents the research questions.
- The second chapter critically discusses relevant literature, drawing on the complexity around ADHD and also tracing international literature on teachers' experiences with regard to their teaching of learners with ADHD to provide a greater understanding of the topic of ADHD. This chapter narrows down the discussion to focus on ADHD in the educational context. In this chapter, the relevance of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological systems theory to the study is also discussed.
- Chapter three describes the methodological orientation of the study and explores how the study was conducted. It includes the researcher's ontological and the epistemological beliefs which influenced choice of the research methodology. It also describes the research design adopted to answer the research questions. Other topics are included in this chapter including data analysis, validity, and ethical consideration.
- Chapter four presents the analysis of the data collection phase by addressing each question. It outlines a number of themes that were drawn from the interview and the FGDs transcripts accompanied by verbatim extracts to capture the voice of participants.
- Chapter five discusses the findings in relation to the existing body of literature drawing on similarities and differences between my study and the extant body of research. In addition, it also links the data to the theoretical framework and provides another level of interpretation drawing on Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory.
- Chapter six summarises the findings in relation to each question and notes the contribution to knowledge that study has made. Limitations and recommendations for future research are also addressed in this chapter. It concludes with a personal reflection and thoughts on the PhD journey, highlighting how the research journey impacted me both academically and personally.

1.14 Summary of the chapter

This chapter introduced a short background of the study. It must be highlighted that there is a growing awareness in the field of inclusive education in Algeria, which succeeded to free itself from the ties of the French colonizer. Thus, a number of reforms have been implemented to ensure quality education for all and maximise equal access and participation for all individuals, including those with additional support needs. The Algerian government is increasingly committed to improve the situation and to ensure full inclusion of persons with disabilities. This appears through enacting a growing body of de facto legislations to ensure equal rights without discrimination (e.g., CRPD), yet there is a need to establish an effective policy to promote the education of learners with additional support needs (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018). Amid all these reforms, ADHD in Algeria fails to receive the necessary attention. To bring this chapter to a close, I would say in light of what has been discussed so far, there is a need to research this 'novel' topic in Algerian middle schools, where many challenges are being faced despite the ongoing discussion of inclusive education reforms.

2. Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The first chapter introduced the context of my research, highlighted the research rationale and the research questions. I will start this chapter by analysing the concept of disability, presenting contrasting interpretations of this concept- from a medical as well as a social perspective- in addition to different alternative discourses. By looking at different ramifications of disability, the chapter moves to the discourse of ADHD in order to shape a milieu where ADHD can be better understood. Furthermore, it reviews relevant literature related to teachers' experience of ADHD including their views, knowledge, and attitudes. In addition, ways to involve learners with ADHD and assist them to the best of their potentials are also addressed in this chapter. A final element in this chapter discusses the theoretical underpinning and its relevance to the present research endeavour.

2.2 Conceptualising disability

Different models tried to define and conceptualise disability differently, I will present different understandings of disability, looking critically at how it is viewed. Disability is rather a complicated term that is understood and may be viewed through different lenses. Over the years, the way society views disability has evolved leading to the development of different models namely, the medical, social and the bio-psychosocial model. Disability started as a medical condition that needs to be 'cured'. Later, the social model grew as a reaction to this model calling for the elimination of social barriers which limit the individual's participation. It stresses the need of including people with disabilities in the society by recognising their fundamental rights including the rights of education. The definition of disability moved from a medical to a social view, led by disability movement activists namely the Union of the Physically Impaired Individuals (UPIAS), a group of disabled people led by Paul Hirst and Vic Finkelstein (Shakespeare, 2017). The biopsychosocial model takes a more holistic view by recognising the complexity of disability and the interaction of biological, psychological, and social factors. Recently, there has been a shift towards emphasizing the perspective of individual strength or the neurodiversity paradigm. The following review presents different conceptualisations of disability through different models.

2.2.1 The medical model

A medical view of ADHD focuses on dysfunction and impairment (Sonuga-Barke and Thapar, 2021). Diagnosis uses a number of persistent symptoms across multiple settings- workplace, home, and school- which are targeted to treatment to reduce the impairment (APA, 2013; Sonuga-Barke and Thapar, 2021; WHO, 2019). Therefore, it views disability as a physical or a medical condition that needs to be fixed. It arises from the biomedical sciences which considers disability as a 'deviation' from the norm, a condition that requires 'medical intervention' (Berghs *et al.*, 2016). The medical paradigm expects from the learner to change to fit into the education system and the social norms. It also perpetuates the assumption that the problem is 'within-child' and views that impairment curtails their participation and limits their access, instead of focusing on how an education system might be disabling them (Graham, 2020). It can lead to discriminatory acts such as labelling and stereotyping (Grue, 2016; Shyman, 2016).

The medical profession continues to exert its power in determining what is 'normal' and 'abnormal' (Haegele and Hodge, 2016). Sociologists raise a multitude of contentious questions about its legitimacy by demonstrating how medicine fails to diagnose a defiant behaviour that has its roots in medical issues from those that are not (Rafalovich, 2015). Many critics have reacted against the medical model, calling for a move away from naturalistic or biomedical explanations. Engel is among the widely known antagonists who criticised the medical model. He regards it as a reductionist view which dismisses the individual's social environment and calls physicians to look beyond laboratories to consider the social environment (Hogan, 2019).

If we look at disability through a merely medical lens, we are encouraging the prevailing stereotypes in the field of disability that disabled people are not educable and thus causing stigmatisation and segregation which is inconsistent with the inclusive education agenda that aims to achieve equality and equity. Inclusive education acknowledges the importance of considering unique individual characteristics and calls for the creation of inclusive learning environments that provide equal opportunities for all individuals to access education (Dally *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, the medical model is based on ableist thinking which focuses on what the person can or cannot do (Graham, 2020) and ignores what the environment can do to improve the individual functioning. It also seems to offer a

narrow definition of disability which does not help to create social changes and reforms to include and accommodate disabled people. On the contrary, it may reinforce discriminatory attitudes based on ableist thinking. The social model, however, considers how the environment can be more supportive to disabled people by combating discrimination and eliminating barriers (Banbury, 2019). Nowadays, there is a shift toward strength-based models (see 2.4 for more details about the neurodiversity paradigm).

2.2.2 The social model

The social model grew out of the criticism forged against the medical model. It is considered as the development of an earlier model by Paul Hint, 1966, 24 years before Oliver's theory or the social oppression theory of disability (Bailey *et al.*, 2015), yet the latter focused more on the lived experiences in the workplace and society of disabled people. The social model views disability as a product of the physical and social obstacles created by society (Owens, 2015). This model breaks the link between disability and impairment. Impairment is linked to individual characteristics (Haegele and Hodge, 2016; Kattari, Lavery and Hasche, 2017), whereas disability refers to the disadvantage engendered by societal barriers, which restrict equal access and participation and cause social oppression (Oliver, 2013; Shakespeare, 2017). Thus, the social model does not deny the existence of mental and physical disabilities. However, it focuses more on the social aspect of disability and how we interpret it. Following this model, it is society which is responsible for disability. By favouring the word 'disabled', the social model refers to the disadvantage experienced by the person, not because of their impairment but because of barriers in the physical and social environment.

Unlike the medical model, the social model acknowledges diversity and focuses on addressing social exclusion (Rees, 2017). It is particularly helpful in educational contexts since it has the potential of providing a clear conceptual framework that assists teachers in dismantling the educational barriers and then making adjustment for learners with disability (Graham, 2020). Thus, it helps in reforming institutions to be more supportive and welcoming for individual differences. In other words, this model shares the imperative of transforming the social and physical environment to be more adaptive to disabled people's needs. Oliver (2013, p. 1025) writes "I have never seen the social model as anything more than a tool to improve peoples' lives". For instance, building ramps and lifts for people with physical disabilities may help them to have a better life quality as the absence of aids and

equipment may make them feel excluded and isolated. This means that this model aims to make reasonable adjustments which refers to “ [...] various accommodations which equalise the environment for disabled people and promote inclusion” (Shakespeare, 2017, p.16). The social model seeks to improve the quality of life for individuals with disabilities by redirecting focus towards societal barriers and addressing them effectively.

Countries nowadays are allocating time and resources to respond to the needs of learners with additional support needs and create a conducive environment for these learners, which goes against discriminatory attitudes. To embrace a social model of education, we need to shift our attention away from viewing students as having inherent deficiencies, and instead focus on the ability of the education system to provide support for a diverse range of learning needs (Naraian and Schlessinger, 2017). This means recognizing that disability is not solely the responsibility of the student to adapt to the schooling context, but rather the system should be designed to be flexible and accommodating in order to ensure that all students can thrive. It appears that the social model is empowering for learners with additional support needs by focusing on the hindrances that curtail participation and catering for their needs. It has an enormous impact by challenging discrimination and normative assumptions (Berghs *et al.* 2019). Goodley, Lawthom and Runswick Cole (2014) called for separating the normative discussion from disability studies and stated, “disability demands non-normative and anti-establishment ways of living life” (p.348). Botha and Frost (2020) identified the discrepancy between societal norms and neurodivergence as a form of ‘minority stress’, impacting the physical and mental health as well as the well-being of neurodivergent individuals. This suggests that the traditional norms and established systems may not fully cater for the needs and experiences of people with disabilities, and therefore, alternative ways of living and engaging with the world are necessary. This perspective emphasizes the importance of embracing diversity, challenging societal norms, and creating inclusive environments that accommodate and celebrate different abilities.

2.3 The Discourse of ADHD

The American Psychiatrist Association (APA) issued different editions of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Health (DSM) that addressed different psychiatric conditions. ADHD first appeared in the second edition of DSM (1968) and was labelled ‘Hyperkinetic Disease of Childhood’ which emphasised the over-activity and

impulsiveness as the core diagnostic criteria of the disorder. At that time, ADHD was defined as “ [a disorder] characterised by over-reactivity, restlessness, distractibility, short attention span, especially in young children” (APA, 1968, p.50). However, it has undergone changes in its nomenclature from Hyperkinetic Disease of Childhood in DSM-II (1968), with an excessive focus on motor activity to ADHD (DSM-III,1975), to a particular interest in the more salient symptoms of attention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity in DSM-IV (2013).

ADHD is characterized as a disorder according to medical classifications such as the DSM-IV (1994) and ICD-10. Within this framework, ADHD can be seen as an impairment, a term that neutrally describes a characteristic or condition an individual possesses. Research suggests that there are underlying neurological differences in individuals with ADHD, particularly in areas of the brain related to attention, executive function, and impulse control. Neurotransmitter imbalances, such as those involving dopamine and norepinephrine, are also thought to play a role in the manifestation of ADHD symptoms, following neuroscience (Bailey, 2015).

Two main approaches respond to impairment: the medical model and the social model. The medical model assumes that the individual with impairments should adapt to an unaltered environment, whereas the social model advocates modifying the environment to accommodate the needs of individuals with impairments. A medicalised approach to treatment supports pharmacological treatment through showing the efficacy of psychostimulants (Methylphenidate and amphetamine) and also non-stimulant drugs, atomoxetine, in regulating ADHD behaviours (Conner, 2015). In addition, medical treatment for disabilities typically aims to bring the person’s abilities in line with what is considered the accepted norm. In other words, the medical paradigm approach towards disabilities is centred on the idea of that the individual should conform to conventional standards, thereby implying that disabilities should be treated as a problem to be fixed (Pellicano and den Houting, 2022).

The medical view might offer a decontextualized idea that transcends social and contextual explanations and may lead to over-diagnosis, prejudice, and stereotypes (Batstra, van Roy and Thootenhoofd, 2022; te Meerman *et al.*, 2017). In other words, this model occludes experiences from the analysis of disability, giving a decontextualized account of the

phenomenon (Timimi and Taylor, 2004). Proponents of the medical model seem to downplay the role of social and cultural values in the diagnosis and the prevalence of ADHD (Smith, 2017). Responding to ADHD solely through a medical lens may result in disregarding the cultural and social significance of the condition, potentially obscuring its broader social implications. This idea of 'universalising' or 'Americanising' ADHD symptoms calls for applying a rigid medical system regardless of the area's local beliefs and cultural attitudes toward the condition. Although pharmacological treatment is used to manage the behaviour of learners with ADHD, they cannot target the wide array of difficulties faced by these learners (DuPaul and Stoner, 2003). My argument is that while science has advanced our understanding of various conditions and provided different tools for diagnosing certain conditions, it is equally important to take into account social issues. This is because considering social factors can contribute to promoting inclusivity in society, by acknowledging the impact of the social environment on individuals' experiences and well-being and also changing the environment to respond to the needs of learners with ADHD.

Using the social model to respond to the needs of learners with ADHD is particularly important as these learners need special assistance to achieve educational, social, and emotional success. Learners with ADHD need special academic support such as classroom modifications in comparison to their developed peers (Barkley, 2016), so tailoring the classroom approaches according to the educational and social needs of individuals with ADHD is also needed. This non-pharmacological intervention is being used to address the academic and the behavioural needs of these learners.

The medical paradigm suggests that learners with ADHD have sustained attention deficit (Liu et al., 2018). Recently, there is a shift from the deficit to strength-based model which acknowledges human diversity, individual strengths, and experiences (Doyle, 2020). This implies that individuals with ADHD may not be physically or mentally impaired, but rather have distinct cognitive abilities. Therefore, perceiving people with neurodevelopmental conditions, according to the neurodiversity paradigm, as unhealthy individuals with defective brain might be a false accusation. The argument laid out in the next section is concerned with exploring neurodiversity. It elucidates the intricacies associated with this particular paradigm in comprehensive detail.

2.4 ADHD and Neurodiversity

Recently, proponents of the neurodiversity paradigm criticised the neurological evidence of the medical model. They claim that the medical paradigm fosters an unnecessary reliance on medical professionals, dissuading children, and their families from utilizing their own capabilities to address challenges (Timimi and Taylor, 2004). Timimi's argument (2022) suggests that conditions like autism and ADHD may not be definitive medical diagnoses based on objective criteria. Instead, they are experiences or behaviours that can be interpreted and categorized subjectively by the person making the diagnosis. This implies that the classification and understanding of these conditions may vary based on the perspective, interpretation, and judgments of the individual making the diagnosis, highlighting the influence of subjectivity in the diagnostic process. Timimi and Timimi (2015) employed the term 'social construction' which indicates how individuals with shared cultural values and beliefs are described as collectively shaping or 'socially constructing' their perception and comprehension of the surrounding world.

Neurodiversity emphasizes the advantages of having a wide range of cognitive abilities and thinking styles in our society, recognizing that individuals with different neurological profiles can offer unique perspectives and skills that can contribute to the complexity and richness of our world (Rentenbach, Prislowsky and Gabriel, 2017). This perspective aims to reframe existing perspectives to better reflect the diverse experiences and insights of those within the ADHD communities (Bertilsdotter Rosqvist et al., 2023). In other words, this reflects an intention to move away from potentially limited or one-dimensional perspectives to embrace a more inclusive understanding that incorporates the richness of varied experiences within the ADHD communities.

Therefore, to resolve the dilemma of the medical model, physicians may need to address disability as a form of human diversity rather than a 'problem' to be 'fixed'. This can promote feelings of self-worth and foster active involvement in various activities (Bozic, Lawthom and Murray, 2017; Sonuga-Barke and Thapar, 2017). There is some evidence to suggest that individuals with ADHD may possess certain cognitive strengths such as problem-solving, creativity, intuition, reasoning, and abstract thinking (Ek *et al.*, 2007; Smalley, 2008; Taylor et al., 2020). ADHD was also associated with 'hyperfocus', a term that is employed to describe the heightened, concentrated attention state often reported by

individuals with ADHD (Hupfeld et al., 2019). Scholars stressed the association between ADHD and an interest-based nervous system as ADHDers have difficulty concentrating on tasks that are not intrinsically rewarding (Dodson, 2022; Hupfeld, Abagis and Shah, 2019). Research also indicates that children with ADHD possess a specific mindset that flourishes in environments featuring novelty, while concurrently avoiding boredom and uniformity (Maisel, 2022).

Therefore, ADHD is characterized by inconsistent attention rather than a deficit in attention. Rather than hyperactivity and attention deficit, 'pace/pacing' and 'variable attention' are used instead to describe ADHD behaviours (Hallowell and Ratey, 2021). From this viewpoint, ADHD is not characterized as a damaged or faulty nervous system; rather, it is a nervous system that effectively operates according to its unique set of rules (Dodson, 2022). Dodson (2022) emphasizes that, rather than a deficit in attention, individuals with ADHD tend to allocate excessive attention to various stimuli and exhibit inconsistent attention. This implies that individuals with ADHD may have cognitive strengths and abilities in certain domains, which challenges the conventional perception of ADHD as solely a deficit-based condition. These strengths could potentially be harnessed and utilized in appropriate contexts, suggesting a more nuanced understanding of ADHD and the potential for leveraging these strengths in various aspects of life, including education, work, and personal development.

Bailey (2015) proposed that the various assumptions that lurk behind the narrative of ADHD fail to explain what ADHD is. Instead, they describe the effects or consequences associated with ADHD, emphasizing actions or phenomena linked to this concept. To move beyond this limited perspective and gain a deeper understanding, Bailey suggests that it is essential to explore how the things we perceive, like ADHD, have been constructed and are continuously upheld. In other words, to truly understand ADHD, one needs to examine the processes by which the concept was developed, how it is defined, and how societal perceptions and norms contribute to its maintenance. Bailey (2015) emphasizes the importance of looking beyond surface-level descriptions and delving into the underlying constructs and perspectives that shape our understanding of ADHD.

2.5 ADHD in the context of schooling

ADHD often manifests as a behavioural condition which leads to behavioural and academic difficulties (DuPaul and Stoner, 2014). Learners with ADHD find difficulties sustaining attention, multi-tasking and organising work (APA, 2013). Therefore, coping with educational requirements would be difficult for them. They can exhibit various behaviours that can have negative effects on their academic performance as well as that of their classmates in the learning environment. These behaviours can take different forms and may interfere with their ability to learn and pay attention in class, disrupt the learning of other students, and create challenges for teachers in managing the classroom (DuPaul and Jimerson, 2014). According to Berenguer Forner *et al.* (2017), individuals with ADHD may experience challenges in maintaining relationships with friends or peers, as well as seeking social approval. This finding indicates that they may experience lower levels of peer acceptance.

The relationship of teachers with learners who have ADHD is also characterised by conflict and less emotional stability (Crum, Waschbusch and Willoughby, 2016). Arguably, Roger *et al.* (2015) concur with Crum, Waschbusch and Willoughby (2016) and found that the relationship between teachers and learners with ADHD is less emotionally close. The results of Ewe's study (2019) reflect those studies as he suggests that students with ADHD tend to feel less connected to their teachers compared to their non-ADHD peers, which is consistent with the teachers' own observations. As a result, teachers often experience less emotional attachment, reduced collaboration, and more instances of conflict in their interactions with learners with ADHD as compared to their interactions with other learners. These findings are also reflected by other studies (Prino *et al.*, 2016; Zendarski *et al.* 2020) which found that children with ADHD have more conflict and less favourable relationships with their teachers compared to children without ADHD.

2.5 Teachers' perspectives on ADHD

Due to the high prevalence of ADHD, teachers are bound to meet learners with ADHD. Teachers who have worked with learners with ADHD have a wealth of first-person experience of learners with ADHD. Their experiences, insights and conceptualisations should be captured to usefully inform current research and enhance the education for learners

with ADHD. In addition, cultivating more favourable attitudes among teachers could enhance the educational achievements and overall school experience of disabled students (Mulholland and Cumming, 2016). Overall, teachers' attitudes and understanding of ADHD are crucial for the successful classroom techniques (Mohammed, 2018).

Teachers usually experience the unruly behaviour of learners with ADHD as being largely 'disruptive'. In addition, they often face challenges to teach these learners (Hornby, 2015; Mulholland, Cumming and Lee, 2023). Cueli *et al.* (2022) conducted a study to investigate the knowledge and attitudes of 417 pre-service and 170 in-service teachers from Spain. The study revealed that a significant majority of pre-service teachers (73%) and in-service teachers (86.5%) reported finding ADHD-type behaviours annoying in the classroom.

Teachers usually talk about the interaction with learners with ADHD as being anxiety-provoking (Roger *et al.* 2015). The results from Mulholland, Cumming and Jung (2015) study showed that the majority of teachers held negative attitudes towards students with ADHD, with many perceiving these students to be disruptive, challenging, and difficult to manage in the classroom. Teachers also reported feeling unsupported in their efforts to meet the needs of learners with ADHD and expressed a need for more training and resources to help them better understand and support these students. Different studies found that teaching learners with ADHD is associated with an increase in teachers' stress levels (Greene *et al.*, 2002; Mulholland, Cumming, and Jung, 2016; Mulholland, Cumming and Lee, 2023).

Similarly, according to a study conducted by Anderson, Watt and Shanley (2017), many in-service teachers hold disapproving beliefs about working with students with ADHD. They reported that teaching these students can be frustrating, stressful, and tiring. In other words, teachers feel overwhelmed and exhausted when working with students with ADHD, which may negatively impact their ability to effectively support these students in the classroom.

Developing a positive attitude toward learners with ADHD is crucial as teachers who have a negative attitude toward these learners tend to underestimate their power and ability to deal with troublesome situations (Khalil, 2019). Overall, the above studies highlight that the behaviour displayed by learners with ADHD may result in teachers' stress and in a perceived sense of challenge in dealing with them. In addition, teachers may experience other

structural challenges that inhibit the accommodation of these learners as being largely annoying. For instance, Naude and Meier (2019) investigated South-African experiences of teaching learners with ADHD and found that large class size challenges the inclusion of these learners in the South African context. On similar lines, Braude and Dwarika (2020) reported, through conducting seven interviews, that class size and curriculum workload played a major role in teachers' experience of teaching learners with ADHD. Large class sizes are a common issue across developing countries (Srivastava, de Boer and San Pijl, 2015). Hoadjli and Latreche (2020) found that class size impedes Algerian teachers' ability to accommodate learners with diverse needs. In addition, Kirby (2017) suggests that the demanding curriculum intensifies the stress teachers face in ensuring that every learner is accommodated and supported effectively.

The above studies highlight the complex challenges that teachers may face when working with learners with ADHD and the importance of providing adequate support and making reasonable adjustments to help teachers manage these classrooms. Through reviewing the literature, it became apparent that existing research on Algerian teachers' views and attitudes toward ADHD is relatively sparse. In Africa, little is known about ADHD (Ayano, Yohannes & Abraha, 2020). Evidence-based knowledge about Algerian teachers' journeys in inclusive classrooms is lacking. Only one study to date was conducted by Hoadjil and Latrache (2020) on Algerian middle school teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education; it was found that teachers need further assistance to carry out inclusive practices. However, no study, to the best of my knowledge, has been conducted to investigate Algerian teachers' perspectives on ADHD.

In general, the studies, discussed above, emphasized the intricate difficulties that teachers may encounter while instructing students with ADHD. This highlights the significance of bringing attention to the experiences of Algerian teachers, with a specific emphasis on their obstacles, feelings, and perspectives. On that account, giving voice to Algerian teachers to speak about their journey of accommodating learners with ADHD is crucial. This would also be important for teachers who have not had such experiences yet.

2.6 Teachers' knowledge

Teachers' knowledge of ADHD is critical for teacher-learner interaction (Mohammed, 2018). It is also crucial for the interaction between teachers and parents (Al-Moghamhsi and Al-johani, 2018; Mohr-Jensen *et al.*, 2019). This provides an argument of equipping teachers with adequate knowledge regarding ADHD.

Many studies focused on measuring teachers' knowledge of ADHD. However, they mostly relied on true/false questionnaires (Sciutto *et al.*, 2016). It is important to note that teachers' knowledge has been studied and explored quantitatively. Researchers quantified teachers' understanding of ADHD using some measures including scales and questionnaires. Jerome, Gordon, and Hustler (1994) invented the ADHD knowledge scale that was used to assess 1289 elementary school teachers' knowledge of ADHD (439 American teachers and 850 Canadian), with the majority of the sample being women. This scale was simple to administer, and it inspired many researchers in this field. However, Sciutto, Terjesen and Frank. (2000) found it to be misleading as a measurement to evaluate teachers' knowledge of ADHD since it is based on a dichotomous format. This might increase the possibility of guessing the correct answer (Soroa, Gorostiaga and Balluerka, 2013). The Knowledge of Attention Deficit Disorders Scale (KADDS) by Sciutto, Terjesen and Frank (2000) replaced this scale and was administered to examine knowledge and misperception of ADHD in New York states. This scale covers the main areas in ADHD knowledge: including general information related to ADHD, symptoms/diagnosis, treatment, and was completed by a sample of 149 teachers. Unlike previous scales, this KADDS has a three-option format (true, false, do not know) which reduces the possibility of guessing correct answers, albeit to a limited extent. In addition, this scale helps researchers to identify gaps in knowledge since participants are given the choice to respond with a don't know option (Soroa, Gorostiaga and Balluerka, 2013). The scales mentioned above are the most popular and the most frequently used tools to assess teachers' level of knowledge.

Through using KADDS with Canadian teachers, Blotnick-Gallant *et al.* (2015) found that participants answered an average of 68% of the questions answered correctly. On similar lines, Shroff, Hardikar-Sawant and Prabhudesai (2017) used KADDS to examine Indian teachers' knowledge of ADHD. A sample of 106 teachers from different grades in 12 schools in the city of Mumbai, ranging from pre-school to high school, took part in this study which

showed moderate knowledge of ADHD with 49 % correct responses. Compared with Blotnicky-Gallant *et al.* (2015), Shroff, Hardikar- Sawant and Prabhudesai (2017) reported lower rates of teachers' knowledge, with 49% of correct answers. A commonly held misperception by Indian teachers seems to be a tendency to link ADHD to dietary management by reducing sugar and additives, unlike participants in Blotnicky-Gallant *et al.* (2015) who disagreed with this statement. Two studies (Guerra and Brown, 2012; Moore, 2021) were conducted to evaluate middle teachers' knowledge of ADHD in South-Texas and South-Virginia. Teachers, in these studies, had significant knowledge regarding symptoms and diagnosis, yet they showed notable knowledge deficiencies surrounding its causes and outcomes.

In Arab countries, comparable results were recorded. Al-Moghamhsi and Al-Johani (2018) used the KADDS to assess 416 elementary school teachers knowledge in Saudi-Arabia. The results of this study showed that the teachers had insufficient knowledge about ADHD, with only 38% of the responses being correct. This is corroborated in Alshehri *et al.* (2021) study designed to evaluate 100 primary school teachers' knowledge in Saudi-Arabia, which revealed insufficiency in teachers' knowledge regarding ADHD. In Egypt, Awadalla, Ali and Eissa (2016) conducted a study to evaluate 39 Egyptian teachers' knowledge across four primary schools and showed that teachers had a moderate knowledge about ADHD. Additionally, only a small number of teachers reported having received training on ADHD. Gaastra *et al.* (2020) found that there is a large gap in Dutch teachers' knowledge of effective CMSs. The findings from Gaastra *et al.* (2020) corroborate those of Blotnicky-Gallant *et al.* (2015) who found that Canadian primary school teachers expressed a desire to know more about how to manage learners with ADHD. This suggests that teachers may not have the necessary knowledge to effectively support students with ADHD in their classrooms.

These studies were successful in bringing insights into teachers' knowledge of ADHD. They demonstrated deficiencies in teachers' knowledge of the nature of ADHD and how to manage learners with ADHD. They utilized research tools in the form of scales that employed leading questions typically presented in a dichotomous or trichotomous format, such as yes/no or I know/I don't know (Soroa, Gorostiaga and Balluerka, 2013). Quantitative approach to data collection would fail to capture idiosyncrasies and multiple perceptions of

reality since it assumes the existence of a single objective reality that is free from individual beliefs. This may limit participants' voices and provide less opportunity to express their needs and talk about their experiences in more depth.

After a critical examination of these tools and international literature, it appears that existing publications are mostly aligned to a medical conceptualisation of ADHD since they are usually formulated based on the DSM that is used by medical professionals who rely on a number of symptoms derived from the medical world to diagnose children with ADHD (Thongseiratch and Worachotekamjorn, 2016). These scales were limited to certain themes which are usually biomedically focused, therefore limiting teachers' answers to a confined medical understanding of ADHD. In addition, the DSM tends to concentrate primarily on the individual, overlooking the potential impact of external factors and constraint (Pellicano and den Houting, 2022).

Overall, they 'measure' teachers' knowledge of ADHD and do not leave space for open-ended answers. This study, however, acknowledges multiple perspectives and realities via adopting a constructivist ontology and IPA as an approach to data collection to investigate teachers' experiences and level of understanding of ADHD, giving them a freedom to express themselves via a number of open-ended questions through SSI_s and FGD_s. It yielded interesting findings on teachers' conceptualisations that were grouped in a way to show commonalities and differences in participants' answers. Significantly, qualitative research exploring teachers' views and conceptualisations remain largely unexplored (Ward, Kovshoff and Kreppner, 2021) since most studies use quantitative measures to gauge teachers' understanding. Two qualitative studies have researched educators' views on ADHD, focusing on the causes of the condition (Moore, Russel and Ford, 2016) or the strategies practitioners use to address ADHD in the classroom (Moore *et al.*, 2017). Russel, Moore and Ford (2016) conducted a qualitative study with 41 educational practitioners from 223 schools in the Southwest of England, who have various roles including teaching, and found that the causes of ADHD were perceived to be biological, environmental, or a combination of both. Despite acknowledging a limited understanding of the condition, some participants believed that biological factors played a major role in the development of ADHD.

It is important to highlight that that most studies focused on primary or secondary school teachers' knowledge. On the other hand, limited investigations have delved into middle

school teachers' perspectives and understanding of ADHD (Guerra and Brown, 2012; Moore, 2021). Consequently, there exists a necessity to conduct further research in this specific domain by investigating how middle school teachers view and conceptualise the condition of ADHD.

Based on this current research study, an investigation into Algerian middle school teachers' knowledge is needed as it will provide information about their current understanding of ADHD and ways to address their lack of knowledge.

2.7 Teachers' training

Developing teachers effectively to meet the continuous demands of the job has different implications. Professional training is crucial to carry out inclusive practices effectively (Schuelka, 2018). Training interventions for teachers on ADHD are especially critical to enhance their understanding of ADHD, equip them to establish a classroom environment that is supportive of students with ADHD, and help them develop effective strategies to manage problem behaviours associated with ADHD (Ward *et al.*, 2022). In addition, it has the potential of enhancing their understanding of ADHD and reduce any misunderstandings they may have about the condition (Barkley, 2015; Mohr-Jensen *et al.*, 2019).

Boudersa (2016) and Soledji (2015) agree on the crucial role of training for enhancing the quality of education in the Algerian system, Boudersa (2016, p.1-2) claimed:

It is always an urgent educational need that teachers should receive adequate educational and professional training to possess adequate knowledge and teaching skills and to be able to dedicate themselves to the teaching profession. Most important also is the fact that, if provided to teachers, programmes of training and professional development have to be introduced, mentored, and evaluated, on a regular basis, by experts in the field

As the above quotation highlights, training helps to provide teachers with the necessary knowledge to practice their job. In addition, it helps them to get a conceptual understanding of ADHD to interact with these learners more effectively (Gwernan-Jones *et al.*, 2016). It works to provide them with knowledge and skills necessary to manage challenging behaviour and improve educational, social, and emotional outcomes (Zentall and Javorsky, 2007).

Different studies suggest that ADHD training programs could be an effective way to improve educators' knowledge and reduce misconceptions about ADHD (Alkahtani et al., 2013; Guerra et al., 2017; Lasisi et al., 2017; Sciutto et al. 2016). In 2017, Lasisi and colleagues conducted a research study to assess the impact of a teacher training program on Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) in primary schools, and to determine the attitudes of teachers towards students with ADHD. The study involved a total of 84 primary school teachers who participated in the training program and were included in the sample. The results indicate that teachers who received the training had better knowledge (in terms of knowledge about ADHD and ways to deal with these learners) and less negative attitudes. A possible implication from this discussion is that increasing knowledge and training regarding ADHD may help teachers to feel more efficacious in teaching. However, there is a paucity of evidence which confirms this conclusion (Latouche and Gascoigne, 2019), yet it is undeniable that teachers with more knowledge regarding ADHD are better equipped to support learners with ADHD (Alkahtani, 2013; Bradshaw and Kamal, 2013). Knowledge is another important factor that helps teacher to pursue their career.

It appears that providing teachers with adequate knowledge is necessary for their professional practice. Unfortunately, Djouima (2016) found that training does not usually meet Algerian teachers' needs and expectations especially when it comes to managing the classroom. In addition, Soladji (2015), UNESCO (2015) and Boudersa (2016) link the low ranking of the educational system to the quality of training. Results from previous studies indicate that teachers seem unable to provide the necessary support for learners with ADHD due to their lack of training (Alkahtani, 2013; Melhem, 2020; Mohr-Jensen et al. 2019). Surprisingly, a number of studies have identified that teachers had no prior training regarding ADHD. Guerra et al. (2017) used a survey design to investigate how teachers' education affects their knowledge and understanding of ADHD. Surprisingly, they found that 60.7 % of teachers had no prior coursework focused on teaching learners with ADHD. This finding prompts questions regarding the level of awareness among stakeholders and the amount of focus directed towards ADHD. This finding is echoed in another study conducted by Mohr-Jensen et al. (2019) who reported that out of 528 teachers, 42% had not received any prior training. Among the total sample, 62.5% of the teachers felt that they did not possess sufficient knowledge about ADHD. This finding is echoed in another study by Alanazi

and Alturki (2021) which took place in Riyadh city, Saudi Arabia, who found that only a small number of teachers who took part in their study had prior training on ADHD while the majority acquired knowledge about ADHD through informal sources such as reading books and browsing websites.

Training interventions can occur at various stages of teachers' professional careers. Several studies have concluded that pre-service training is not effective in adequately preparing teachers to tackle the persistent challenges associated with teaching in an inclusive classroom environment. Stites *et al.* (2018) found pre-service training ineffective to prepare teachers for the realities of the inclusive setting. This also corroborates Liang and Gao's study (2016) which reported that teachers, in their study, found the training they received insufficient to provide a good accommodation for inattentive and hyperactive learners. They identified lack of knowledge and pragmatic experience as barriers to a proper inclusion for learners with ADHD. Similarly, Poznanski, Hart and Cramer (2018) indicate significant deficiencies in the understanding of ADHD and classroom management strategies among pre-service teachers. In other words, the results show that there are substantial disparities or inadequacies in the knowledge that pre-service teachers have about these topics. They concluded that teachers in their study would benefit from further professional development opportunities. These findings call the usefulness of these pre-service teachers' training into question.

Similar to the above findings, Ward *et al.* (2020) suggested that teachers who received pre-service training believed that it was not effective in preparing them to address ADHD. This might be due to the fact that the period of time allocated for learning and developing various knowledge and skills necessary for the classroom is limited during initial teacher training (ITT). On the other hand, a meta-analysis conducted by Ward and colleagues in 2022 indicated that teacher training programs for ADHD that included ongoing coaching and support for teachers were more effective than those which did not, yet having disconnected and one-off training may not assist them in responding to the requirements of different situations.

The overall implication from the above discussion points to the importance of teachers' training. In addition, the picture is that many teachers have not received significant or any ADHD training. As indicated by the above-mentioned studies, teachers often feel ill-

equipped to handle difficult behaviour in the classroom, and this is because teacher education programs tend to place little emphasis on classroom management. In other words, there is a lack of attention or emphasis on teaching classroom management skills in teacher education, which leaves new teachers feeling unprepared to deal with challenging behaviour in the classroom.

It should be highlighted that development should be thought of as a continuous process to help teachers meet the continuing demands. This leads to the view that professional development should be considered an ongoing process and should acknowledge personal as well as contextual factors that are likely to shape it. Boud and Hager (2012) argue that professional learning opportunities should be “situated” (p. 27) via integrating CPD into teachers’ daily practices. Liang and Gao (2016) and Strelow *et al.* (2021) concluded that more effective training should be provided for teachers to prepare them fully for the challenging task. Consistently, 92 % of teachers in Greenway and Rees Edwards (2020) study expressed their desire for additional training. In addition, several studies have identified a requirement for more continuous professional development (CPD) to fill gaps in knowledge and improve professional competence (ComRes, 2017; Sciutto *et al.*, 2016). CPD is key in successful inclusive education (Schuelka, 2018; UNESCO, 2017).

It is possible to assume that traditional training models are less successful in producing positive outcomes. This suggests that more effective and sustainable solutions are required in the long term. In addition, considering different modes of professional development that foster individual and collaborative work would be more advantageous.

2.8 Modes of professional learning

Professional development typically refers to organized training programs provided by educational institutions, which are led by trainers or instructors. The purpose of such programs is to equip educators with the skills and knowledge necessary to meet the learning objectives of their students and their department. Kennedy (2005) argues that this type of training:

supports a skills-based, technocratic view of teaching whereby CPD provides teachers with the opportunity to update their skills in order to be able to demonstrate their competence. It is generally

‘delivered’ to the teacher by an ‘expert’, with the agenda determined by the deliverer, and the participant placed in a passive role.

The above quotation implies that traditional training advocates a top-down approach which is typically administered by an expert, who determines the agenda, while the teacher assumes a passive role as a participant. However, it is important that teacher development programs should incorporate various learning modes that engage teachers and allow them to play an active role in building their professional knowledge (Keavy, Carse and Jess, 2019). This means providing opportunities for teachers to participate in the learning process and contribute to the construction of their own knowledge in a bottom-up fashion.

A combination of professional development opportunities is likely to provide teachers with ample opportunities to advance their understanding of classroom practices. In Wenger’s (1998) view (cited in Kennedy, 2005), a community of practice should develop a shared understanding of their common goals and objectives, thereby enabling its members to have a degree of influence over the direction and priorities of the community’s activities. This means that members should have the ability to shape and direct the community’s work, based on their shared understanding of what is important and relevant to the group. By creating their own understanding of the joint enterprise, the community can ensure that it remains relevant and responsive to its members’ needs, while also fostering a sense of ownership and engagement among its participants.

The above discussion suggests that teachers’ education should also include and encourage informal modes of learning including cooperation with colleagues and other people in teachers’ workplace environment. In addition, through ongoing reflection, each teacher can actively participate in their professional development. Kosnik *et al.* (2015) argues that CPD should include self-reflective practice. Husband (2015) contends that ideas constructed throughout teachers’ careers raise their awareness of their CPD needs. Similarly, Herbert and Rainford (2017) claim that meaningful CPD occurs through reflection and experiencing.

Maley (1989) argued.

[T]he aim of professional activity should be to keep the teacher’s sense of plausibility alive and, therefore, open to influence by the

ongoing experience of teaching and interaction with other teachers'
perceptions and senses of plausibility (in Maley, 2018, p.28)

It is highly important to treat teachers as active learners who construct personal beliefs throughout their careers which are likely to provide lessons for future teachers in similar contexts, helping them to learn from the expertise of others.

The above views about CPD reflect its complex nature which translates into individuals and their organisation having input into what CPD opportunities should incorporate to promote development. They suggest that teachers should be given voice to structure their CPD. In other words, it is worth giving some consideration to teachers' suggestions as this would help to make CPD more effective. This would also assist in generating empirically validated knowledge which breaks the gap between theory and practice of teaching. Therefore, equipping teachers individually and collectively to support and shape their practice is crucial as education is always in a state of flux. Development should be regarded as a life-long career requiring individuals to have input into what makes them better prepared to manage their teaching.

2.9 Language teachers' emotions and emotional labour

Instructors' mental well-being influences the quality of their teaching and students' emotions (Mercer, 2018). Emotions are viewed as states connected to communication and actions. They form a vital element in how teachers shape their identity by establishing emotional loops. As highlighted by Benesch (2017), emotions shape an individual's sense-making and understanding. Dewell and Paulsco (2019) highlight that emotions have a remarkable impact on the process of teaching and learning the English language.

Emotions are also perceived as a sociocultural phenomenon primarily influenced by not only individual traits but also by interpersonal relationships and the broader societal environment (Richards, 2020). Zembylas (2005) views emotions as 'discursive practices' (p. 936) and argues that 'power, agency and resistance are at the centre of exploring the role of emotion' (p.936). Viewing emotions as 'discursive practices' implies that emotions are not just internal feelings but are also constructed and expressed through language and communication within a given social and cultural context. According to this viewpoint, when teachers experience emotional challenges, it is not indicative of a deficiency in their ability

to manage emotions or lack of emotional intelligence. Instead, these emotional struggles mirror the difficult or inequitable circumstances they encounter within classrooms, schools, and the broader societal context (Benesch, 2020). Song (2018) encouraged teachers to engage in 'emotional resistance to hegemonic discourse and unfair practices' (p. 464). This involves expressing emotions in a way that questions established societal and institutional norms and practices that are considered unfair and biased.

Teachers experience various emotions while teaching which necessitates a need for regulation and control (Benesch, 2020; Song, 2021). This process of regulating and managing emotions is referred to as 'emotional regulation, self-regulation, emotional literacy and emotional intelligence' (Benesch, 2020, p.27). Emotional regulation is crucial to establish a favourable connection with learners, foster a sense of enjoyment, and effectively handle any anxieties (Dewaele, Gkonou and Mercer, 2018). Favoured emotions include 'confidence, optimism and passion' (Dewaele, 2018, p.482), as well as 'empathy, respect, trust, and responsiveness' (Gkonou and Mercer, 2017, p.42).

Benesch (2012) has advocated for research into the relationship between teacher emotions and language instruction, suggesting that integrating emotions into critical English language teaching (ELT) can bring about pedagogical change. Through her groundbreaking research on emotions within language classrooms, Benesch (2012) asserts that teachers acknowledging a range of emotions in both themselves and their students during instruction, including negative ones, could lead to pedagogical improvement and personal growth. Therefore, it is incumbent on researchers to take a closer look at teachers' emotions within the institution.

Teachers may also experience the tension between the job requirements and their internal feelings. This is referred to as 'emotional labour' a term coined by Arlie Hochschild (1983), which involves expressing, suppressing, or managing emotions as part of their job to meet the emotional and relational demands of their students, colleagues, and the educational environment. Hochschild (1983) argues that engaging in emotional labour can be harmful to employees, potentially resulting in 'alienation'. This alienation manifests when individuals disconnect from their authentic selves to display emotions that align with the broader societal or organizational context. However, teachers engage in emotional labour not only to adhere to pre-determined emotional rules but also because they perceive such

endeavours as crucial for achieving their teaching objectives and fostering favourable learning outcomes (Sutton, Mudery-Camino, and Knight, 2009). For instance, teachers must regulate their own anger within the classroom, express sympathy in uncomfortable situations, show care for their students' development, consistently offer encouragement to both students and their parents, and engage in cooperative efforts with their peers. Larrivee (2012, p.37) argued that 'teaching is emotional labour'. Zaretsky and Katz (2019) argued that teachers consistently experience emotional labour due to a higher prevalence of problematic behaviours in the classroom when compared to other professional settings.

Research on language teachers' emotions has gained momentum. Different studies have explored English language teachers' emotions. Miller and Gkonou (2018) explored how emotional labour and personal agency influence the experiences of emotional rewards among educators in tertiary-level English language programs in the UK and the US. During interviews, participants acknowledged experiencing emotional stress due to the relational demands of their job, yet they were committed to an approach of "teaching-as-caring" and found psychological benefits in establishing strong connections with their students (Miller and Gkonou, 2018,p. 54). Another finding was that with increased experience, teachers became more adept at managing their emotions by learning to distance themselves emotionally or physically from challenging situations. Humphries (2020) found that students' behavioural issues gave rise to teachers' emotional labour. In the context of the study by Humphries (2020), it suggests that when students exhibit behavioural issues such as disruptions, defiance, or emotional outbursts in the classroom, teachers must invest additional emotional labour to stay calm, provide support, manage conflicts, and create a positive learning environment. This emotional labour can include staying patient, empathizing with students, de-escalating tense situations, and maintaining a professional demeanour despite the challenges presented by the students' behaviour.

Overall, these studies suggest that educators frequently engage in emotional labour during their interactions with students. This can be to cultivate motivation, establish favourable relationships, demonstrate care, or manage difficult student behaviour.

2.10 Teachers' agency

Teachers are important agents in schools as they have an influential role in initiating changes to promote inclusivity (Pellicano, Bölte and Stahmer, 2018). Various studies

underscored the significance of affording teachers the opportunity to exercise their own agency (e.g., Babino and Stewart, 2018; Sánchez-Suzuki Colegrove and Zúñiga, 2018; Glas, 2016). Priestley et al. (2012) views teachers as reflexive agents whose thoughts and actions are 'influenced by, but not determined by society' (p.197). This implies that teachers possess a level of autonomy and reflective capacity in their thinking and actions. While their thoughts and behaviours are influenced by societal factors, they are not rigidly dictated or controlled by these external influences as they have the ability to critically reflect on the societal context, understand its impact on their roles, and make informed decisions based on this awareness. It suggests that teachers can exercise their professional judgment and adapt to their specific educational contexts, considering societal influences without being completely bound by them. This perspective underscores the importance of agency and critical reflection in teaching practice. For educators, agency can be demonstrated through an individual's transformative actions, such as introducing innovations into their teaching methods (Eteläpelto, 2013). The correlation between agency and personal change or transformation can manifest in various ways, including adaptation and accommodation, where individuals exercise agency by interacting actively with the social context (Kitayama and Uchida, 2005; Markus and Kitayama, 2003). Through an adaptive orientation, individuals actively shape their own responsiveness to the environment as they engage in agentic actions (Emirbayer and Mische, 1998). Agency can also manifest through teachers' resistance to maintain the status quo in the current education system (Pyhältö et al.,2012; Vähäsantanen,2015).

Certain researchers highlight personal or internal factors that either facilitate or impede agency in various contexts, such as past accomplishments, knowledge, experiences, and individual values (Pantić, 2017). A recent international study into the perception and demonstration of agency by Oolbekkink-Marchand et al. (2017) indicated that agentic behaviour can be influenced by factors beyond the immediate context. Others recognize that teachers' agency is not solely determined by individual factors, but also by contextual factors. Rogers and Wetzell (2013) advocated for an enhanced comprehension of the patterns of language and communication that shape teacher agency, the environments where agency becomes evident. Similarly, Priestley *et al.* (2016) propose that agency should be understood within specific situations. It follows that agency is not only a characteristic of

an individual, but also a product of the context in which they are situated. Therefore, it seems crucial to consider the different tensions that exist in teachers' social sphere and the different factors that might shape and promote teachers' agency. The present study focuses on teachers' challenges to explore how they can practice their agency. In addition, it is important to note that for agency to flourish, both individual and contextual factors should be considered. Teachers' experiences help to map individual and contextual influences on their ability to function in their teaching environments, providing future prospects to enhance their agency.

2.11 Managing and involving learners with ADHD in the classroom.

Teachers can adopt a number of classroom strategies to help learners with ADHD academically and socially (LaTouche and Gascoigne, 2019). Educational strategies have positive effects on academic and behavioural outcomes of children with ADHD (Forresi *et al.*, 2020; Prinstein *et al.*, 2019) and they are particularly useful for youth with ADHD (Evans *et al.*, 2018).

Teaching in inclusive classrooms means that teachers are required to meet the needs of all learners. Applying a number of classroom strategies can be one way to address the needs of learners with ADHD. Therefore, developing knowledge regarding different classroom strategies is likely to assist teachers in meeting the needs of all learners. These strategies can take different forms and can be implemented across different contexts.

2.11.1 Behavioural strategies

The behavioural approach can be traced back to Pavlov's classical conditioning (1930) and Skinner's operant conditioning (1938) which posits that behaviours are the product of learning and can be learnt or extinguished. These might include teacher-led antecedent and consequence-based classroom strategies (Wolraich *et al.*, 2019).

Two main types of approach can be identified: reactive strategies (consequence-based), which involve consequences for behaviour, and proactive strategies (antecedent-based), which focus on addressing potential triggers or antecedents of behaviour. These strategies can be employed by teachers to manage the behaviour of learners with ADHD. They describe how teachers can address the behaviour of these learners.

- Antecedent-based strategies manipulate the environment and events before the behaviour takes place. In other words, they entail a change in antecedent-based events to prevent the occurrence of target behaviours. For example, setting classroom rules, reducing the length of the assignment, and providing students with task choices (DuPaul and Weyandt, 2011).
- Consequence-based strategies, on the other hand, target the environment after the behaviour occurs and might include praise, reprimands, token economy (e.g., poker chips, and response cost (Gaastra *et al.*, 2020) by removing tokens or reinforcers for 'disruptive' behaviour. Overall, these strategies include positive and negative reinforcement.

The above discussion has provided an overview of some important management strategies that might be useful to address the behaviour of learners with ADHD. However, these strategies focused mainly on preventive measures of 'undesirable' behaviour. According to Davis, Floridan and Ainscow (2004), the behavioural model has been criticised as it focuses exclusively on "measurable learning outcomes" (p.9). In addition, it tries to make assumptions regarding learners' motivation by selecting specific rewards and token economies. Relying solely on positive and negative reinforcement may lead to the assumption that students are passive and need external motivators to behave well, which overlooks other effective classroom management tools (Parker, Rose and Gilbert, 2016).

2.11.2 Considering alternative approaches: EFL Context

Learners with ADHD struggle with different aspects of L2 learning. Hyperactivity and impulsivity can impact spoken interaction and production by causing a lack of self-control, impatience, excessive talking, and unpredictable verbal expressions which impact the classroom dynamics (Kałdonek-Crnjaković, 2022). Research has also demonstrated that learners with ADHD experience difficulties in reading comprehension (Turketi, 2010; Miller *et al.*, 2013) and specific writing and listening difficulties (Kałdonek-Crnjaković, 2018).

English Language teachers can draw upon different strategies including: encouraging learners to deduce word meanings from context, (2) advocating for interactive learning experiences and enhancing phonological awareness (Villalobos, 2012), (3) instructing on effective study strategies (e.g., employing planning sheets or story mapping) (Davis and

Florian, 2004), (4) emphasizing focused learning of language segments, (5) delivering clear and detailed explanations of language structure mechanics, (6) facilitating student practice through repetitive exercises, (7) offering diverse content types to engage students through various approaches (Smith, 2015), and (8) utilizing personal anecdotes for additional support (Pentón-Herrera, 2020). Cabaroğlu and Tohma (2021) found that Turkish ELT teachers, in their study, utilised general classroom strategies that are not specific to ELT. This implies that ELT teachers should be trained on using classroom techniques that are more engaging and suitable to ELT. Participants in the study of Kałdonek-Crnjaković (2018) reported that ADHD affects the classroom dynamics. To address this, they reported employing a number of proactive and reactive strategies.

Mitchell and Sutherland (2020) emphasised that the learning spaces in inclusive classrooms should be made stimulating, engaging, and attractive. Therefore, it is important to acknowledge and investigate alternative approaches that can encourage active student engagement, self-discipline, and intrinsic motivation. These may include fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility for learning to reduce power imbalance, providing opportunities for student choice and autonomy, and using collaborative learning strategies that promote active participation and peer support. By exploring a range of management tools, teachers can create a dynamic and an inclusive learning environment that meets the diverse needs of their students.

My views align with Turketi (2010,p. 22) who claims that:

It is my current opinion that for teaching English to ADHD children no separate method or approach need to be developed per se, since the ESL (EFL) methodology already has a rich variety of feasible tools which can be successfully applied in teaching English to students with these learning differences.

The above quotation suggests that there is no requirement to develop a distinct method or approach solely for teaching English to children with ADHD because the ESL (EFL) methodology already offers a diverse range of effective tools that can be utilized successfully in teaching English to these learners who have unique learning needs. Bob and Konicarova (2018) argue that in the context of teaching children with ADHD, non-traditional teaching methods such as 'Communicative Language Teaching' (CLT) are particularly beneficial. These methods prioritize practical application and engagement, rather than

traditional lecture-based instruction. In addition, if an educational environment prioritizes physical activity, outdoor play, free movement, and assumes that children are naturally active, teachers are more likely to have a positive view of children with ADHD compared to environments where children are expected to sit still and remain at a desk for most of the day (Metzger and Hamilton, 2021). Therefore, it is important to encourage the adoption of approaches that encourage learners' participation and active learning. Teachers should also allow opportunities to "mingle, walk around a little, do some activities standing up, helping to move furniture or even just to change places" (Scrivener, 2012, p.232). This is because children diagnosed with ADHD often struggle in the classroom setting where they are expected to comply with regulations, sit still and pay attention (Kendall, 2016). In addition, they typically exhibit better performance in subjects that involve physical and practical activities (DuPaul and Stoner, 2014; Imerag *et al.*, 2013).

Additionally, CLT offers a plethora of cooperative learning and autonomous learning opportunities that foster learners' engagement. However, it is crucial to differentiate between the strong and weak versions of CLT. The weak version of CLT focuses on language functions and linguistic items, giving special attention to the theory of language itself. It places emphasis on teaching specific language functions and structures and incorporates activities that facilitate practice of these language components. Presentation Practice Production (PPP) exemplifies the weak version by following a specific and rigid sequence, where language components are presented, practiced, and then produced. This method highlights the systematic practice of language items within a predetermined order.

The strong version of CLT, on the other hand, prioritizes learners' active participation through meaningful activities that promote authentic communication (Richards and Rogers, 2014). Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and Project-Based Learning (PBL) align more closely with the strong version of CLT by emphasizing authentic communication and real-world tasks. Task-based approaches in language learning begin with the learner and prioritize meaningful communication (Skehan, 2021). Tasks are designed to elicit valuable and often personal expressions from learners. The language that holds significance is the language used to convey those meaningful expressions, as determined by the learner. The tasks themselves may be developed based on a needs analysis, considering how the learner will utilize the language in real-life situations (Long, 2015). The aim is for the task to serve as

a facilitator for learners to shape their language development in individualized ways, optimizing the likelihood of following personalized developmental paths rather than according to a predefined sequence that may not be suitable for everyone (Long, 2015; Ellis et al., 2020). This offers more flexibility for learners and provides them with ample opportunities to navigate their own developmental paths. Therefore, this approach recognizes that learners have unique strengths, interests, and abilities and enables them to engage with language in ways that are personally meaningful and effective for their learning journeys. Similarly, PBL is an active learner-centred instructional approach that emphasizes their active involvement in the learning process. It is characterized by promoting students' autonomy, engaging them in constructive investigations, setting meaningful goals, fostering collaboration and communication, and encouraging reflection within real-world contexts and practices (Kokotsaki, Menzies and Wiggins, 2016).

Behavioural strategies may help teachers to deal with the behaviour of learners with ADHD. However, in an EFL classroom, it is worth considering other 'communicative' techniques which would engage all learners. CLT moves away from traditional lesson planning that requires the learner to sit and listen to the teacher's instructions to classroom activities that encourage learners' engagement through role plays, group work activities and project learning (Richards, 2006). The active engagement of learners with ADHD increases their attention span (Mezzanotte, 2020). In addition, this approach addresses the communicative needs of learners which is likely to be conducive for those with ADHD who often present with problems in communication (Greene *et al.*, 2002). Besides, an important aspect of CLT classrooms is small-group activities which tend to be more engaging and motivating for learners. These include the following, according to Richards and Rogers (2006):

- Information gap activities: where learners are divided into two groups and given different pieces of information and should collaborate and exchange information to complete the task. For example, figuring out the difference between two pictures.
- Gamification and jigsaw activities: teachers often incorporate games and engaging activities to make the language learning process more enjoyable and interactive. For instance, a teacher might play three different recordings, each with a different focus, and divide the class into three groups, assigning each group a specific recording to listen to. The teacher may then rearrange and mix the groups, allowing students

from different groups to share what they learned from their recording with other students. This activity promotes communication and collaboration among students, as well as the use of language skills in a fun and engaging way.

It is recommended that teachers should vary interaction patterns through whole class work, working in pairs and groups, close and open questioning, choral responses, and individual work to make the classroom engaging and motivating (Scrivener, 2012). These activities reduce teacher talking time and enable learners to take an active role in their own learning. In addition, running dictation technique (Scrivener, 2012) involves students working collaboratively in groups to complete a dictation exercise of a sentence or a text. Each group comprises a runner who retrieves the text from a predetermined location outside the classroom, and a writer who accurately transcribes what the runner dictates.

Through advocating a socio-constructivist learning environment, CLT is likely to engage different learners who are involved in their knowledge construction. Therefore, it is possible to assume that teaching more communicatively would be more inclusive of learners with ADHD than in GTM classroom where they are required to sit throughout the lesson. Traditional approaches focusing on memorisation and rote learning often lack opportunities for interaction and communication. The typical pattern of interaction is predominantly teacher-centred, with extended periods where students are expected to engage in silent written exercises. This pattern lacks diversity compared to Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which incorporates shorter and more diverse stages of interaction. Learners with ADHD would feel more engaged in small group instruction where they had the chance to interact with each other. Besides, communicative approaches devolve agency to the learner through cooperative learning and constructing knowledge through social interaction. This approach is likely to promote the inclusive education agenda, which is based on a humanistic idea, enabling all learners to participate in schools. In addition, CLT appears to be a very functioning route for communicative competence growth and for engaging learners inside the classroom as it encourages cooperative learning.

The above review leads us to conclude that teaching in a way that emphasizes communication and interaction where students are encouraged to engage in authentic and meaningful exchanges following a learner-centred approach is likely to create a more engaging and interactive classroom. The glue that brings pupils with different needs

together is language, which enables them to engage in reciprocal interactions where the teacher is a facilitator and learners play an active role in shaping their learning.

2.12 Cross-context collaboration

Addressing the needs of learners with additional support needs requires the engagement of different parties to be more effective. In addition, this joined-up approach to dealing with the challenging behaviours of learners with ADHD may lighten the burden from the shoulders of teachers. Collaboration is stressed in the inclusive education agenda and the UNCRPD as a way to support the education of learners with additional support needs. Ainscow (2020) emphasised that the inclusion of different parties is crucial to promote the inclusive education agenda. He also stressed the importance of raising parents' awareness to work closely with teachers. Similarly, Mitchell (2015) argued that various stakeholders involved in education, such as the principal, head teachers, senior members of the school's leadership, the governing board of the school, and regional or local educational authorities should demonstrate a dedication to inclusive education. School consultation, for example, is an approach to delivering services indirectly, whereby a triadic relationship is established between a consultant, a teacher, and a student. In this model, the consultant works with the teacher to provide direct services to the student, rather than working directly with the student themselves (Park and Park, 2017). This consultant can be the school psychologist or any expert in the field. Collaborative consultation can also include partnership between parents, teachers and psychologists that can help to improve educational outcomes of learners with ADHD (DuPaul and Weyandt, 2011). Through seeking guidance and advice, individuals who lack experience can enhance their knowledge and skills by learning from the expertise of professionals (Atkinson, 2002).

While a significant amount of attention has been directed towards meeting the needs of students, there has been comparatively less emphasis on tailoring consultation services to the needs of teachers. Although teacher-focused interventions are essential, they have not been given as much consideration in the literature (Park and Park, 2017). On that account, it seems crucial to shift attention to teachers' requirements, knowledge, and beliefs to provide a comprehensive and tailored set of services to support teachers in working with students with ADHD and improving outcomes for these students in the classroom. Batstra, van Roy, and Thoutenhoofd (2022) proposed that shifting the discourse towards the needs

teachers face when addressing specific classroom challenges moves away from solely attributing difficulties to children's disorders and instead recognizes the actual problems teachers encounter while educating certain students.

Bessai (2019, p.8) considers that parents' involvement in the Algerian context as "an additional asset to the success of this project [inclusive education]". Similarly, Lawrence, Estrada and McCormick (2017) investigated 14 elementary school teachers' experiences of working with students with ADHD in North and South Carolina. Teachers who took part in this study stressed the importance of parental involvement. In their study, Hapsari *et al.* (2020) found that teachers recognized the significance of collaborating with psychologists and parents to effectively address the requirements of students with ADHD.

In a study conducted by Hoadjil and Latrache (2020) on middle school teachers, it was discovered that the Algerian teachers identified a requirement for assistance from the Ministry of National Education. Specifically, they emphasized the importance of providing more training and assistance to help them engage learners with diverse needs through parents' collaboration and further training. Therefore, they value working in partnership with different stakeholders that goes beyond the boundaries of the classroom. This multi-layered support is likely to help teachers develop their professional practice by assisting them to meet the needs of these learners.

Cooper and Hughes (2007) identified ADHD as a multifactorial condition which requires a coordinated, multi-agency approach from parents, teachers, and educational psychologists. Therefore, teaching learners with ADHD is considered a complex phenomenon, nested within the context of relationship with different actors, with varying relationships, and multiple influences. More specifically, the successful inclusion of learners with ADHD requires a joint effort between different stakeholders. In addition, a positive ethos that is embraced by the entire school community is crucial to teach learners with ADHD more efficiently (Carroll and Hurry, 2018; Lawrence *et al.*, 2017; Ward, Kałdonek-Crnjaković 2020; Kovshoff and Kreppner, 2021). Given the fact that the behaviours of children with ADHD often manifest across settings, it is also crucial for strategies to include learners with ADHD to be implemented across settings (Villodas *et al.*, 2014). Home-school communication is likely to help learners with ADHD and increase their academic outcomes (DuPaul and Weyandt, 2006). Thus, developing partnership between home and school is useful in this

context as it might lead to bridging the gap between these two settings. However, there is a potential for a lack of understanding to occur during the communication between school and home (Gwernan-Jones *et al.*, 2016; Mitchell, 2018). On that account, it seems that fostering communication between different stakeholders is crucial.

To put it in more general terms, cooperation between different parties is crucial for the development of inclusive practices. Multi-agency teams and professionals' collaboration is essential to enhance the well-being of both children and staff members (Hodkinson, 2016), yet coordination is often fragmented (DuPaul *et al.*, 2020).

Cooper and Hughes (2007, p.51) argued that effective collaboration and multi-agency working should consist of three components.

1. First, it is important for all professionals to have shared goals.
2. Professionals must effectively communicate with each other.
3. Finally, they should respect the roles and the responsibilities of those they work with.

After considering the points discussed earlier, I arrived at the conclusion that in order to safeguard the inclusion of learners with ADHD, there should be a collaboration between different stakeholders. In other words, including learners with ADHD should be a common concern for all stakeholders. In addition, it is also crucial for the support system to recognise teachers' beliefs and experiential knowledge and expertise, thereby creating a holistic approach to teachers' and learners' needs.

2.13 Theorising the research findings.

It is important to note that Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model (1998) is designed specifically to explain the process of child development. It is also used in the context of adult development. Newman and Newman (2016) stated that Bronfenbrenner's theory has been increasingly utilized to enhance the comprehension of adult development.

Bioecological model informed my understanding of teachers' experiences. It was used to contextualise the research findings and frame the recommendations. It sets the context of a system framework that influences teachers' practices. I will briefly review the bioecological model's original application and its relevance to the context of teachers' development.

More details about how this model can relate specially to teachers' experiences will be provided in the discussion chapter.

2.13.1 Bronfenbrenner's original theory

The bioecological model is a model of human development that describes the interaction of environmental and biological factors in shaping human development (Mercon-Vergas *et al.*, 2020). It was first introduced in the context of child development and focuses on the individual as the central figure in their environment. This approach is human-centred and examines how the developing child or individual may impact their own development and be influenced by their surroundings (Elliot and Davies, 2020).

Bronfenbrenner's theory placed a significant emphasis on proximal processes and the role of the individual in their own development. The interrelationships between the person and their environment in the theory were labelled as proximal processes, as stated by Davies and Elliot (2020). They refer to "complex reciprocal interactions between a person and their environment which must occur on a fairly regular basis over extended periods of time" (1995, p.620). Therefore, the *Process* dimension in Bronfenbrenner's theory represents the dual interactions between the developing person and their environment (microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem and macrosystem). Proximal processes for children include "parent-child and child-child activities, solitary or group play, reading, and learning new skills" (Bronfenbrenner, 1995, p. 620). Bronfenbrenner and Morris (2006) also referred to solo proximal processes that can be performed on the absence of other persons. This implies that children's disposition and resources might influence the power and the direction of their development. Bronfenbrenner gave examples of some solo activities including reading a book and learning a new skill (Merçon -Vergas *et al.*, 2020).

Person characteristics refer to the child's personal traits which affect the course of their own development. They are divided into three types: force, resource, and demand. Force refers to person's disposition which may enhance or impede development including motivation and persistence. Resource characteristics refer to conditions that inhibit or serve individual's development including experiential resources, skill, and knowledge (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). Demand characteristics, on the other hand, stand for the individual traits which may encourage or discourage certain reactions from the environment.

The context in which a child grows up plays a crucial role in shaping their development, which can be understood through four different systems: microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, and macrosystem. The microsystem refers to the immediate setting where the child spends most of their time, including their home and school. The mesosystem refers to cross-context collaboration between the children's parents and school, for instance. The exosystem refers to a setting that does not include the developing child such as parents' workplace. The macrosystem refers to cultural environment and attitudes in the society in which the child lives (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 1998).

Time refers to historical events that occur in the child's life. According to Bronfenbrenner (2005), developmental changes are influenced by various factors, including life events, experiences, and the environment. These factors can be external, such as environmental conditions and social interactions, or internal, such as individual characteristics and personal choices.

2.13.2 Bronfenbrenner's theory for adult development

Chu *et al.* (2021; p.2) claimed that Bronfenbrenner's theory:

provides a useful theoretical framework for studying the contexts in which teachers exist and develop; thus, it has been used frequently in research on language teacher psychology and practice

The works of Lopes (2009); Hwang (2014); Price and McCallum (2015); Edwards (2020); Chu *et al.* (2021) are all examples of studies where Bronfenbrenner's theory has been used to enlighten teachers' development. Hwang (2014) conducted research aimed at exploring the impact of the ecological contexts on the development of teacher educators (TEs) in South Korea. The study aimed to understand how various factors, such as the socio-cultural context, curriculum, and pedagogical practices, influenced the growth and development of TEs in this country. He used this framework to study the professional development of teacher educators in South Korea. It was found that the professional development of teacher educators was affected by various factors present in different ecological contexts. These contexts ranged from the institutional context, which included issues like heavy workload and limited time, to the political and social context, which entails the national educational system. Like Hwang (2014), Algerian teaching practices are influenced by

different ecological contexts including institutional ones: class size and time constraint (Bouhadiba, 2018) and national or political decisions: the top-down approach to curriculum design (Law N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008, Article 20), which is likely to create a 'hegemonic pedagogy' to meet externally imposed obligations. In addition, the substantial workload that middle school teachers are facing represents a difficulty for their professional development, and it also has an impact on the quality of their teaching (Chelli, 2014).

Lopes (2009) conducted a study to explore the lived experiences of South African teachers of learners with ADHD. Their experiences were framed within the ecological systemic view. This study reported that teachers' experiences of working alongside learners with ADHD is affected by other members of the society operating in the exosystem and macrosystem. In another study, Edwards (2021) provided a summary of the ecological influence of action research on the development of English language teachers, with a specific emphasis on the three subsystems of the ecological systems model, which are the microsystem (individual teacher) mesosystem (institutional organisation), and macrosystem (educational, political, and social values).

This framework has often been employed to address concerns related to the psychology of language teachers, such as their emotions (Chen, 2019; Sun and Yang, 2021; Cross and Hong, 2012). In Price and McCallum's (2015) study, the environmental factors were believed to affect the emotional and physical health of teachers, which in turn could impact their capacity to maintain high levels of performance. They also noted that ecological factors including classroom challenges, teachers' preparation impact teachers' 'fitness' or their ability to maintain reciprocal interaction. They recommended that teachers should develop self-awareness and self-reflection in relation to their understanding, their beliefs, abilities, goals, challenges, and ambitions. This entails identifying the areas where one has control and can make a difference, as well as recognizing the areas where external factors have more influence.

The publications of Bronfenbrenner from 1973 to 2006 clearly show the evolution of the theory from one that considers the social feature of human development to one that is more inclusive, highlighting the influence of both the context and the person on their own development. Overall, earlier studies have validated the flexible use of the ecological systems model in the field of language teacher education, as well as in exploring teachers'

emotions. Their adaptations were context-specific by focusing on the environments where teachers, in their own studies, work and develop.

The above studies mostly focused on the ecology of teachers' development in which teachers work and did not consider the individual characteristics that teachers could bring to their work and build throughout their career. By focusing on teachers' experiences and their main challenges through adopting IPA, this study would help to highlight teachers' perceptions of their own environment, as called by Bronfenbrenner 'phenomenological conception of the environment', as well as different environmental factors that teachers identified to shape their teaching experience of learners with ADHD. It is important to highlight that Bronfenbrenner was continuously working the theory to present a holistic picture of human development. He criticised prevalent approaches at his time which dismissed the role of the individual and the broader context in which they live (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). This complexity resonates with teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD that are shared through their accounts, where individual and contextual factors link to create and shape their experiences. The study added further validity to the applicability of the bioecological theory to the context of teacher development.

2.13.3 Rationale for choosing the bioecological theory.

My study is, to the best of my knowledge, the first of its kind in the Algerian context as investigating the journey of educating learners with ADHD is under-researched in this context. Therefore, theorising based on existing theories would not be possible.

By immersing myself with teachers' accounts, I realised that their experiences occurred within a complex pattern of interaction of different systems that a simple theory cannot account for. The Process Person Context Time (PPCT) helped to understand how personal characteristics of teachers and external environmental factors interacted to shape their own experiences, by weaving connection between them. Therefore, it would provide insights into how different factors constitute experience.

It was instrumental in mapping connections between themes and develop a deeper understanding of the experiences of the participants. Through the use of IPA and the bioecological theory, environmental and individual intricacies shone forth. In addition, through a systemic perspective that prioritizes individual experiences, it became possible to

identify the various environmental elements that impacted the development of teachers in their accounts. Therefore, It was also helpful to situate teachers' experiences within the broader context of teachers' development where each element within the environment is likely to have either a positive or a negative impact. This approach allowed for a better understanding of how different factors in the environment may influence a teacher's experience when working with students who have ADHD. In summary, it facilitated the identification of environmental elements in participants' narratives that could enhance the overall experience of teachers when working with learners with ADHD. In other words, with my extended view of teachers' experience in light of Bronfenbrenner's theory, I have managed to identify different gaps in several areas of teachers' education and development, a theme that persisted in teachers' accounts and which seems to shape their teaching paths. By comprehending the diverse levels of influence on teachers' experiences, a better support system can be provided as Bronfenbrenner's theory advocates for supportive communities and institutions (Hoare, 2008). Creating and sustaining supportive communities and institutions is crucial for promoting teachers' positive development and well-being. This inquiry would help to provide evidence-based knowledge about the needs of teachers from their vantage point in order to understand how their development can be better supported. In addition, the study would provide a fresh perspective of conceptualising Algerian teachers' experiences of working alongside learners with ADHD and their developmental pathways.

The school context is a complex system that cannot be understood from a theory with a narrow focus. Ainscow *et al.* (2012) claimed that schools are complicated, messy, and changeable. Teaching does not occur in a vacuum, rather local, national authorities and different stakeholders play a role in supporting or impeding teachers' effort to change. Viewing the classroom as a system in which different elements interact to either support or suppress the learning of teachers was deemed necessary to understand teachers' accounts. The complexity of the environment is a basic tenet of Bronfenbrenner's conception of his theory. Without a broader focus, the complexity of the classroom in which teachers function "cannot be fully understood" (Hardman, 2011, p.5). My argument is that the moment of interaction between teachers and learners with ADHD is complex where different interrelated environmental features and individuals shaped this interplay, so different

patterns of interaction have made their experiences. A theory that focuses solely on one aspect of the environment would not be sufficient in describing or explaining the intricate experiences of teachers. Such a theory would have a limited perspective and thus fail to capture the multifaceted nature of the teaching profession, as it is influenced by numerous environmental factors such as the school culture, community, and policies. In essence, a comprehensive theory of teaching must consider the complexity and interplay of various environmental and individual factors that shape the experiences of teachers. I believe that teachers' experiences can be better understood within a bioecological system, as such a framework accommodates different factors.

According to Bronfenbrenner (2005), human development is dependent on the subjective and the objective experiences of the person living in that environment. This means that individuals' development is shaped by both their own personal experiences and perceptions, as well as the objective circumstances and events in their environment. These factors work together to influence an individual's development over time within the ecological context in which they are situated. More importantly, this model acknowledges the role of individual teachers in framing their own experiences. This is compatible with the overall aim of my research which endeavours to attain first-person account of the phenomenon under investigation.

According to Bronfenbrenner (1979), understanding the interconnectedness of various environmental factors in shaping development requires an examination of how individuals perceive their environment. He asserted that any theoretical framework should take into account the subjective experiences of individuals within their surroundings. Therefore, he placed equal importance on the experiential aspects of development, considering the way people experience and interact with their environment as a fundamental factor in understanding human development. A critical element in the definition of the bioecological model is experience (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006). He defined experience as:

Relevant features of any environment for human development include not only its objective properties but also the way in which these properties are subjectively experienced by the persons living in that environment (Bronfenbrenner, 2005, p.5)

In summary, Bronfenbrenner's theoretical perspective acknowledges the role of subjective experiences, an essential component in the present study in shaping individuals' development and emphasizes the importance of considering this factor in any theoretical framework.

Bronfenbrenner's ideas were influenced by Lewin's Phenomenology which has immensely influenced his thinking about the ecological model (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). In his book 'making human beings human' published in 2005, he acknowledged great debt to Kurt Lewin and his ideas about the relational and the contextual view of human behaviour. Thus, the concept of interdependence and nested structures was influenced by the ideas from Lewin, which implies the dynamic properties of interaction. The phenomenological conception underlying Bronfenbrenner's theory lends great parity with Heideggerian philosophy of being in the world or 'Dasein' (for more details see chapter three, p.78). IPA researchers view experience as a "worldly and relational phenomenon" (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, p.29). People's experiences are therefore understood in relation to the world or the context where they take place. Teachers and the environment are dynamically interrelated.

It is worth mentioning that the theory was robust in different ways as it helped to provide a rich and a more complex interpretation of the phenomenon under study. In addition, it helped to present a more holistic picture of teachers' experiences in the wider context, shedding light on both personal and environmental influences. To sum up, it provided another layer of interpretation that is more complex. It also established a useful framework that accommodates different factors that would enhance the experience of teachers of learners with ADHD and thus contribute to teachers' development (see chapter five, p.154). An important implication from the findings is the need to reconceptualise teachers' development more holistically.

2.13.4 A Snapshot into the bioecological model and its relevance to teacher development

2.13.4.1 Process

Bronfenbrenner and Morris (2006) emphasized the reciprocal and interactive nature of the proximal processes between a person and their environment in the context of PPCT (process-person-context-time) framework. This highlights the critical role of the developing

individual in their own development through the reciprocal and immediate interactions with their environment. According to Bronfenbrenner, individuals make sense of their world through these interactions and play an influential role in changing the prevailing order (Tudge *et al.*, 2009). It is in the context of schools that teachers' experience becomes meaningful, through engaging in some interactions with pupils, colleagues and so on. Certain factors within the environment may foster or inhibit individuals' development. Bronfenbrenner (1993) included the instigative characteristics of the environment which can be useful or debilitating for the individual's development and place some constraints on some activities (Hayes, O'Toole and Halpenny, 2017).

Proximal interactions taking place in teachers' work include interaction with pupils, colleagues, and psychologists. It is widely believed that developing close bonds with students gives teachers an inner sense of fulfilment and a sense of purpose. These connections can help the teacher better understand the requirements of their pupils, guide their instructional strategies, and foster a secure and an encouraging learning environment. Additionally, personal relationships with children can contribute to the teacher's job satisfaction and overall well-being, making teaching a fulfilling and meaningful career (Split *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, these interactions are likely to influence teachers' professional practice as they give meaning to their work. Interactions with learners with ADHD can be sometimes stressful for teachers (Greene *et al.*, 2002; Lawrence, Estrada and McCormick, 2017; Mulholland, Cumming and Jang, 2015; Roger *et al.*, 2015). However, teachers can also develop their own approach to teaching by regularly engaging with their students and gaining insights into their individual learning requirements. This is achieved by building a deeper understanding of the students' needs through ongoing interactions. For instance, a teacher's interactions with pupils and teaching style may be influenced by a genetic inclination (*Person* characteristics) towards being extremely empathic. This characteristic may make the instructor more sensitive to the emotional needs of their pupils and better equipped to offer comfort and understanding when needed.

Other immediate factors that are likely to contribute to teachers' development include time for group reflections where groups of teachers can analyse their experiences to ensure the development of the necessary social and professional skills. In addition, consultation with psychologists is likely to provide teachers with expert knowledge on how to deal with

learners with additional support needs. DuPaul and Weyandt (2011) stressed the importance of psychologist consultation in dealing with learners with ADHD. Boud and Hager (2012) claim that professional learning opportunities should be “situated” (p.27) via including CPD in teachers’ day to day practice. In other words, ensuring that CPD is linked to the challenges teachers face can make it more meaningful and effective, as it provides relevant support to teachers on a regular basis. In addition, teachers’ development becomes more complex as they make linkages with other immediate and distal environments. This is elucidated in the second proposition underlying the theory: “the form, the power, and the content of these proximal processes are influenced by personal as well as contextual influences”(Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006) (More details about how this applies to the present study are provided in chapter five, p.154).

2.13.4.2 Person

By adopting an anthropocentric view, Bronfenbrenner (1993) emphasised the role of the individual in his theories which he views as a:

Highly complex biopsychological organism—characterized by a distinctive complex of evolving interrelated, dynamic capacities for thought, feeling, and action (p.7)

This suggests that individual characteristics can reduce or enhance the process of development (Bronfenbrenner, 1995). Therefore, individual characteristics can have an impact on the trajectory and intensity of proximal processes throughout an individual’s life.

Relevant literature have distilled many individual characteristics which might be necessary for teachers’ development. Husband (2015) argues that experiences and ideas constructed throughout one’s career contribute to their development. Husband (2015) confirms that experience further CPD needs. Applying this to the present study means that teachers’ needs at different stages of their career should be taken into consideration. Teachers’ beliefs and personal characteristics are important components of teachers’ development.

Bronfenbrenner (2005) conceptualised the individual as an agent of change in their own development. Encouraging teachers’ own agency helps them to achieve a high order of decision making (Priestley *et al.*, 2016). In the Algerian context, it is particularly crucial to

prioritize the voices of Algerian teachers in order to challenge the prevailing systems of power and the technocratic approach to decision-making within English language teaching. According to Gutierrez (2019), when educators actively participated in the initial planning stages, addressing their identified learning challenges, and implementing them during professional development practices, they were able to proactively anticipate and navigate the obstacles that typically impacted their level of dedication and involvement. Therefore, it is possible to assume that when individuals feel appreciated as part of a community, they would be encouraged to become more involved, committed, and creative, which ultimately leads to improved collective outcomes and accomplishments of the group.

Factors that originate from teachers themselves may promote or inhibit their career trajectories. Feelings and emotional well-being are also important to achieve healthy development. Studies revealed that teacher emotion impact different aspects of teacher's development including their personal and professional lives in addition to students' learning (Hagenauer and Volet, 2014; Schutz, 2014). Therefore, studying and understanding teachers' emotions is also important. In addition, teachers' self-efficacy has been established as a crucial factor in successful teaching and is used to refer to teachers' conviction in their ability to design and execute effective teaching strategies that produce desired results in terms of student engagement and learning (Bandura, 1977). This implies that teachers' beliefs in their own capacities promote their achievement and personal well-being. It also defines their abilities to implement strategies to involve learners (Latouche and Gascoigne, 2019). Zee, de Jong, and Koomen (2017) considers self-efficacy as one of the psychological resources for teachers' performance in the classroom. This implies that self-efficacy protects teachers from negative psychological outcomes and helps them to cope with challenging behaviours (Chan, 2002; Zee and Koomen, 2016). It also suggests that high levels of self-efficacy have been found to reduce negative emotions among teachers. In other words, when teachers feel confident in their abilities to teach, they are less likely to experience stress, anxiety, or other negative emotions related to their job (Korpershoek *et al.*, 2016).

Earlier research indicates that having adequate knowledge is also crucial for teachers to perform effectively in their profession (Alkahtani, 2013; Bradshaw and Kamal, 2013; Al-Moghamhsi and Al-Johani, 2018; Mohamed, 2018; Mohr-Jensen *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore,

the literature highlights the significance of providing teachers with appropriate training to increase their knowledge.

2.13.4.3 Context

Bronfenbrenner's terminology of the different structures was adapted from Brims's (1975) terminology of microstructure, mesostructure and macrostructure.

Context refers to various settings (microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem and macrosystem) where proximal processes take place and with whom, as described below:

- Microsystem is the lowest structure in the theory in which an individual is situated. This system refers to the factors within the classroom which influence their ability to practice their job. Teachers' development at the microsystem is tightly linked to their personal experience and people they directly interact with including pupils, colleagues, and psychologists within the school environment.
- Mesosystem represents the active participation across different microsystems as home-school communication. Unlike the microsystem, the mesosystem refers to the cross-setting interaction and activities. It represents the relationship between teachers and people outside the educational institutions including the learners' parents, for instance.
- Exosystem: beyond the immediacy of the microsystem and mesosystem context lies the Exosystem which refers to the context that does not contain the developing person, yet in which events occurring affect their lives (Bronfenbrenner, 2005). In my study, it refers to the context where ground rules about training opportunities are set. The Ministry of National Education does not usually engage teachers but makes decisions which influence their practice including training. It is in this context where decisions regarding development courses and opportunities are made. In-service training of teachers are limited to ad-hoc occasional sessions delivered by inspectors including workshops and seminars (Ghedjghoudj, 2014). The development of teachers, in this context, involves their interactions with experts 'inspectors' through training.
- Macrosystem: represents the overall societal and structural decisions which influence the person's beliefs and functioning (Guy-Evans, 2020). It refers to abstract

influences on individuals including values, attitudes, and policies (Hayes *et al.*, 2017). In Algeria, the new curriculum standards have been introduced as a fundamental representation of the guidelines for teachers' practices (as I have already explained in chapter one, page 14). These standards serve as a blueprint for educators to follow in their teaching approaches.

In view of this ecology of influences, individuals do not live in a vacuum (Christensen, 2016). In my view, these different levels do not operate separately as they find their way into teachers' microsystem and frame their professional experience. Overall, the context represents the environmental levels in which different systems and sub-systems influence the experience of teachers and their pedagogical practice.

2.13.4.4 Time

Time represents change and stability over a period of time within the person and the environment in which they function (Bronfenbrenner, 1994; Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006). This means that experience is ongoing and oriented toward continuous growth and change, where it can alter the existing relations between the person and the environment (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). Bronfenbrenner (2005) stressed the role of the individual as an active agent in their own development, so fundamental to Bronfenbrenner's view is continuity and change.

Bronfenbrenner (2005) believes that developmental changes are triggered by events in one's life or experiences as a result of the environment or human-within factors. Relating this dimension to the present study, time would also refer to what happened in teacher's careers that would have impacted them positively or negatively. The time dimension was created as teachers described and reflected on their experiences to identify challenges, feelings, and impact. I have already explained that experience may provide teachers with opportunities to further their CPD through reflection. In addition, teachers' past experience and learning shape their current practices (Heikonen *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017). This stresses the importance of time in shaping teachers' development. Therefore, the temporal component constitutes an important factor as it would help them to constantly reflect on their teaching and monitor their actions (Heikonen *et al.*, 2017; Naraian and Schlessinger, 2018). Reflective practice "enables teachers to stop, look, and discover where they are at that moment and then decide where they want to go [professionally] in the future" (Farrell,

2012, p.7). Boudersa (2016) stressed the importance of promoting Algerian teachers' active engagement and their reflective teaching. One way to achieve this would be through encouraging them to tell their stories and reflecting on them. This would enhance their sense of criticality about their teaching journeys and help them to identify any weaknesses or strengths. The description of participants' experiences also included their desired changes in the future which provided evidence-based knowledge about their requirements.

Canh (2014) recommended that teacher education schemes should include "a module of reflection", which can include teaching some skills such as "observation skills, self-monitoring skills, and self-evaluating skills" (p. 217) since this component is essential for teachers' professional performance and progress. Reflection is a crucial method for bridging the gap between theory and practice. By engaging in reflective practice, individuals can recognize and articulate patterns of thought and theoretical concepts that arise within the context of their work. This process allows for a deeper understanding of how theory and practice intersect, and how they can inform and enhance each other (Mathew, Mathew and Peechattu 2017). In addition, reflexivity helps to examine beliefs entrenched in a particular educational system because unchallenged assumptions may perpetuate inequalities for learners with additional support needs (Allen, 2015). Teachers who see students with impairments through the medical model lens (Broderick & Lalvani, 2017) may not think of adapting the learning environment to the needs of those learners. Rather, they would think that schools always make good decisions when it comes to the schooling of learners with additional support needs. In addition, they would not view the flaws in the existing structure since they view it as suitable and welcoming, even in cases when it might not be the best way to accommodate learners with additional support needs. By saying this, I mean that challenging some assumptions about teaching is likely to foster teachers' criticality about their own teaching and would increase their sense of independence.

On the other hand, adhering strictly to pre-determined principles and standards may not be appropriate for the creativity of the human mind and teachers' active role in society. Teachers may lead changes in education if their needs are met and if they are empowered to do so. There are not fixed rules or finished characteristics that make up the inclusive education professionalism (Li and Ruppap, 2021). To elucidate, there is a need to consider all sorts of experience, including formal and informal ones, that make up teachers' professional

identity. In addition, Mercer (2010) argued that one cannot understand the classroom without considering the temporal referents. More importantly, the change of the orientation of language teaching profession in the new wave of teaching methods during the post-method era bears testimony to the fact that reflection is crucial as teachers are encouraged to reflect on their contexts to calibrate their teaching to the needs of learners and practicalities of the context. Prabhu (1990) emphasises teachers' plausibility through reflecting back on one's experiences to construct theories about teaching. A first step to achieve this would be through engaging teachers' voices and encouraging them to reflect on their own experiences.

2.13.5 Criticism of the bioecological theory

Notwithstanding the value of Bronfenbrenner's work, his theories have limitations. Guys and Evans (2020) raised the question "If proximal processes are intended as the engines of development, what are the differences between those that produce dysfunction vs competence?" (p.118). They tried to answer this question and argued that the second proposition of the theory the form, power and content can apply to negative interactions. This suggests that proximal processes function at different levels and intensities, depending on whether their outcome is positive (competence) or negative (dysfunction) (Xia *et al.*, 2022). Merçon--Vargas and colleagues (2020) introduced the notion of inverse proximal processes which have higher effect on disadvantaged environment causing dysfunction. They also claimed that the bioecological model can be also used to study the developmental outcome of negative interactions. Navarro *et al.* (2022) stated that by incorporating positive and negative proximal processes, the bioecological theory would present a more holistic picture of human development. I would argue that teachers in the present study had both positive and negative interactions that have influenced their development trajectories. This helps to bring awareness into how different systems can affect each other and can subsequently influence teachers' development, either positively or negatively.

2.14 Summary of the chapter

The literature review in chapter two has provided detailed information related to ADHD, drawing on different discourses. In addition to teachers' perceptions, knowledge, training and pedagogical strategies were also discussed. No specific examples in the literature

discuss Algerian teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. Therefore, the current study intends to fill this gap in the literature by providing information about Algerian teachers' encounters of teaching learners with ADHD in inclusive classrooms. Through reviewing the literature on ADHD in the classroom, it seems that there are different factors which may affect teachers' career trajectories, including individual and contextual ones. In addition, teachers must be empowered and trained to use different strategies more effectively including training them how to address the needs of learners with ADHD in the EFL classroom. Aiding teachers to promote the inclusion of these learners may protect them from feeling emotionally exhausted and may yield better outcomes for the schooling of learners with ADHD. Equally important is the fact that teachers should be given a chance to practice their own agency and should be instructed on how to promote and use their own resources. This agency does not occur in a vacuum; rather it should be supported and fostered by the social sphere, for example via cooperation between different parties.

3. Chapter three: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Undertaking a research study is important for researchers to quench their thirst for knowledge in a particular field. A research study serves to fill gaps in knowledge by illuminating the state of understanding and awareness of a particular subject. The focus of the present study is to develop an understanding of teachers' experience of working alongside learners with ADHD. To this end, I decided to align my study with qualitative framework using IPA as a methodology to meticulously study teachers' experiences of working with learners with ADHD. This chapter commences with the researcher's philosophical beliefs regarding ontological and epistemological orientations, which influenced my understanding of how best to gain knowledge. A precis of key methods and the procedures employed for investigating Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of accommodating learners with ADHD will be presented. In addition, information about the analytical stage, researcher role, the research validity and ethical procedures are outlined.

3.2 Developing the research questions.

The scant research basis for Algerian teachers' perspectives on ADHD triggered my interest to conduct the present research. The big question is how teachers experience learners with ADHD inside the classroom. Through the study, my goal is to gain a first-person perspective on what it is like to work alongside learners with ADHD. In addition, I seek to encourage the expression and representation of individual perspectives, opinions, and experiences, creating opportunities for them to share their voices and ensure they are valued. This would allow for a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the journey of serving learners with ADHD. To achieve this overarching aim, I constructed the following questions:

1. How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD?
2. How do different factors contribute to teachers' sense of challenge?
3. How do they describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD?
4. How do they describe the impact of their experiences?

The above questions aimed at exploring teachers' different views of ADHD, providing a detailed phenomenological description and analysis of various aspects of their experiences

including their feelings, struggles and stories as a way to access their subjective world. To elucidate, I endeavour to investigate lived experience as they are expressed from the vantage point of teachers who are experiencing the phenomenon under investigation.

By defining the overall objective of the study, which specifically focuses on the experiences of teachers, including the challenges they face, their emotions, and impact on their professional journeys, I have identified the most reasonable approach to follow in conducting my empirical research. First, it is necessary for me to choose the paradigm that is most suitable to the research questions and the overall aim of my research. According to Guba and Lincoln (1990, p.17), a paradigm is “a set of beliefs or worldviews that guide action”. To wit, a paradigm represents how the researcher views reality which influences certain decisions regarding the choice of the methodology.

Through this study, I acknowledge multiple constructions of reality through adopting a social constructivist paradigm (often described as interpretivist paradigm, Mertens, 2015). In an interpretivist paradigm, the researcher seeks an understanding of the subjective meanings people ascribe to their experiences (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Following this paradigm, reality is subjective and multiple. Adhering to an interpretivist view, I understand that Algerian EFL middle school teachers’ experiences cannot be studied as an external and an objective reality because people have different perceptions of their experiences, which are subjective. Researching within a positivist paradigm, on the other hand, acknowledges the existence of a single objective reality (Willig, 2013). Therefore, If I were to conduct my research using a positivist paradigm, I would be assuming that there is only one objective reality, which goes against my goal of understanding the various perspectives of Algerian EFL middle school teachers when it comes to teaching students with ADHD. Therefore, a positivist paradigm is not suitable for my research.

Ontologically, my study leans toward a constructivist ontology since I acknowledge multiple views and stories of Algerian EFL middle school teachers regarding their teaching of ADHD learners. Via this research, I aim to capture the multiplicity of teachers’ subjective accounts regarding their experience of teaching learners with ADHD. Reality, on this evidence, exists in the form of multiple constructions by participants and is shaped by human experiences which become accessible only via reconciling the subjective interpretations of various participants. Therefore, I believe that knowledge is subjective, and it is based on people’s

experiences and their interpretations of the world around them (Ryan, 2018). This interpretive epistemology enabled me to view how participants make meaning of their experience of educating learners with ADHD. Participants' sense making or the subjective evidence should be collected from participants (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Therefore, it is important for the methods to be congruent with my interpretivist approach.

3.3 Why qualitative research

Choosing an interpretive epistemological stance predisposes me to research within a qualitative framework since such a framework allows the researcher to interpret how human beings make sense of their own experiences (Merriam and Tesdall, 2016; Patton, 2015). In addition, in view of the subjectivity of human experiences, the utilisation of qualitative methods was deemed more suitable to the aim of my study. In other words, the reduction of complex issues to a limited number of questions and response options via quantitative measures would not be relevant to the study of human experiences which usually requires subjective tools of understanding it.

Researching within a quantitative or a scientific research framework is based on the idea of testing pre-existing theories via using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2014). This type of inquiry would not be suitable to gain insight into human experiences that cannot be presented in simplified numerical data. Besides, the aim underlying my research questions was not to measure observable data, but to explore the varied and different meanings of teachers' experiences. In this research, I am more focused on gaining in-depth understanding of participants' journeys, therefore I have chosen to use the qualitative paradigm. This approach enabled me to fully explore all aspects of the phenomena as they reveal themselves through the data I collect. Hence, to adequately explore the research questions, an inductive or 'bottom-up' methodology would be necessary.

According to Leavy (2020), researchers may use qualitative approaches to vigorously investigate the meaning that people attribute to activities, situations, events, and artefacts in a social environment. Therefore, qualitative research design is used to explore how teachers make meaning of their own experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. It allows the researcher to make sense of participants' stories and experiences. Most importantly, Smith *et al.* (2002) explain the fact that qualitative research is "especially useful when the

research is concerned with either a novel domain or where the issues are complex or dilemmatic” (pp. 132–133). As the topic of ADHD is under-researched in the Algerian context (see section, 1.7), researching this topic qualitatively is more appropriate.

In light of what has been discussed so far, qualitative research makes the best fit with my study enabling the subjective experiences to shine through.

3.4 Why Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

There are different approaches to qualitative research including grounded theory, case study, ethnography, narrative inquiry, and phenomenology (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Phenomenology has its roots in philosophy and focuses on how phenomena are experienced by those who participate in them. One branch of phenomenology is Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). This approach started in psychology in the UK in the 1990s and most published works of the early period were related to the experience of illness, including chronic pain, cancer, and similar conditions (Smith, 2011).

Although IPA has been originally applied in psychology, it widened its reach to become a method of inquiry across different domains including education. It recently captured attention in the field of education (Eatough and Smith, 2017; Gauntlett *et al.*, 2017; Moriah, 2018; Noon, 2018). This thesis, thus, extends the number of educational studies using IPA by exploring the experiences of Algerian EFL middle school teachers who teach children with ADHD. IPA has a strong following as an approach for exploring teachers’ experiences of teaching learners with ADHD (e.g., Hemming, 2017; Kendall, Wagner and Ruane 2011).

Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, three of the most acknowledged theorists of the IPA approach claim that “IPA is a qualitative research approach committed to the examination of how people make sense of their major life experiences” (2009, p.1). IPA, in this sense, is a participant-oriented qualitative research approach that seeks to understand the phenomenon from the perspective of those who have direct experience of it. The focus of my study is how teachers interpret their experience of teaching learners with ADHD. This methodology is true to the aim of my study and the unique experiences of participants as it values the subjectivity of participants’ stories. Through its ideographic nature, It would offer unique perspectives to address the big research question : what is it like to have a learner

with ADHD inside the classroom? . These unique insights, therefore, will help to draw a holistic view of the intricacies associated with teaching learners with ADHD.

IPA was chosen in preference to other methods since it is a participant-laden approach that allows a thorough investigation of human experiences in more depth. Therefore, the choice of IPA reflected my desire to develop an in-depth account of my participants' experiences. Another reason for choosing IPA is to give voice (Noon, 2018). The rationale for advocating participants' voice is to make them visible and powerful in different systems of power. Advocating voice and empowerment for participants enabled me to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences and provided an alternative perspective to dominant discourses, such as policy-driven approaches to teachers' development and curriculum design.

The goal behind the research questions was to gain phenomenological insight into the struggles, joys, and stories of the participants. IPA would allow for an in-depth exploration of the teachers' understanding of ADHD, uncovering their interpretations, beliefs, and attitudes towards this condition. IPA approach adds depth and nuance to the understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. In addition, it helped to uncover the factors that teachers perceive as challenging in dealing with students with ADHD. It helped to provide insights into their subjective experiences and the meanings they attach to these challenges.

Phenomenological research captures experience as a dynamic, and an affective process which is tied to the world (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). IPA places the person at the heart of the researcher's endeavour and considers their feelings and cognition. Heidegger suggests that Dasein, or human existence, is consistently influenced by and imbued with different moods (Whalen, 2015). Moods (or *Stimmung*) represent a fundamental aspect of our being in the world and our engagement with the external world. These affective experiences have a revelatory force as they disclose certain features of situations where we find ourselves, in other words our existence (Elpidorou and Freeman, 2015). In addition, Smith (2011) suggests that : "IPA wants to learn about the participants' cognitive and affective reactions to what is happening to them and how they are making sense of their experiences" (p.10). Via conducting this research, I wanted to investigate how Algerian EFL teachers are making sense of their experiences of teaching learners with ADHD and their emotional reactions to those experiences. IPA enabled the exploration of teachers'

emotional responses and feelings towards students with ADHD. It could uncover a range of emotions and attitudes, providing a deeper understanding of their experiences. In addition, it shed light on how teachers perceive the impact of their experiences in teaching students with ADHD. This included changes in teaching strategies, and attitudes, as a result of their encounters with students with ADHD.

3.5 The basic tenets of IPA

The key features of IPA are phenomenology, hermeneutics, and ideography.

3.5.1 Phenomenology

Husserl introduced phenomenology (1931) as a way to make meaning of the lived experience of participants (Alase, 2017). Fundamental to Husserlian phenomenology is the description of the essence of the lived experiences of participants (Smith, Flowers, Larkin, 2009). Thus, phenomenology developed as an approach to qualitative research seeking to describe the essence of the phenomenon from the perspectives of actors who have experienced it (Teherani *et al.*, 2015). It focuses on establishing and describing the essence of the phenomenon through transcending pre-existing beliefs (Larkin and Thompson, 2022). This means that by adopting a phenomenological approach, researchers must transcend any judgement in pursuit of the core of the phenomenon. Via the pursuit of the eidos, phenomenologists need to disengage from the activity and attend to the eidetic feature of the phenomenon (van Manen, 2017). In other words, Husserl calls for deactivating the researcher's assumptions about the world which might falsify the phenomenological description through 'bracketing' or 'epoche' to capture the essence of the phenomenon (Overgaard, 2015).

It seems possible to assume that descriptive phenomenologists call for putting out of action the researcher's beliefs and preconception, knowledge, and beliefs about the phenomenon since it might lead the research astray. To wit, pure phenomenological research starts with an approach that is free from hypotheses or preconception through bracketing. Bracketing my own assumptions in the present study was not possible as I cannot rule out my insider knowledge about the topic which is likely to enhance the understanding of the phenomenon. In addition, my study builds on IPA which views that examining the lived experiences via bracketing preconceived knowledge is too simplistic and unattainable (Spinelli, 2005). In addition, grounding my research on the lived experiences and meaning

outside interpretation would not be possible as my aim is not just to describe the phenomenon under investigation, but I also seek to develop an interpretive account of the experiential phenomenon.

Two concepts are crucial in phenomenology: a worldly person-in-context 'Dasein' and intersubjective or our relational engagement in the world (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2021), so Heidegger also discusses our being in the world which is always relational and temporal (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This means that IPA emphasises the role of context and time in our own experiences.

3.5.2 Hermeneutics

Hermeneutics is the theory of double meaning and interpretation (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). Heidegger shifts attention to meaning making through double hermeneutics (Smith *et al.*, 2009) which is used to emphasise the duality of the researcher's role where "the participants are trying to make sense of their world; the researcher is trying to make sense of the participants trying to make sense of their world" (Smith and Osborn, 2007, p.53).

Put simply, IPA provides a thorough understanding and a deep elucidation of participants' experiences. It does not only describe but also interprets what it is like to experience a particular phenomenon. For this reason, IPA was chosen for the current study since the researcher does not only aim to describe EFL middle school teachers' experiences of teaching ADHD but also interpret their experiences through explaining what it means to have an ADHD learner inside the classroom.

IPA rejects the old phenomenology or Husserlian approach to the study of human experiences and in lieu of bracketing, it calls for acknowledging the researchers' biases and preconceived ideas. Ricoeur (1970) distinguishes between two strategies of interpretative inquiry: a hermeneutic of empathy (of meaning) and hermeneutic of suspicion (critical engagement) where the researcher tries to work out the hidden meaning through immersion in the data (Shinebourne, 2011). This implies that the researcher does not accept what is said at face value, yet they engage in reflection through questioning participants' accounts. Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) argued that in IPA it is possible to combine both modes of meaning investigation "so long as it serves to "draw out" or "disclose" the

meaning of the experience” (p.36). This implies that the researcher’s role in IPA is to work out the hidden meaning by reading between the lines to make meaning, while being mindful of the specific context and attending participants’ experiences.

As I engaged in the hermeneutic cycle, I looked at how the parts and the wholes intersect to create a story. I began my analysis by looking at individual cases and making sense how the parts and the wholes intertwine. For example, by examining the language use by participants and employing different types of coding (linguistic, descriptive, and conceptual) and moving between parts and wholes to examine how these interrelate to create a story for each participant. In developing a pattern across cases, I also engaged in another layer of analysis, and I examined the data across cases (cross-case analysis) where I sought to compare all the data for each participant. Going back and forth between my preliminary analysis for each participant and the data across cases or the general pattern, I could engage in a ‘hermeneutic cycle’.

3.5.3 Ideography

Smith (2004) criticizes nomothetic research that seeks the generalisability of claims regarding a particular phenomenon. IPA rebuffs this approach and calls for focusing on personal accounts of the phenomenon rather than generating universal laws, as prescribed by nomothetic research (Larkin, Shaw and Flowers, 2019). Unlike nomothetic approaches, IPA is committed to the microanalysis of data or ideography with the aim of examining single cases before generating a general pattern of experiences (Smith and Osborn, 2015; Eatough and Smith, 2017). Heidegger criticised descriptive phenomenology which aims to create a general picture of a phenomenon (eidetic structure) and focuses on developing a detailed analysis of experiences instead (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). IPA is mainly idiographic on it focus on how particular people experience a particular phenomenon in a particular context (Smith *et al.*, 2022). IPA, thus, would help in getting an in-depth understanding of a particular experience. One way my IPA study expresses commitment to ideography is via the use of single-case studies or small sampling with the intent of a detailed discussion of the perception and understanding of a particular group rather than making more general claims (Smith and Osborn, 2007). Via purposive sampling, I recruited nine participants to be able to give a detailed account of single cases. Throughout the analysis, I focused on single cases before moving to what their accounts say about the

phenomenon. At this stage, similarity was highlighted since a good IPA study ends up with a pattern of convergence accompanied by personal testimonies (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). The analysis was structured according to a number of superordinate themes which map connections between emergent themes. In addition, idiographic statements are also included to represent the individual voices. This enabled me to be fair to all voices and views expressed in the interviews and the FGDs.

The idiographic commitment in IPA implies that it is more concerned with making detailed insights instead of drawing general conclusions and claims. However, it can move to general claims, a step that needs to be done with caution (Smith and Nizza, 2022). This implies that the details of a single case also illuminate an understanding of a shared commonality, as “the very detail of the individual also brings us closer to significant aspects of a shared humanity” (Smith, 2004, p.43). This also suggests that the detailed insights that emerge from the interpretative inquiry are likely to be transferrable to other similar contexts (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009), so here we are talking about transferability of findings instead of generalisability which is often the task of quantitative researchers. According to Bitsch (2005), transferability can be facilitated by providing a thick description and using purposive sampling. Depending on those criteria, readers can draw conclusions whether the findings are applicable in their own contexts. According to Li (2004):

[T]o enable judgments about how well the research context fits with other contexts, thick descriptive data, i.e., a rich and extensive set of details concerning methodology and context, should be included in the research report (p. 305).

Lewis and Ritchie (2003) call this inferential generalisations which enable readers to make judgement about the transferability of findings to other similar contexts. To avoid claims of false transferability, they noted that findings should be checked against other sources. This means that the findings should not be taken at face value and should be examined thoroughly.

Depending on what has been discussed so far, information about sampling and participants are provided. In addition to this, a thick description of the research approach elucidating all the stages of the data collection process is provided so that readers can decide whether the

study can be replicated to other contexts which share some similarities. Furthermore, the discussion chapter (check page 154) allows readers to make accurate judgment about the transferability of findings by viewing how they fit in the larger context.

3.6 Limitations of IPA

Tuffour (2017) argued that there exist four conceptual and practical limitations of using IPA:

1. IPA does not take into account the influence of language on individuals' experiences or perceptions.
2. The extent to which IPA captures an authentic portrayal of individuals' experiences and their significance, rather than just mere viewpoints, remains uncertain.
3. IPA concentrates on individuals' interpretations and endeavours to comprehend their first-hand experiences, but it does not elucidate the underlying causes or reasons for their occurrence.
4. The relationship between cognition and phenomenology is not entirely comprehended and can be viewed as incompatible.

Following the same line of thought, Willig (2013) argues that language can only provide researchers with an insight into how individuals articulate their experiences, rather than a direct comprehension of the experiences themselves. In response to the critiques forged against the role of language, Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) argued that IPA looks at how meaning is made in discourses, narratives, and metaphors (Tuffour, 2017). In addition, they advised researchers to focus on linguistic comments and what language says about their experiences. They noted that metaphors can play a significant role in the analysis as they serve as a potent linguistic tool that connects descriptive observations to conceptual understanding.

During the process of data analysis, linguistic comments were powerful tools which aided in the meaning-making. In addition, they helped me to form questions and hypotheses about the hidden meaning of some descriptive comments. Therefore, they linked descriptive meaning to more conceptual understanding. I adopt the perspective that language can provide insights into how participants perceive and experience a particular phenomenon. In other words, by examining the language used by individuals, I could gain a nuanced understanding of their subjective experiences. In addition, the expression of human experiences and emotions offer a window into the participants' worldview.

Tuffour (2017) raised his scepticism regarding the role of cognition in IPA. Smith (2011) emphasised that the aim of IPA is to form meaning about participants' cognitive and affective reactions to their experiences. By claiming this, Smith (2011) meant that people's cognition is important to the meaning making process. This is unsurprising given that IPA places a premium on reflection on what people do (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This introspective examination of experiences resonates with cognitive psychology. In this world, we are continuously engaging in self-reflection about what we experience. IPA views individuals as self-reflective and self-interpretative individuals (Clarke, 2010). In addition, Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) have also discussed that reflection is a pre-requisite to IPA research, so bracketing our own conceptions might not be possible under IPA.

In IPA, the only time a researcher has to bracket his own assumptions is while collecting the data to "enable participants to express their concerns and make their claims on their own terms" (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, p.42). Both participants and researchers are reflecting to make sense of what is happening to them. Participants were continuously reflecting on their own experiences to make meaning of them. As part of the analysis process, I had also to engage in reflection by considering both the participants' narratives and my own knowledge in order to gain an understanding of how they made sense of their own experiences. The finding chapter (see page 107) includes examples of my reflective dialogue.

Another issue that is highlighted in the literature relates to IPA's complexity and the length of time it takes to analyse (Clark, 2009). Since IPA is committed to the painstaking analysis of individual cases before moving to general claims, this level of complexity and length is expected. In addition to this limitation, Willig (2008) highlighted that IPA would fail to provide causal explanations. She explained that it aims to provide description of events, rather than seeking explanation to their occurrence. Hermeneutics, the theory of interpretation in IPA, helps to explore the phenomenon in more depth, working out how the parts relate to wholes in a hermeneutic cycle. The interpretative nature of IPA, unlike descriptive phenomenology, aims to explore the phenomenon presented by participants, which may include investigating its causes. Furthermore, Bronfenbrenner's theory was also used to provide some causal explanation to the meaning participants ascribed to their experiences through suspicious interpretation, questioning the hidden meaning of

participants' stories, and explaining the power dynamics and relationships between the different systems that shaped participants' journeys.

Willig (2013) has also questioned the validity participants' accounts and considered that phenomenological research would be unsuitable for participants who struggle to articulate their experiences. As I worked professionally in a similar environment, I have felt that this sample is appropriate for the research under study. On the strength of being the research instrument, I took up the position of listening and facilitating the task for participants to express their voices and concerns.

3.7 IPA and theory

IPA is an inductive and a flexible approach to data collection which aims to develop unanticipated set of themes (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012; Smith, 2004). In the literature, there were different views regarding the use of IPA within an existing theoretical framework since its strength lies on the fact that it can be used in areas without a theoretical framework (Reid, Flowers, and Larkin, 2005). Some argue that work within an established theoretical framework might not be feasible or suitable for IPA research (Brocki and Wearden, 2006). Their argument suggests that researchers in IPA should refrain from testing preconceived hypotheses, as the aim is to explore specific areas of interest in a thorough and comprehensive manner (Smith and Osborn, 2003).

IPA aims to study experiences on their own terms (Smith and Osborn, 2015) where researchers should not invoke a "specific pre-existing formal theoretical position" (Smith, 2004, p.45). Therefore, it emphasizes a more open and exploratory approach, allowing for the emergence of themes and patterns within the data itself. It prioritizes a bottom-up approach, where one spends time carefully studying and analysing the data before attempting to import a theory (Eatough and Smith, 2017). This approach allows for a more accurate understanding of the data and helps to ensure that any conclusions or interpretations made are well-supported and based on the evidence at hand. It also enables researchers to gain a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the data and encourages a more reflexive engagement with the material being analysed.

By avoiding top-down interpretations, researchers are more able to focus on the details of the data and work towards uncovering its true meaning. Initially, my attention was centred

on the patterns and themes that surfaced from the collected data. The goal was to extract valuable insights that could aid in addressing the research questions. I refrained from imposing any preconceived notions onto the phenomenon under investigation, and instead prioritized an in-depth examination of the events to explore experiences that participants reported from their work life. In other words, the themes emerged from the transcripts rather than according to pre-defined constructs. This helped me to stay committed to IPA inductive nature where I drew conclusions based on teachers' accounts. In addition, this helped to ensure that my analysis was informed by participants' own words and realities and was not influenced by external theories.

The inductive nature of IPA can result in unexpected avenues of exploration (Noon, 2018). It allows for new insights and perspectives to emerge during the analysis process, which can lead to surprising directions in understanding the phenomenon being studied. In addition, IPA work can make theoretical connections usually after the textual analysis takes place where the researcher can be more speculative and critical (Smith, 2004). As a result of the analytical stage, I discovered new and unforeseen paths in teachers' experiences which are closely connected to Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory or the 'PPCT' model. This latter was used to map connection between emerging themes and contextualise the research findings within the broad literature. Therefore, connections with Bronfenbrenner's theory were established after developing an in-depth understanding of participants' narratives.

Participants' narratives were then placed within the wider literature and Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory. After developing the analysis based on teachers' accounts, I could later bring the data into contact with Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model, which resonates with IPA 'Dasein' contextualising the findings in the wider pattern of relationships, keeping an idiographic commitment through the dimension of the 'Person'. This allowed me to look at the phenomenon from different perspectives and viewpoints while attending to things that matter for participants. Put differently, the theory is used to map the different factors that affected teachers' experience and put them into action through different system. It deepened my understanding of wider issues that may have influenced teachers' experiences.

3.8 Considering alternative approaches.

Before deciding to choose IPA as an approach to data collection and analysis, I have considered different alternatives. By undertaking this endeavour, I aimed to investigate the experience of participants with regard to their teaching of learners with ADHD. One could argue why I did not consider alternative approaches like narrative inquiry or a grounded theory approach.

While both IPA and grounded theory share different characteristics, they are also different in scope and are used for different purposes. Both methods use a data-driven approach, where the researcher starts with the raw data and works to develop theories and explanations based on the data. Grounded theory researchers use a large sample to generate a theoretical understanding of a phenomenon and it is concerned with the general explanation of a process or an action that is derived from the views of a larger sample (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Gill, 2020). IPA, on the other hand, is concerned with the microanalysis of the experiences of a small sample of participants (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2021). Therefore, it focuses on the particular meaning a person ascribes to a particular experience. This search for meaning contradicts with the essential tenet of grounded theory which aims to develop an explanatory analysis that focuses on actions and processes rather than themes (Patton, 2015). Exploring social processes often prioritizes comprehending group-level dynamics rather than individual-level dynamics. According to Willig (2008, p.45), the IPA approach is characterized by an “inside-out” perspective, rather than “outside-in” approach used in grounded theory. This means that IPA starts with individual cases before moving to any conclusion about a specific population.

What appealed to me about IPA is its focus on the individual, which allows for a more in-depth and personalized understanding of their experiences. For my current study, my goal was to gain a deep understanding of the personal experiences of a limited number of teachers. Therefore, I have chosen to use IPA as my preferred research approach since it allowed me to develop a comprehensive analysis of the individual cases, rather than seeking to establish broad generalizations from a larger sample.

Despite the differences between IPA and grounded theory, IPA sometimes can lead onto a grounded theory study (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). According to Smith, Flowers, and

Larkin (2009), grounded theory is presented as the primary alternative to IPA. However, this contradicts with the aim of my research, which is to gain a detailed understanding of the lived experiences of a small group of teachers. Therefore, IPA is a more suitable research method for my study than grounded theory.

One may question why I did not select narrative inquiry as my research method, given my interest in exploring the stories of participants regarding their teaching of learners with ADHD. While both methods aim to uncover meaning and understanding from the perspective of the participants involved (Griffin and May, 2012; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022), a common theme in narrative analysis relates to identity and the social aspects of the narrative rather than how people make sense of their own experiences. In addition, the approach of narrative inquiry involves investigating the different stages of an individual's life course in order to better understand and order the meaning of their experiences (Creswell and Poth, 2018). This means that the chronological order of events is emphasized, unlike IPA which aims to provide a comprehensive description and interpretation of the shared and distinct experiences of participants in relation to a particular phenomenon. This involves examining the commonalities and differences in the way individuals interpret and make sense of their experiences. While IPA does consider the temporal dimension of participants' accounts (through *time* and *being*), my research did not specifically aim to focus on this aspect. Instead, my primary focus was on interpreting the meaning that is shared and distinct in the participants' stories and experiences, as captured by the idiographic focus of IPA. In addition, narrative inquiry may involve a larger sample size and a broader range of data sources (e.g., interviews, diary), while IPA typically involves a smaller sample size and in-depth analysis of individual cases (Leavy, 2020). I have decided to use IPA instead because my aim was to delve deeper into the personal experiences and perspectives of the participants, rather than constructing a chronological narrative. IPA allows for a more detailed analysis of the nuances of the participants' experiences and provides a framework for exploring how they make sense of their experiences in relation to their broader life context.

3.9 Research design

My study follows an exploratory sequential multi-method design where data was collected in two consecutive phases using Semi-structured Interviews (SSIs) and Focus Group

Discussions (FGDs). By exploratory, I mean that my study aims to investigate the experiences of participants who took part in the study through nine SSI_s (phase 1, see appendix C) and two FGD_s (phase 2, see appendix F). It is worth noting that both SSI_s and FGDs involved the same participants. In the initial stage of my research, I conducted individual interviews with nine middle school teachers who all had experience teaching students with ADHD. FGDs were conducted as a follow-up to SSI_s, providing participants with additional opportunities to discuss topics that may not have been covered in sufficient detail during the initial interviews. However, not all participants agreed to take part in the FGDs, resulting in three participants per group to ensure the depth of information.

Since my study aimed to capture the experiential account of Algerian EFL middle school teachers, interviews were chosen due to their suitability to experience-based questions (Braun and Clark, 2013). Most importantly, IPA has long been used with SSI_s (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009) to gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study. They have been a commonly employed method in a significant amount of research that utilizes IPA (Haegele and Zhu, 2017; Huff and Clements, 2017; Rizwan, and Williams, 2015; Shaw and Anderson, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, 2011, 2014). SSI_s helped me to access the participants' experiential world (McIntosh and Morse, 2015). In addition, this method has been the most feasible and favoured approach to capture idiographic accounts (Smith, 2004). The interviews were semi-structured so that teachers will have the chance to talk about their experiences in details. The interview questions were not restricted to the interview schedule questions and participants were encouraged to share their stories of their classroom experiences. Therefore, to maintain the inductive nature of IPA, I actively encouraged participants to share narratives or stories that they considered personally significant or important to them. The inductive research allowed for flexibility and openness in exploring the research topic.

Smith and Osborn (2003) describe interviews as the primary data collection method in IPA. However, FGD_s can also be used alongside interviews (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2020) as IPA accommodates different methods of data collection (Noon, 2018). Smith (2004) did not preclude FGD_s from the discussion of IPA methods which can be ripe for exploration. IPA relied solely on SSI to generate data, so it may be timely for the consideration of other data

generation tools. While the use of FGDs in IPA research is not yet widespread, it is likely to provide a promising avenue for future research in the field.

FGD involves gathering a small group of individuals together to engage in facilitated discussion on a particular topic. It is frequently used as a qualitative approach to gain an in-depth understanding of social issues and is deemed useful to understand people's experiences and beliefs (Mishra, 2016). Besides, it is used to explore topics that lack investigation (Nyumba *et al.*, 2018). This lines up with the aim of the current research which endeavours to investigate the experiences of Algerian EFL teachers of teaching learners with ADHD, an area that lacks a thorough investigation. IPA aims to examine convergence and divergence in participants' accounts (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). Building on group dynamics, the researcher could identify similarities and differences in people's accounts through an interactive discussion. Thus, FGDs helped to offer a worldly perspective of a phenomenon which is referred to 'intersubjectivity' in IPA (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). Heidegger views the person as a 'worldly person-in-context' or what is called 'intersubjectivity' which refers to the interconnected and interactive quality of engaging with the world (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). This worldliness or relatedness implies that the person is inseparable from the world they live in. Heidegger, through the study of Dasein, which is one of the key tenets in IPA, rejected the notion of Husserlian reduction that attempted to study consciousness separate from the world and focusing on the phenomenon as it appears rather than involving in it (Qutoshi, 2018). The intersubjective qualities rooted in IPA mesh well with the main feature of FGD since this latter allows the researcher to draw a worldly perspective of the phenomenon building on group dynamics, that represented participants relational nature and engagement with the world. FGD aims to capture shared and unshared experience (Sullivan, 2014) which eased the task of spotting similarities and differences, convergence, and divergence. In addition, group discussions made it possible to complete, deepen and contrast the opinions of teachers. Besides, the use of focus groups in this study is compatible with my ontological and epistemological beliefs, seeking to capture the multiplicity in participants' accounts.

Although relatively few in number, some authors have incorporated the use of FGDs into their IPA research studies (Blake, Seamark and Seamark, 2007; Dunne and Quayle, 2001; Flowers, Duncan and Knussan, 2003). Randazzo, Farmer, and Lamb (2015) discovered that

utilizing FGDs as a data generation method enabled them to gather rich individual accounts through group discussions. Similarly, Smith (2004) and Langdrige (2007) have noted that combining IPA and FGD is advantageous for data exploration. Tomkins and Eatough (2010), for instance, used FGDs in their study on the experience of parental caring and found that the discussions helped to reveal the participants' thoughts and feelings. Ian, one of the participants, expressed how the FGD helped him to reflect on his changing sense of self and priorities. He realized that the group discussion enabled him to think, reflect, and make sense of his experience. It seems that FGDs can provide a valuable opportunity for participants to reflect on their experiences and gain new insights. This suggests that they can be a useful tool for collecting rich and diverse data that can enhance the interpretative phenomenological analysis process.

According to Smith (2004), it is essential for the researcher to ensure that participants can discuss their personal experiences in sufficient detail and intimacy during FGDs for the data to be suitable for IPA analysis. Thus, the success of using FGDs as a data collection method in an IPA study depends on the researcher's ability to manage the group dynamics and facilitate a supportive environment that encourages participants to share their experiences. This suggests that the researcher's skills play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of FGDs in IPA analysis. I would argue that there is no right or wrong method in a particular research approach, and researchers should choose the method that enables them to achieve the aims of the study. To this aim, I made participants at ease to discuss their personal stories; I tried to give them equal opportunities to voice their experiences. I did my best to avoid getting one participant leading the discussion. On the other hand, I did not let the group dominate the discussion and the analytical process since this may mask the idiosyncratic nature of participants' accounts. This was achieved via adopting Smith and Eatough (2010) additional iterative loop (see 3.12.2).

The use of focus groups in combination with individual interviews is well-established (Morgan, 1996), yet it witnessed a controversy regarding its use in IPA based on the premise that it dismisses individual accounts. Despite this disadvantage, FGD is still a cost-effective way that permits rich data collection. It boasts an aura of social interaction and group dynamics that help to spot convergence and divergence between participants' stories, an essential feature of the IPA endeavour.

3.10 Sampling

IPA uses purposive sampling to identify a small and a homogeneous sample that can offer rich nuances and accounts of a specific phenomenon (Smith, *et al.*, 2009). In addition, the IPA samples are kept small to enable a thorough and a detailed analysis on a case-by-case basis (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2014). A purposive sampling was chosen because the aim was to develop an understanding of Algerian EFL teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. To achieve this aim, specific teachers were selected purposefully and intentionally. I established specific criteria for purposively selecting participants in my study. All participants needed to be employed in the middle school sector and located within the eastern region of the country. By recruiting participants from the same region, I aimed to enhance the homogeneity of the sample. Additionally, participants were required to have prior teaching experience with students diagnosed with ADHD. Thus, purposive sampling was used to serve a very specific purpose which is in this case exploring the experiences of nine Algerian EFL middle school teachers, who have a teaching experience of working with learners with ADHD.

The small number of participants is suitable for IPA and a large sample may not meet the depth that I sought to achieve. I also aimed to develop an account which would illuminate the lived experiences of a small sample of teacher and subject the data to a detailed scrutiny. Therefore, a total of nine teachers were selected from two schools (referred to school A and B) located in the eastern region of Algeria to stay committed to IPA ideography.

Githaiga (2016) recommended that researchers should reduce focus groups to less than five participants to allow an in-depth discussion of participants' accounts. Phillips, Montague, and Archer (2016) argue that it could be advantageous to keep focus groups smaller when IPA is the intended analytic approach. To adhere to the idiographic approach in data collection for IPA, two group discussions were held with Algerian EFL teachers, comprising a total of six participants, with three teachers in each group (see Appendix A). Participants who shared their willingness to participate were contacted to liaise time and location where the interview and the FGD would take place.

3.11 Data collection procedures

Participants were recruited from the city where I used to work as a teacher, a city located in the east of Algeria, as a former teacher via purposive sampling. The standard practice in Algerian middle schools is for learners presenting with symptoms of ADHD to be assessed and diagnosed by school psychologists, and information about these learners and their educational needs are communicated to teachers at the beginning of each academic year.

At first, I contacted the education and teaching centre and was granted permission to access the two schools. Once I received written consent, the written permission was handed out in envelopes to the school directors. In addition, choosing participants from the place where I worked previously as a teacher enabled and eased access to the participants. Before being included in the study, the participants were asked if they had any previous experience in teaching learners with ADHD.

Individuals who reported having experience with learners with ADHD were provided with participant information sheets, which clearly outlined the research aim and objectives. They were also asked to review and sign a consent form, checking whether they permit the interview to be recorded. Participation in the interviews was voluntary and the anonymity of the respondents was emphasised. Interviews were carried out within these schools and each interview was scheduled to last from 30-90 minutes. Due to the newness of the research topic and the limited awareness regarding the condition, some interviews were relatively short in duration.

Following IPA guidelines, the interview schedule incorporated various types of questions, such as descriptive, narrative, evaluative, as well as prompts and probes. Furthermore, the sequence of questions was carefully planned, with the intention of initiating the interview with a question that would help participants feel comfortable and at ease. In SSI_s, teachers were first asked to introduce themselves. This type of question helped to break the ice between me and the interviewees. The remainder of the questions dealt with specific issues related to the experience of interviewees including their challenges, feelings, and perceived impact (see appendix C). Subsequently, FGD_s were utilized to delve deeper into topics that arose during the interviews that would benefit from more data (see 3.9) (see also appendix G). All participants were provided with debriefing sheets at the end of the interviews and

the group discussions allowing them the opportunity to ask further questions. In addition, these sheets reiterated the study aims, provided references for further reading, my personal contact information and that of my supervisor and thanked them for their participation. Participant information sheet, consent form and debriefing sheet for both individual interviews and group discussions are all accessible in appendix B.

3.12 Data analysis

IPA values subjective interpretations and brings to the fore participants' meaning through giving voice to their experiences. IPA is committed to a degree of open-mindedness (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). This means that the IPA researcher should accept and acknowledge all participants' views and perceptions. Throughout the research, I walked with participants through their experiences and focused on every detail that might be necessary to make their individual experience shine forth.

IPA involves adopting a reflexive and a cyclical approach to data analysis, moving forward and backward between the parts and wholes to make sense of a particular phenomenon. This implies moving between individual cases to identify common patterns and divergence across the sample with the aim of providing a deep understanding of a phenomenon. IPA analysis usually focuses on what is distinct (ideographic focus) but also what is shared (i.e., commonalities across the group) (Reid, Flowers and Larkin, 2005). In addition, researchers move from phenomenological to interpretative coding, questioning participants' accounts. They try to make sense of participants making sense of their experiences, or what we call double hermeneutics (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). It is about a continuous reflection on one's preconceptions, jotting down anything that may leap out at the researchers' minds when doing the analysis. A reflexive journal was used to note down any pre-conception and any emotional reactions. The analytical stage in IPA includes identifying convergence and divergence, commonality, and nuances.

The study follows Smith, Flowers and Larkin's (2009) step by step analysis. Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2022) published an updated version of their book, with new terminologies to refer to superordinate and sub-ordinate themes. Due to the study already being underway, it was not feasible to incorporate the changes into the analysis.

3.12.1 Interview analysis

The table below outlines the key steps that were followed in order to identify and analyse the themes and meanings that emerged from the interview data.

Step 01: transcription	All the interviews were audio recorded (verbatim transcription)
Step2: rereading and rereading	This step involves a careful reading of the interview transcript to engage actively with the data searching for the richer accounts.
Step 3: initial noting (see appendix D)	<p>This step involves identifying anything of interest, anything that matters to the participant and the meaning of these things.</p> <p>Three types of comments or coding were used : descriptive comments (describing the content of what participants have said), linguistic comment (focus on language use by participants) and conceptual comment (which is more interrogative)</p> <p>Using a hard copy of the transcript, I highlighted sections of the text, using three different colours, that represent the types of coding presented above (descriptive, linguistic, and conceptual).</p>
Step 04: developing Emergent theme	Turning initial notes into themes via searching for connections across patterns of meaning
Step 05: searching for connections across emergent theme (see appendix E)	<p>At this stage, I tried to look for a pattern across the themes via:</p> <p>Abstraction: grouping themes together to form a superordinate theme</p> <p>Subsumption: emergent themes become superordinate themes</p> <p>Contextualisation: work out what the themes tell about the life of participants and their experiences</p> <p>Numeration: identify how many times the theme was mentioned.</p> <p>Function: working out what themes mean for participants by looking for the</p>

	<p>positive or the negative aspects in participant’s experiences.</p> <p>Polarisation: looking for a set of themes that show oppositional relationship</p>
Step 06: moving to the next case	During this stage, I set aside the themes I had previously identified and instead focused on the new cases to determine the emerging meaning.
Step 07: search for pattern across cases (see appendix K)	In this stage, the focus is on identifying the core essence of the phenomenon and finding connections across cases to establish shared meanings that participants attach to the phenomenon. By identifying commonalities across multiple transcripts, a general pattern can be established, which helps to draw broader conclusions about the phenomenon being studied.

Table 1: Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009) step by step analysis

3.12.2 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) Analysis

IPA provides flexibility for researchers. It outlines a set of procedures which can be adapted by investigators to suit their research (Palmer *et al.*, 2010; Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2014; Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009; Smith and Osborn, 2008). It is also believed that IPA’s status as a new and a developing approach allows researchers more room for creativity and freedom (Willig, 2008).

At this stage of the analysis, I aimed to work toward giving the possible and more accurate representation of data. I began to explore the range of techniques to assist me in engaging with the voices of all participants. Various studies have outlined a systematic process for adapting Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) to be utilized with focus groups. These studies provide a step-by-step guide on how to modify IPA methodology to accommodate the group dynamics and interaction inherent in focus group discussions (Love, Vetere and Davis, 2020; Palmer *et al.*, 2010; Tomkins and Eatough, 2010). By following these guidelines, researchers can increase the rigor and reliability of their findings and ensure that their conclusions are based on a robust and thorough analysis of the data. Different IPA studies using FGD have drawn on those guidelines to analyse FGDs (Randazzo, Farmer and Lamb, 2015; Spjeldnæs *et al.*, 2014; Sternheim, Startup and Schmidt, 2011).

The analytical stage for the FGDs drew on IPA tradition along with ideas from Palmer *et al.*, (2010), particularly language and positionality. It also built on Love, Vetere and Davis (2020)

adapted model of analysis. Since FGD requires multiple hermeneutic where the researcher is making sense of participants' making sense of their experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022), I maintained focus on idiosyncrasies during the analysis process to keep engaged to all participants' voices. I applied Smith and Eatough (2010) additional iterative loop to identify group and individual patterns. This resulted in the development of the following stages which enabled me to engage with the depth and the breadth of data.

- **Step one: transcription**

This step involves transcribing FGDs verbatim using word (including participants' emotion, tone, silence) (Palmer *et al.*, 2010).

- **Step two: Reading and rereading.**

This involves a thorough reading of the transcript to familiarise myself with its content. This step was needed to engage with the meaning of the text.

- **Step three: Initial and exploratory comments (coding) (see appendix G)**

I used Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009) coding method which cover the following:

Descriptive coding: these comments capture the content and the context of participants' journeys to extrapolate significant life experiences.

Linguistic coding : this involves a focus on language use; for example, laughter, repetition, tone, metaphors to determine the significance of these language features to participants' experiences.

Conceptual coding: This involves a move from descriptive to more interpretative comments, questioning participants' accounts and moving to a more implicit meaning of their experiences. Briefly, this step entails looking at participants' accounts at a more implicit level.

The researcher at this stage should consider how their preconceptions might influence the research and the analytic process or their own positionality (Palmer *et al.*, 2010). As I have mentioned, I kept a reflective journal to write down any reflection I have about the research data. Using a hard copy of the transcripts, I highlighted sections of the text, using three different colours, that represent the types of coding presented above (descriptive, linguistic, and conceptual).

- **Step four: Extrapolating themes**

This step requires identifying themes that emerge from the data, while considering both the micro and macro levels of analysis. Once the themes are identified, an additional iterative loop was used to examine the idiographic meaning of the whole text, following the approach proposed by Tomkins and Eatough (2010). This step involves working with one group at a time and asking a series of questions to understand the meaning of the themes within the context of the larger text. During this stage, a series of questions were posed to gain a deeper understanding of the data:

1. What experiences are being shared?
2. What are consensus issues?
3. How conflict plays out?
4. Is there any individual account that is being marginalised? (Palmer *et al.*, 2010)

The present study used an additional iterative loop (Tomkins and Eatough, 2010) (see appendix I) to strike a balance between group and individual patterns. This loop assesses themes in a top-down and a bottom-up level.

Figure 1: Tomkins and Eatough (2010) Additional iterative loop

The diagram presented above illustrates the additional iterative loop proposed by Tomkins and Smith (2010) that was used during the analysis of FGDs. This iterative loop ensured that the final report reflected both individual and group patterns of meaning. The loop was used in two different steps, which operated at different levels, top-down and bottom-up. At the top-down level, the researcher looked at group themes to evaluate how well they represented individual themes. At the bottom-up level, I looked at individual themes to assess their relationship with the overall emerging taxonomy. This iterative loop ensured that equal attention was given to both idiosyncrasies and shared meanings across the group.

- **Step Five: Moving to the next FGD.**

The aforementioned steps are repeated with the second FGD, setting aside the emergent themes from the previous FGD.

- **Step Six: Developing a pattern across FGDs.**

At this step, I tried to look for commonalities and differences between the groups to draw themes. Here, I integrated the themes drawn from each FGD to develop an overall analysis of the topic under study, in relation to the research aims and questions and keeping an idiographic commitment to data (Palmer *et al.*, 2010).

As a final step and after analysing the interviews and the group discussions, I tried to develop a pattern across them, working out similarities and differences. Repetition of themes across the interview and the group discussions was considered to be an indication of their recurrence.

To sum up, FGDs do not divorce from IPA's idiographic commitment. Rather, intersubjective qualities shined forth and idiographic accounts could be drawn through a thoughtful plan that looked at both group and individual patterns. Through this review, I provided a systematic analysis based on suggestions by Palmer *et al.*, (2010), Tomkins and Eatough (2010), keeping in mind IPA tradition. This adapted analysis takes into account both group and individual taxonomy.

3.13 Researcher role and reflexivity

Particularly in qualitative research, the role of the researcher as the primary data collection instrument requires the identification of personal beliefs and values (Creswell, 2014). According to Creswell (2013), since the researcher is the key device in the collection and analysis of qualitative data, reflexivity is deemed essential. This means that qualitative research is value-laden, and biases cannot be suppressed (Creswell and Poth, 2018). In addition, IPA acknowledges that such bias cannot be avoided since it influences validity of research process. It rather stresses the need for sustained reflexivity (McNarry, Allen-Collinson and Evans, 2018). IPA represents the population of qualitative research with self-reflective, self-interpretative individuals (Clarke, 2010). This implies that the researcher cannot eliminate their preconceptions entirely but can aim to be aware of them (Larkin and Thompson, 2012). Therefore, biases should be stated before embarking on data collection and are managed through continuous reflexivity. In other words, the researcher has to be transparent from the start and should acknowledge their own biases.

Reflexivity is crucial for qualitative researchers since it enables them to acknowledge their own roles in the creation of knowledge and self-monitor their own biases to enhance the accuracy of the research (Berger, 2015). This suggests that a reflexive approach has the potential of reducing biases since the researcher becomes increasingly aware of areas where they have biases (Holmes, 2020; Rowe, 2014). Therefore, reflexivity increases researchers' awareness of certain biases to reduce their impact on the research process. Being a researcher with an insider knowledge of the topic, I had to continuously reflect on my position and how it shaped the conversation (Berger, 2015). Because of my personal connection and dedication to the topic, it has been essential for me to engage in both reflective and reflexive thinking during the research process. For this purpose, a reflexive diary was used to jot down any reflection that comes to the researcher's mind. Reflexivity helped me to notice times when I had a strong reaction to what participants said and noted it down to reflect on it when interpreting the data.

I was an 'insider' to the educational research since I have worked as a teacher in the past in the same area (see section 1.7). I should acknowledge that the experience of working within the research setting eased my access to participants, which saved me effort and time. As a former EFL middle school teacher in Algeria, I have first-hand knowledge of the difficulties

that EFL teachers encounter when instructing learners with exceptional needs. This awareness of these challenges has significantly enabled me to empathize with the participants in the study. I sometimes drew on the knowledge I have previously developed as an academic and a professional to understand the phenomenon more deeply. Therefore, my insider knowledge informed my analysis and the interpretation of findings. According to Noon (2018), the use of IPA allows investigators to rely on their own interpretation derived from their prior experience. Sharing common features with Algerian EFL middle school teachers including identity, language and experience helped me to understand their stories. Because we shared the same languages (Berber, Arab, French), I was able to comprehend both spoken and nonverbal communication, allowing me to perceive the unspoken message, investigate more effectively, and identify clues that others may overlook, as stated by Berger (2015).

I also need to acknowledge the possible conflict between my position as a doctoral researcher and my involvement in this context. Throughout the research process, I traversed the “insider-outsider continuum” proposed by Hellowell (2006, p.488). Initially, I acted as an insider researcher with a high degree of involvement with the study participants. However, as the research progressed and as I moved back to the UK to analyse the data, I assumed a dual role as both an insider and an outsider, investigating the topic from the perspective of my position as a previous teacher and a doctoral researcher, who is no longer part of the context being studied. Therefore, I was also aware that while we shared an experience, it was different for each. Engaging in a reflexive cycle helped me to stay keen on the influence of my preconceptions on the interpretations of findings and to ensure that the themes do not entirely build on my own experiential knowledge but also participants’ experiential accounts. I have ensured that my prior knowledge and experience as a middle school teacher did not influence the interview process and the collection of data. Therefore, the reflective diary enabled me to keep reflecting throughout the research process. Continuous reflection was needed to stay committed to participants’ voices. However, I also understand that my personal experience is an important asset of the interpretative process. I believe that we are embedded in a social world where we form our own knowledge which should not be dismissed as it might help to illuminate a particular type of understanding. In the data analysis (see chapter four, page 107), I have included

reflective boxes that contain extracts from my reflective diary. These boxes share my internal dialogue throughout the research journey and aim to provide the reader with a deeper understanding of my reflections. Additionally, I have included reflective commentary within the main body of the analysis to further elaborate on these reflections.

3.14 Validity in IPA

In this thesis, IPA assumes a more dominant role. Therefore, in order to assess the quality and validity I followed the guidelines put forth by the founders of IPA. Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009) suggested that Yardley (2000) criteria are appropriate to judge the quality of IPA research. Yardley (2000) guidelines are outlined below with a description on how I applied them in my research:

Sensitivity to context: this entails an awareness of relevant literature and the wider socio-cultural context that surrounds the study and how these might influence the researcher's interpretation of what participants have said (Yardley, 2017). To address this criteria, I considered the following:

- A comprehensive analysis of the literature was carried out on the primary subject of the study. Due to the limited research available on the research area, additional pertinent literature was included to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the matter of concern.
- As a result of my prior employment in the same town where the research was conducted, I was able to acquire a socio-cultural understanding of the study area.
- A crucial aspect that aided in the development of sensitivity to the research context was the careful incorporation of the participants' own language in investigating and elucidating the phenomenon under scrutiny (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Therefore, sensitivity to the context was achieved through a careful consideration of the meaning generated by participants regarding their stories and avoiding any pre-conceived ideas to impinge upon their sense making.

Commitment and Rigour: Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) identified the commitment and rigour of the researcher as central elements in ensuring validity of an IPA study. Commitment, as the name suggests, refers to the level of effort committed to data collection and analysis. Since researchers are the main instruments in qualitative inquiry,

validity is related to the effort and ability of researchers to demonstrate an accurate representation of participants' accounts (Patton, 2002). In IPA, commitment refers to the degree of attention given to participants during data collection and data analysis (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

I demonstrated commitment, in the present study, through devoting time and effort to ensure that participants are at ease to share their stories. Idiographic commitment shows how the small number of participants was chosen to stay committed to each participant's story. As far as analysis is concerned, data was transcribed verbatim, and analysis was carried out after a thorough reading of the transcripts. Verbatim extracts from the transcripts were chosen to stay committed to using participants' own words. According to Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009) rigour depends on the selection of an appropriate sample of participants who can provide in-depth and rich data. In this study, I chose a purposive and a homogeneous sample of EFL middle school teachers who possess an experience in instructing learners with ADHD to ensure the depth and richness of information (see section 3.10 for more details).

Transparency and Coherence: transparency relates to the description of the stages of research, with reference to participant selection, steps to conducting the interview and data analysis (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). According to Yardley (2000), transparency and coherence are maintained through the use of transparent methods, data presentation and reflexivity. It relates to clarity and cogency of the description and argumentation (Yardley, 2017). In the current study, I provided a clear description of the stages of research, sampling procedures (purposive sampling) and I included a description of the coding method (following Smith, Flowers, and Larkin's three-step coding (see Appendix B, F). Furthermore, the process of data analysis was thoroughly elaborated upon.

Coherence refers to how well the research fits the theoretical approach being implemented (Yardley, 2008). In this regard, IPA study should be consistent with phenomenological theoretical perspective and hermeneutics (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). I have shown earlier that IPA followed from the ontological and epistemological assumptions I have adopted in the current study. Through double hermeneutics, I sought to make meaning of participants making meaning of their experiences, keeping an ideographic focus, and reflecting on my own assumptions and pre-conceptions. In addition, reflexivity helped to

clarify biases and disclose my background, assumptions, and beliefs early in the process which might influence their own interpretations. This would help readers to understand the researcher's position. To remain true to the participants' subjective experiences and the nature of IPA, I first focused on generating meaningful narratives that are grounded in the data. However, as the analysis progresses, I began to identify connections between the emerging themes and existing theoretical frameworks, here Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model which provided another complex layer of interpretation.

Importance and Impact: Importance is the value of research. The present study contributed novel viewpoints regarding teachers' outlook on ADHD and broader concerns pertaining to their professional growth. Understanding the lived experiences is vital for informing policy making and addressing the challenges in teaching learners with ADHD. The study presented an innovative viewpoint that can guide the professional advancement of teachers within the scope of the study, facilitating new directions for research in the field.

3.15 Ethical considerations

Ethical consideration was placed at the forefront of the research endeavour and ethical approval was sought through the university committee. For the purpose of getting ethical clearance from the school, I completed the university standard forms, and attached the interview schedule, the FGD questions, participant information sheet, consent form and the debriefing sheet. I received ethical clearance to conduct my data collection in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009) cited a number of ethical principles such as informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality as important considerations for IPA research. Throughout this investigation, I explicitly applied the ethical principles highlighted by Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2022) and the British Educational Research Association (BERA) (2018).

In light of the above discussion on ethical guidelines followed in qualitative research in general and in IPA in particular, I have devised my own plan to deal with ethical issues:

Ethical issues	Steps taken
Informed Consent	<p>The centre of education and teaching was contacted prior to getting in touch with EFL middle school teachers and a permission to access the schools was granted before embarking on data collection.</p> <p>I contacted the school directors to inform them that I was granted permission to access the school (By the centre of education and teaching)</p> <p>A written participant information sheet was distributed to teachers explaining the focus of the study and potential outcomes.</p> <p>Opportunity to discuss and ask any question was given to teachers.</p> <p>Time commitment was discussed with teachers to agree on a specific time slot and place to carry out the interviews and the group discussions</p>
Right to withdraw	<p>Ensuring the right to withdraw at any point of the research was made clear at the beginning.</p> <p>Participants were informed that they had the right to withdraw at any point of the discussion</p>
Confidentiality and anonymity	<p>Participants were assured that data will be kept confidential.</p> <p>Their credentials were kept confidential, and pseudonyms were used.</p>
Data storage and Privacy	<p>Participants were informed that data recordings will not be shared with third parties (just me and my lead supervisor have access to them). I reassured them that their permission is needed to disclose information and recordings to third parties.</p> <p>They were also informed that it is going to be saved in an encrypted password-protected folder of the researcher's personal laptop.</p>

<p>Avoidance of harm</p>	<p>Avoid talking about sensitive issues.</p> <p>During the data collection I tried to put participants at ease by breaking the ice and avoiding distress and discomfort</p> <p>Evaluating the risks and benefits of the study for participants were weighed against each other.</p> <p>Reassuring participants that my study focuses on their experiences to inform school practices and raise awareness of ADHD, so there is no right or wrong answer.</p> <p>Since my study aims to develop an understanding of how teachers feel toward learners with ADHD. I'm aware that this topic might generate emotional reactions in the teachers. Therefore, managing unforeseen ethical and emotional challenges through reassuring my participants that their narratives will be kept confidential was needed. I also made sure to create a comfortable and relaxed environment for the participants in order to encourage them to share their emotional experiences.</p> <p>Throughout my research, a consideration of the researcher-participant relationship is vital (Yardley, 2017). In this study, participants are treated as experts and power relationship was deemphasised. I helped them to feel relaxed and at ease to share their personal experiences, reassuring them that they have the right to withdraw at any level of the research.</p> <p>I took all reasonable precautions to avoid any harm, yet I was aware that unexpected things might take place.</p>
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Table 2: Steps taken for ethical clearance.

3.16 Summary of the chapter

The use of IPA enabled an in-depth investigation of Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experience of working alongside learners with ADHD. Through its idiographic commitment, this methodology yielded data which facilitated the analysis of participants' stories. To achieve this, I made initial, descriptive, and exploratory comments of the participants' answers. In addition, I moved between parts and wholes in a hermeneutic cycle to make meaning of data. This data was organised into a number of superordinate and sub-ordinate themes which are accompanied by verbatim extracts from the transcripts to capture the true voice of participants. To protect their voices, I followed a number of ethical guidelines outlined by the founders of IPA and BERA. By following this methodology, this study yielded worthwhile data which are presented, in relation to the research questions, in the next chapter.

4. Chapter Four: Findings

4.1 Introduction

IPA aims to provide an in-depth understanding of participants' experiences by employing a process of double hermeneutics. This process involves the researcher making sense of how participants themselves interpret and derive meaning from their own experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). The analysis of data follows Smith, Flowers, and Larkin's (2009) step-by-step guide to data analysis (see chapter three, section 3.9). The analytical stage, according to Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009), is by far the most important part in IPA. This chapter responds to the four research questions that this thesis had set out to answer. This will be done by presenting the results from the nine SSI_s and two FGD_s conducted with Algerian EFL middle school teachers. Therefore, the analysis has been organised using the research questions, addressing conceptualisations, challenges, feelings, and experience. It is worth mentioning that the idiographic nature of IPA helped me to capture the heterogeneity of teachers' experiences of accommodating learners with ADHD.

4.2 Participants

Participants were selected from the same city, located in the East of the country. My lived experience of working in this context led me to identify a need to investigate Algerian EFL teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD since I noticed that they were struggling with inattentive and hyperactive EFL learners (see section 1.7). Participants ranged in age from 27 to 56 years old. This group is homogeneous in terms of nationality, profession, and sharing an experience of teaching learners with ADHD, but they are more diverse in terms of their educational background, age, and attitudes. Although they all shared the experience of teaching learners with ADHD, they had different levels of experience as some have been teaching more than others, some are more experienced than others are. The study, thus, included both novice teachers and experienced teachers. This adds diversity to the study, providing varied insights and accounts to the phenomenon under study. Individual profiles for each participant are included in an appendix (A). It includes information about my participants that they, themselves, provided when asked to introduce themselves in addition to information I gleaned from their responses .

It should be noted that the FGDs were conducted due to their compatibility with the fundamental tenets of IPA (see section 3.6). In addition, they provided an opportunity for participants to discuss points that were unclear or not thoroughly discussed in the interview. Unfortunately, not all participants agreed to take part in FGDs. Thus, two group discussions (n=6) were conducted with the number of three teachers per group. This number enabled me to keep committed to IPA ideography, giving participants equal opportunities to express their unique and individual viewpoints.

4.3 Themes clustered according to the research questions.

A number of themes emerged from teachers' accounts of their experiences. The following table outlines the themes as they relate to each research question. The analysis groups the data into four major themes. The account of the themes below describes commonalities and differences between Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences. Since my study uses IPA, it is, thus, committed to the analysis of individual accounts, moving between parts and wholes in a hermeneutic cycle to capture the similarities and differences between Algerian EFL middle school teachers' accounts. An analysis of superordinate and sub-ordinate themes aligned with the research questions is presented, drawing on individual interviews and group discussions. It includes verbatim extracts from both sets of data transcripts. Therefore, participants' own words are used to illustrate the themes and to capture their voice and the idiographic nature of my study. It is worth noting that the hermeneutic circle enabled the researcher to move between parts and wholes to make sense of the phenomenon under study.

The first theme explores teachers' conceptualisations of ADHD. The second theme uncovers teachers' perceived challenges. The third theme presents teachers' feelings toward learners with ADHD and finally the fourth theme represents teachers' responses with regard to the impact of working with learners with ADHD. Under these major themes, a number of sub-ordinate themes are presented, and personal accounts are highlighted.

Research Question	Superordinate theme	Sub-ordinate themes
Question One: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD ?	Conceptualising ADHD as a heterogeneous condition	ADHD as an impairment ADHD as a social condition Typically, different
Question Two: How do different factors contribute to Algerian EFL middle school teachers' sense of challenge ?	Teachers' perceived challenges	Professional development Working conditions Curriculum overload Multi-tiered support: community engagement
Question Three: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD?	Teachers' affective experience	Emotional hardship Time and reduced stress Care/ responsibility
Question Four: How do they describe the impact of their experience of working with EFL learners with ADHD?	Experience and time	Reflecting upon past experiences Perceived improvements Confidence and experience

Table 3: List of superordinate themes as they relate to the research questions.

4.3.1 Conceptualising ADHD as a heterogeneous condition

RQ1: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD?

A starting point in both instruments was teachers' understanding of ADHD. The analysis sets forth a number of themes that were drawn from participants' accounts. One superordinate theme was drawn from teachers' responses regarding their conceptualisations of ADHD which captures the heterogeneity in participants' views regarding the nature of ADHD. This superordinate theme: conceptualising ADHD as a heterogeneous condition focuses on what factors teachers perceive might lead to ADHD. The final sub-ordinate theme: typically different represents teachers' views of learners with ADHD, as 'abnormal' or 'distracting' individuals. It's noteworthy that participants employing the term 'ADHD' are signaling their

acknowledgment and acceptance of the medical definition of ADHD. Nevertheless, the extent to which they openly conveyed their perspectives varied among individuals

The first superordinate theme (conceptualising ADHD as a heterogeneous condition) is divided into three sub-ordinate themes:

- ADHD as an impairment
- ADHD as a social condition
- Typically, different

The above sub-ordinate themes depict the dichotomy on teachers' understanding of ADHD who used different discourses to talk about ADHD. The following discussion, thus, first details three different and opposing conceptualisations of ADHD. Each addresses the condition differently and stemming from different factors. It is important to keep in mind that teachers' reference to either the medical or the social understanding sometimes does not imply their adherence to one model. Ahmed, Laila and Ali conceptualisations were not based on a single explanation, rather they acknowledge both individual and contextual factors. In addition, some teachers used an exclusionary discourse which labels these learners and views the behaviour manifested by them as abnormal and a 'distraction' for the teacher and their classmates.

4.3.1.1 ADHD as an impairment

An important feature of participants' descriptions of ADHD was the sense in which they linked ADHD to the individual body. This theme resounds throughout most interviews since the majority of the discussion around teachers' conceptualisations was biomedically focused, although each participant approached the topic in a slightly nuanced manner. Most teachers emphasised the biological discourse of ADHD. I underlined some words in the teachers' responses to depict some language use that helped to formulate an understanding of their conceptualisations of ADHD.

Ali indicated "this disorder has different roots, including genetic...I guess, maybe social, and maybe organic". By highlighting genetic, social, and organic factors, the quote suggests that ADHD is complex and may be influenced by a range of factors, including both biological, organic factors. However, the use of "I guess" suggests that the speaker is speculating or

making an educated guess about the possible causes of the disorder, rather than stating definitive conclusions based on empirical evidence.

Similarly, Laila highlighted, in a tone almost void of uncertainty, “I also see that genes contribute to the development of ADHD”. Ali and Laila shared in their scepticism of ADHD as a genetic disorder. The biological discourse was further emphasised by Fouad :

ADHD is a syndrome where the child has difficulties paying attention, emotional expressions because I can see this during many classes that I have some learners with these problems , with excessive movements and trouble concentrating ... that’s quite [???] problem for me

The above quotation seems to be a straightforward observation about the challenges that learners with ADHD may face in the classroom, and the impact that these challenges may have on the teachers’ ability (here Fouad) to effectively support these learners.

The unifying feature of teachers’ responses seems to be intertwined with a medical view of ADHD through their use of words influenced by the world of medicine (as syndrome, genetic) and labeling the disorder as a biomedical construct stemming from different factors that are related to individual characteristics. They tend to relate ADHD to the learners’ body either by highlighting the role of genes, neurology and heredity in the development of ADHD, yet lacking detailed information.

Other responses to this question included:

It’s a behaviour symptom. This term stands for learners who can’t keep calm during the teaching process and for a long time (Ahmed).

I also see that genes contribute to the development of ADHD...it may also be related to some problems in the brain circuits which interferes with the learner’s behaviour (Laila)

Well, I know what the term stands for... I know it stands for Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) ...I know that it is a condition that may affect people’s lives. They have a small attention span...I guess it’s about attention deficit which may run in families maybe can be due to a lot of genetic issues... a lot of medical conditions...this syndrome is characterised by inattention and hyperactivity (Mohamed)

Depending on what I read about ADHD I think ADHD learners have some problems in the brain...maybe i'm not sure...or maybe they get it from their parents or maybe family...their behaviours are difficult to explain (Ali)

The quotes above suggest that different participants in the study hold different views on the nature of ADHD. Ahmed sees it primarily as a behavioral issue related to the learner's body, while Laila believes that ADHD may have a genetic basis and run in families. The participants' conceptualizations of ADHD are largely informed by medical evidence and focus on individual characteristics of the disorder, particularly bodily behaviours and impairment. This implies participants' acceptance of the medical definition of ADHD.

Although expressed in a slightly different way, the quotes, collectively, highlight a belief in the medical characteristic of ADHD, which is body-centered. Just two participants supported the role of medication and were more explicit about their views, yet an aura of doubt and uncertainty prevailed in their responses:

I remember I read something about this 'ADHD', I think it sometimes needs a medical orientation where severe cases can be given some drugs I don't know... to lessen their hyperactivity or regulate their behaviours (Jalil)

Well, I think these learners can be given medicine...I have read this somewhere I don't remember...this medicine is used to treat the symptoms or something...to be honest I'm not sure if this helps 100% to remedy some behaviours(Ali)

The above quotes suggest that Ali and Jalil have doubts about the extent to which medication can fully address the symptoms of the disorder. They also highlight the need for accurate and reliable information about ADHD, in order to better support learners who may be struggling with the disorder. Through looking at participants' responses and the uncertainty that characterised most of their responses, it seems possible that these participants adopted a unitary medical conceptualisation without fully understanding it. Another possible explanation would be that although participants view ADHD as a medical condition, they use the social model to address the needs of learners with ADHD.

Reflective box:

By focusing on the individual factors that might contribute to ADHD, I thought that these participants are using the medical to respond to the needs of learners with ADHD, implying the need for the child to change to fit in the educational system.

I thought that this is a way to escape the responsibility of engaging learners with ADHD from the learning process. I jotted down this perception, yet I had to withhold making conclusions until further information was gathered.

4.3.1.2 ADHD as a social condition

On the other hand, there was also a stated belief in the environmental influence on ADHD which is presented as the product of contextual dynamics. Consequently, participants presented ADHD as an exogenous phenomenon. Laila describes how the school environment might cause learners' stress:

I think that ADHD is influenced by different factors, including factors triggered by the educational system... I mean kids at a very young age entering middle school ...it's totally a transitional step that might cause ADHD...it's like they are having less relax and play time...less recess and lot of tasks to do...lot of presentations to deliver and I think this puts students in a very stressful situation which may trigger ADHD

The above passage implies a sense of understanding and acceptance of learners with ADHD. Laila thinks that the environment is limiting these learners' activity and is assigning many things to be achieved. When asked about their conceptualisations of ADHD in the group discussion, Laila and Ahmed were unanimous in their view about the contextual impact on learners with ADHD:

Ahmed: Personally, I see that there are many factors that participate to the development of ADHD. The conditions of the learner's schooling and the methods of teaching that are highly demanding for the learner might be responsible for ADHD

Laila: (nods her head) Yes, I agree with you. The new educational system is so demanding; asking the child to sit for a long time , without speaking or moving, must be so boring for the pupil.

Ahmed: Yeah...severe instructions (Focus Group Discussion 1)

These participants stressed the role of the environment that might play in creating the behaviour of learners with ADHD. Notably, their descriptions focused on the external influence which might be caused by the school context and the system in general. Ahmed specifically suggests that when the schooling conditions and the teaching methods are too demanding for the learner, it may contribute to ADHD. The quote implies that Ahmed considers environmental and contextual factors to be significant in understanding and potentially responding to the needs of learners with ADHD. Laila goes further to suggest that the new educational system is particularly demanding, forcing children to sit still for long periods without any movement or interaction, which could lead to boredom and potentially contribute to the development of ADHD. The excerpt suggests a concern that current teaching methods may not be conducive to the learning and well-being of all children, and alternative approaches may be necessary to create a more engaging and supportive learning environment.

Amel and Amina conveyed a similar mutuality in the group discussion:

Amel: We can't say that ADHD is a medical condition. Basically, it's a social condition. If provided with the necessary support, the teacher can alter the learner's behaviours and accommodate them successfully..still there are ways to involve these learners

Amina: I totally agree with you because when we think of ADHD as a medical condition we are ignoring the role of the context, especially the educational context

(Focus Group Discussion 2)

The quotes from Amel and Amina suggest that they both hold the view that ADHD should not be solely understood as a medical condition. They emphasize the importance of the educational and social contexts in which learners with ADHD find themselves, and suggest that these factors play a significant role in shaping their behaviors and experiences. The interviewees appear to be advocating for an inclusive approach to understanding and supporting learners with ADHD, one that takes into account the various social factors that may impact their learning and development. They believe that with appropriate support and accommodations, teachers can successfully engage and involve learners with ADHD in the learning process. This implies that they are following the social model to respond to the needs of learners with ADHD.

Ali advocates a holistic approach of looking at ADHD:

As I have mentioned, ADHD learners might have some problems in the brain. In addition, It might be related to the surrounding... The child or the student , let's say, is affected by the surrounding environment. For example, when you don't give much attention to a learner and this is due to the lack of time...h/she starts to be noisy to attract attention by doing some gestures..i don't know. For example, hitting the table, laughing for no obvious reason. I think this lack of attention from my part or other teachers causes them this hyperactivity or as you mentioned ADHD..the society has to do with this as well...because as a child not receiving enough attention from outside or within the school might be responsible for many things...

As the above excerpt demonstrates, Ali thinks that learners with ADHD might use challenging behaviours to attract others' attention which was initially missing. This implies that not receiving the needed attention from the surrounding may exacerbate the situation of the learner with ADHD who may become even more active to seek the needed attention. The interviewee suggests that ADHD may be related to a lack of attention and support from teachers or caregivers, and that this may cause hyperactive behavior in learners as a way of seeking attention. He also notes that societal factors may play a role in ADHD, as children who do not receive enough attention or support from the broader community may be at greater risk of developing the disorder

4.3.1.3 Typically different

The third sub-theme relates to teachers' conceptualisations and characterisations of ADHD which seem responsible for creating teachers' negative feelings toward learners with ADHD. They talked about how they perceived these learners which implies a sense of difference. Therefore, this theme illustrates how the behaviour of learners with ADHD might lead teachers to view these learners as 'others' and 'different'.

Teachers tend to view ADHD as primarily a behavioral issue, as they define the condition based on observable behaviors that disrupt the learning environment for both the teacher and other students. This suggests that the behaviours manifested by these learners were being problematised since teachers discussed having difficulty to manage classes that included learners with ADHD, which they attributed to the 'distracting' nature of the disorder.

Mouhamed shared “Well, I guess it’s about pupils lacking attention in class, they talk to each other, they move of their places”. In the same vein, Mr Fouad shared:

The ADHD learner has difficulties paying attention, excessive movement, rush movements, mood swings, etc. (silence) I can notice ADHD in learners very clearly since they can’t stay in their seats or keep quiet and they can’t concentrate for a long time

(FGD 2)

The extract above shows how Fouad makes meaning of ADHD through its behavioural manifestations. Most teachers demonstrated an understanding of the types of behaviour which could be considered typical of learners with ADHD, yet they portrayed these characteristics in a negative manner, potentially resulting in additional issues like disruptive behavior and conduct problems. This emphasizes the significance of properly addressing and managing the behaviors of learners with ADHD, while avoiding negative stereotyping or labeling that could lead to further challenges.

For Amina and Imene, learners with ADHD can disrupt the classroom environment and can ultimately impact the learning experience for both the students with ADHD and their classmates:

ADHD is an obstacle to the success of the lesson, ADHD learners distract and interrupt other learners (Amina)

ADHD learners disrupt some teachers and their classmates (Imene)

In another recurring aspect of this reported distraction, Mohamed stated

This [ADHD] affects pupils especially in classes where they lack a lot of attention in class, they talk to each other , they move of their places...they can be doing things which hinder their grasp of information ...grabbing information and using it for themselves...it may sometimes go beyond that...it may cause these learners seem restless... they move out of their places , they come to the teacher’s to the board and this is quite an issue...forgive me I did stutter there for a little bit...

Mohamed discusses how he deals with the ‘disruptive’ behaviour of students with ADHD by implementing disciplinary measures and utilizing various techniques to refocus them on the task at hand. According to these teachers, learners with ADHD behaviours are largely

'distracting' for teachers and their peers. This might explain why teachers find it challenging to deal with learners with ADHD especially at the beginning of their careers.

Overall, the excerpts show the ways in which ADHD can be understood in the educational context. The majority of participants in the study expressed difficulties in managing students with ADHD, as the common theme among their responses was to view ADHD as a challenging teaching experience. They highlighted how the potential for distraction associated with ADHD had a negative impact on the learning environment, both for the teacher and other students. In addition to the prevailing thoughts that learners with ADHD may cause distraction in the classroom, teachers used 'othering' discourse' to categorise these learners. This means that the teachers used language that separated or alienated learners with ADHD from other students in the classroom, emphasizing their differences and creating a sense of 'otherness'. The use of such language may contribute to further stigmatization and negative attitudes towards learners with ADHD, rather than promoting inclusion and understanding. Amel, for instance, conveyed:

Now, from the first session I can say if that boy or girl is normal or h/she is an ADHD learner, from his/her reactions...

The above extract highlights an important point regarding Amel's conceptualisation of ADHD. The underlined word implies that Amel conceptualises ADHD as an abnormal condition, a feature that might have a cultural relevance. Amina expressed the same outlook:

our educational system include [sic] these learners with normal learners in normal schools

Some participants' 'normal/abnormal' discourse reveals an important point regarding their conceptualisations of ADHD, seeing other learners as the norm while ADHD, with additional requirements, as abnormal learners. This is a subtle example that demonstrates why learners with ADHD may be seen as challenges and a distraction.

Jalil explained his view regarding viewing ADHD as an abnormal condition;

Once the learner gets into class, h/she should behave the way others do. H/she should listen carefully, pay attention to the teacher...this is how the majority behave...all of a sudden you find one or two

learners moving here and there, playing with their pens...moving their seats...you know... trying to make a mess...it's abnormal...you know...I see it strange...this way of behaving in the class is unusual ...it's different

Ali reiterates Jalil's view:

You sometimes think that these learners are abnormal...they way they react...the way they use gestures...it's awkward...they are supposed to listen and concentrate...this is their future...their careless behaviour annoys me sometimes...sorry to mention this ...but this is uncommon in our schools...we are grown up in a society where the teacher is to be respected...I feel bad sometimes...so I keep telling my self maybe I did not do enough or I didn't give such learners much attention...I do my best to involve them...I do further reading I ask colleagues just because I feel responsible for my pupils...

Ali's quote compares the behaviours of learners with ADHD to the norms of the society where the behaviours of these learners do not seem to be 'tolerated'. Similarly, Mohamed claimed: "In my opinion, the behaviours manifested by these learners are abnormal, not usual in our classes ..".

When asked about why she thinks ADHD is an 'abnormal condition', Imene explained:

R: *You mentioned that these learners are abnormal, can you explain why did you say that?*

I: *You can see that they are abnormal when you compare them to the group. Most of the learners, they do sit and concentrate when you explain the lesson... I know they are just adolescents or even kids and they need to move...I can understand that...but this type of learners even when other learners are concentrating and listening to the teachers...These learners, on the other hand, can't... they are doing things as playing they try to get things from their school bags.*

Collectively, these quotations suggest that learners who did not meet teachers' expectations of the ideal discipline of the class were presented as the 'distracting and abnormal' others. This also implies that teachers define those learners who are behaving at odds with the prevailing order of the classroom as 'others'. The use of the word 'abnormal' suggests that participants perceive ADHD as deviating from what is considered normative. This perception may be influenced by cultural beliefs and norms regarding what is considered acceptable behaviours. The cultural relevance of this perception is that it reflects the values and

expectations of the society in which participants live and work and may influence how ADHD is perceived and addressed in that context.

The IPA's idiographic approach allowed me to comprehend both individual and collective perspectives, giving equal attention to both group and individual experiences. Therefore, it is important to note that although the majority of teachers expressed negative opinions about ADHD, regarding it as a difficult, disruptive, or atypical condition, a few teachers recognized the diversity within today's classrooms. Ahmed, for example, was more positive about ADHD:

I would say it's a behaviour symptom [sic] where learners can't stay still for a long time and this is the nature of most classes or what we call mixed ability or heterogeneous classes

(FGD, 1).

Ahmed had a different perspective on ADHD compared to what was previously discussed in the theme. Ahmed appears to view ADHD as a prevalent condition that contributes to the diversity of the classroom environment, rather than as a deviation from the norm. This perspective implies that he sees students with ADHD as part of the norm and recognizes the importance of accommodating their unique needs in the classroom. Mohamed held a comparable viewpoint:

I can go through with my already mentioned point...the matter that I mentioned...they do take a lot of time to actually sitting in place...but I cannot put all the blame on students...it's a condition that students, themselves may desperately trying to fix...

Although the participants portrayed a negative attitude towards describing the behaviour of these learners, it is noteworthy that they also employed terminology suggesting compassion and concern for them . They also appear to take an overall empathic stance (for more details see 4.3.3.3). However, this idea of 'ideal' learner behaviour may lead to some stereotypes toward the construct of ADHD.

Reflective box:

Referring to the behavior of learners with ADHD as othering can have negative consequences such as reinforcing stereotypes and stigma towards this group of learners. It is important to avoid categorizing individuals based on their behaviours and abilities and instead focus on understanding and supporting their unique needs and strengths. My impression was that assigning labels to learners with ADHD implies a deficit-oriented perspective. In addition, I felt that teachers are teaching less communicatively following a teacher-fronted approach. Alternative methodologies could be more inclusive of these behaviours.

In a communicative classroom that involves a lot of group work, student talking time and physical movements, these behaviours would be less problematic. Maybe if the lesson stages were shorter, if tasks included more student participation, the teachers would regard their students less negatively.

At this stage of the analysis, I made a conscious effort to avoid allowing my personal opinions to interfere with my goal of enhancing understanding. I recognized that without exploring this area thoroughly, there would be no clarity on the matter.

4.3.2 Teachers' perceived challenges

RQ2: How do different factors contribute to Algerian EFL middle school teachers' sense of challenge?

In their responses to the first question, participants conceptualised ADHD as a challenging condition. This theme has been recurring across most interviews since participants shared the challenge of teaching learners with ADHD. It represents and conceptualises ADHD as a challenging disorder as most participants reported experiencing difficulties and challenges linked to learners with ADHD 'disruptive' behaviours in the classroom which interfere with their ability to do their job properly and carry out their lesson smoothly. Challenges, in this context, exist in the form of a number of obstacles and hurdles that face Algerian EFL middle

school teachers , who participated in the enquiry, in the workplace and which negatively influence their professional practice.

Participants identified obstacles they went through in their teaching career, and they described hardship they face at different levels and to varying degrees. This superordinate theme delves deeper into the type of challenges teachers face. They volunteered information regarding different challenges they meet regarding working conditions, professional development as well as other factors. Amel summarised her conceptualisation of ADHD in the group discussion “ADHD for me are challenges and obstacles to the teaching and the learning process, the teacher finds it difficult to deal with such category”.

This section illustrates and explains the themes related to teachers’ challenges with verbatim extracts from the transcripts of the nine interviews and the two FGDs.

4.3.2.1 Professional development

In recounting their training experience, the participants noted that it was conducted by inspectors and centred mainly on topics related to lesson planning and time management:

we were trained how to use a method based on three levels (PDP): pre-listening, while-listening, and post listening [...] the final stage expect from the learner to use what have been acquired in previous stages via some writing tasks ...there is also another method PPU (Presentation, Practice and Production)...this one is more linked to grammar and vocabulary...it starts by setting up the situation moving to practising the new language in filling gaps activities, synonyms and antonyms and even conjugating verbs, then they are encouraged to use the target language in formal writing...I think these methods are the most used ones...however those with inattention and hyperactivity issues don't listen to the teacher while he presenting the lesson...this becomes problematic (Imene)

It can be inferred from the above quote that the training the teachers received focused on teaching them methods that involve less physical activity and require learners to sit and listen more attentively. Similar views were expressed by other participants:

Actually, inspectors taught us how to reach the lesson objectives and how to frame the lesson including PDP (pre-listening, during listening and post-listening) where they use the structure and the vocabulary they learnt in the passage and use it in written paragraphs and PPP (presentation, practice and production) to teach grammar and writing these are guided by the teacher and help the learner to

practice the structure they learnt in written activities, For instance, when teaching past simple tense, the teacher usually presents the rule on the whiteboard, then the pupils are asked to memorize that rule and apply it later in the exercises, filling gaps, writing a paragraph, sometimes speaking yet sometimes there is no time to hear all students so I prefer writing (Fouad)

The inspector taught us different things regarding planning the lesson, how to manage time, how to teach generally and about grammar...I had no idea about how teach grammar lesson, reading lesson and listening lessons...but the real practice starts when you enter the classroom (Amina)

The training helped me to manage time, assess learners' papers, exercises, monitor their performance. (Ali)

The training given to the teachers focused on topics such as time management, lesson planning and emphasised the use of prescriptive teaching methods like PPP and PDP. This approach was more teacher-centred, where the teacher is viewed as the leader and guide for the classroom, which may not be suitable for learners with ADHD who struggle to sit still and listen to the teacher's instructions.

There were also times where participants alluded to their lack of knowledge of ADHD and reported a need for further professional development. Findings from the interviews have shown that the majority of participants including Fouad, Mohamed, Ahmed, Amel and Imene expressed dissatisfaction with their knowledge of ADHD.

Fouad stated in a very low tone:

we, teachers, have limited knowledge... we just see what is apparent...we don't see what is deep.... there are deep things we can't see...you need to read more about certain conditions as ADHD to know how to deal with them.

The above quote is indicative of the perceived insufficiency and superficiality of Fouad's knowledge of ADHD. Amel, in addition to other participants, was forthcoming about her lack of knowledge. She mentioned to "be honest, we are not educated to deal with pupils with additional support needs". Amel's use of the pronoun 'we' implies and could be suggestive of a togetherness in the challenge. Teachers' difficulty in handling students with ADHD could be attributed to their inadequate understanding of the condition.

Ahmed admits his lack of knowledge “knowledge we have about these learners is somehow limited....a more thorough knowledge is needed to help teachers feel less stressed to deal with these learners”. Like other participants, Imene mentioned:

we were not introduced to this ADHD in the training we had, I knew I will be teaching learners with additional support needs like those with physical or sight impairment...that’s all... because I saw this even when I was in university. I also remember that trainers mentioned pupils with physical impairments...that’s all...for conditions as autism, hyperactivity and attention problems I read or search, sometimes ask colleagues to find out what is suitable...

The excerpts above imply that teachers may have lacked the necessary resources or training to support students with ADHD effectively. Imene appears to have taken the initiative to educate herself about the condition through self-directed learning. She also had to consult with colleagues in order to find suitable strategies.

Participants expressed criticism towards their training, which they believed did not equip them with sufficient knowledge about ADHD. They also spoke about not receiving any training regarding additional support needs education and a lack of continuous training. This might help to explain participants’ poor knowledge and understanding of ADHD.

They highlighted the need for more training. In FGD1, Ahmed and Laila engaged in an interactive discussion regarding the training they received:

Ahmed: Before there was some CPD sessions...we still have some training days to help the teacher with new situations

Laila: (scrunched up her nose) Unfortunately, I see that these training are more theoretical than practical (terminology and concepts)

During a conversation with Ahmed, Laila’s tone became more subdued, potentially indicating her dissatisfaction with the training she received. She expressed disappointment with the in-service training sessions that focused mainly on theoretical aspects such as terminology and concepts, rather than practical strategies for dealing with ADHD in the classroom.

Imene also stated:

Actually, it was only theoretical...they teach us how to organise the lesson...we dealt with classroom management, but not very

deeply...how to manage time...how to assess pupils' learning... it was more about the content of the lesson...

A number of participants emphasized the importance of having additional opportunities for professional development:

Teachers are in need of more training sessions so that they can face the continuing challenges...these sessions must target the teacher's practical needs... (Imene, FGD2)

I had training days before we are given certificate by inspectors 15 days before starting teaching and the two other during winter and spring Holiday...actually after receiving the first training you will go to the school and start teaching...actually these were only theoretical, and the real practice starts when you enter the class...the practice is something else...maybe more of continuous support and training will benefit teachers' knowledge... in my case I had to read and look for information myself...I had to ask other teachers who went through the same issue...(Amina)

For me, I see that the training I received prior to starting this job did not help me I have always to read and search to understand certain things especially challenging ones as autism, ADHD ,etc (Fouad)

I think teachers, especially novice ones, will need continuous support and provision of knowledge and understanding about different things and disorders. In my case, I always use google to understand learners' more as meeting with the psychologist at the beginning of the year does not help me so much...as needed I mean...so I need to search and look for reasons (Ali)

Overall, the quotations indicate a significant need for more training that is tailored to the needs of teachers to help them respond to the ongoing challenges and deal more effectively with learners with ADHD. It should also have the potential of bridging the gap between theory and practice. This finding also indicates participants' commitment to engage with CPD sessions to increase their knowledge since they might have felt a responsibility toward these learners.

It should be highlighted that due to lack of training, participants had to rely on self-directed learning, searching for information and asking colleagues for advice in order to better understand how to meet the needs of their students with ADHD. This also suggests a gap in the initial teacher training program or a lack of emphasis on inclusive education, which can result in teachers feeling ill-equipped to support students with diverse learning needs.

4.3.2.2 Working conditions.

The reported challenges of Algerian EFL middle school teachers in implementing inclusive education for learners with ADHD were related mainly to classroom size, and the limited time allocated for the English session. Thus, this theme encapsulates the challenges surfaced relating to working conditions that might inhibit more personalised teaching for learners with ADHD. These factors in addition to some previously mentioned challenges such as lack of knowledge and training might make teaching these learners a daunting task. This theme is evidenced into the interview:

For me I don't see that ADHD is a major problem in classrooms because I see that teachers should accept learners as they are...For me, I respect them, I try to understand every one of them, but imagine you are teaching a class with 30 learners, how would you find time to deal with each one separately? (Laila)

The above excerpt shows that large class size might make it difficult to deal with individual needs. Asking rhetorically, Laila was trying to contextualise her individual experience within the broader patterns of relationships. The rhetorical form could have been employed since Laila was seeking connection and not a confirmation or disconfirmation of what she has said. Implicitly, Laila's comment suggests the challenging nature of teaching within large class sizes inhibits her from taking care of each individual in the class and responding to individual needs due to shortage of time. It is certainly possible to infer from this quotation that Laila thinks this is a shared concern in classrooms with large numbers.

We could also see other participants expressing a similar concern:

If you are to ask me...I would suggest a lot of things...I believe I would suggest having less crowded classes to devote more time...I believe having less crowded classes could be a very good thing because you not only spot ADHD learners...this helps us to minimise time having to deal with ADHD learners...it may improve our way of dealing with the lesson...you would devote more time to this category (Mohamed)

I would say to provide individual attention to every learner and make ADHD learners more engaged, the number of learners per class should be reduced...I sometimes teach in a class with 45 learners...this stresses me (Fouad)

Through the above passages, Mohamed and Fouad explicitly expressed a need to have structural changes in classrooms through reducing the number of learners per class to accommodate learners with ADHD successfully, thus allowing individualised attention.

Similar to other respondents, Ali reflects on his teaching experience of learners with ADHD with reference to classroom size: “Due to the high level of learners in class, I found teaching ADHD learners a difficult task”. He later explained “There are about 40 learners in each class, so this make [sic] it nearly impossible to deal with them individually”. This argument connects with Imene’s excerpt which entails that providing care for each individual might become a cumbersome task in crowded classes. Another participant volunteered information regarding the classroom size, she mentioned “to deliver the lesson in a class with more than twenty learners...it’s highly demanding...this affects your ability to teach successfully and meet your objectives” (Amina). Amina weighed up the effect of classroom size on her teaching which becomes challenging in crowded classes. It is apparent from teachers’ accounts, in this context, that it is not only ADHD pupils which worry them, but also the voluminous number of learners per class, in addition to other factors including lack of training and knowledge.

As far as time is concerned, almost all participants shared concerns regarding the short time allocated to EFL teaching that may inhibit them from supporting ADHD effectively. Some teachers shared the view that teaching learners with ADHD is time-consuming including Mohamed, Amina and Jalil.

Amina reiterated this sentiment:

I don't just teach one class several hours. They have just two hours a week. This is the first thing...the teacher here maybe need time... it's time consuming...maybe this ADHD learner inhibits him from transferring the information or explaining the lesson ...that's why I find it highly demanding... if we have more hours, we can teach them successfully among normal [sic] learner (FGD2)

Jalil and Ali voiced the same concern:

We are struggling with time...you have to achieve the objectives of the lesson and make all learners understand [long pause] this is a difficult task, you know (Jalil)

Actually, lack of time makes me feel so stressed, especially when I don't finish my lesson or achieve my objectives. In addition, some learners as those with ADHD takes a lot of my time...this is another struggle (Ali)

Along with concerns about teaching learners with ADHD, participants also expressed concerns about time management. The comments suggest that teaching learners with ADHD can be a time-consuming process. Participants assume that ADHD can 'disrupt' the teaching process, and teachers may have to spend a considerable amount of time redirecting these learners back to the task at hand instead of focusing on the lesson plans and objectives. This implies that they need more time to work with learners with ADHD.

4.3.2.3 Curriculum overload

Another aspect of workload was volunteered regarding the content of work ascribed to teachers:

We, as teachers, are struggling with time and the curriculum that we have...it's a must to finish the curriculum, the objectives that we have to attend by the end of each session (Amina)

Different things do not allow us to use innovative strategies including overloaded programme (Ahmed, FGD 1)

The above quotations communicate a tone of power and pressure being exerted over teachers. The quantity of work that teachers are tasked to complete might exacerbate the impact of teaching these learners. This means that having too many tasks or responsibilities in the current program hinders teachers' ability to think creatively and come up with innovative solutions. It also implies that having a more manageable workload or reducing some of the existing responsibilities could potentially allow teachers to use more innovative strategies.

This theme was also apparent in the group discussion:

Imene: I share my colleagues' views on the lack of training. I also see that the workload and the different responsibilities that the teacher has may overload him/her. I, for example, sometimes feel lost between delivering the content of the lesson, which is sometimes too much to be achieved in one session and focusing on individual learners and gauge their understanding of the lesson.

Ahmed: I totally agree with you ...different things do not allow us to use innovative strategies including overloaded program with many responsibilities and works assigned to the teacher.

(FGD1)

There is a sense that the curriculum imposed on teachers is rigid and governed by external requirements that do not take into account individual learner needs. Participants described being weighed down by the pressure and the responsibility of achieving the objectives of each session and finishing the curriculum. Therefore, they felt to be limited by the need to cover a specific curriculum. This suggests that teachers need more flexible curriculum to work with learners with ADHD and cater for their needs.

Mohammed and Ali reiterated this sentiment:

At the beginning of the year, we are handed the curriculum, a finished product with a number of objectives to be met ...with a guide on how to organise and deliver the lessons ...Most teachers I met complain about the different work they have to do that is included ...I also sometimes feel overwhelmed by the quantity of work I have to deliver...

We have a plan that requires you to do many activities for the learner which is not possible in one hour with 40 learners per class...this is tiring...I do my best to give equal attention to every learner including hyperactive and inattentive learners...but sometimes I have to finish the lesson and the plan

Imene also spoke about the same issue:

I think the government puts the guidelines of the curriculum; this lesson is divided into two parts: the first part is more theoretical where the teacher has to deliver the content of the lesson...the second part is a set of activities to evaluate the learners' understanding which is too much to be done in one session...sometimes I don't have the chance to look at all learners' answers because I run out of time.

It seems that teachers are given a pre-designed curriculum with specific objectives and guidelines on how to teach the material. However, many teachers find that the workload and responsibilities that come with implementing the curriculum to be overwhelming. It appears that the amount of work allocated for the teacher may create a sense of disorientation between teachers trying to find a balance between the objectives of the lesson and individual requirements.

Similar to Imene, Jalil and Fouad commented:

Do we have a special programme for these learners...of course, we don't, so it must be challenging to deal with these learners...In addition we receive this ready-made curriculum from the government which most of the time I find it too much to be achieved during the allocated time (Jalil)

You have to adapt yourself to the standards of the curriculum or the coursebook and act depending on the objectives of the lesson...within the session maybe I can achieve just 70 % out of the lesson purposes and not all learners will have the chance to practice what they have learnt... (Fouad)

Teachers, in the above quotes, expressed their dissatisfaction with the curriculum where the parameters of practice are defined by external forces, here policy makers. The quotes also imply that teachers are expected to conform to the standards and objectives outlined in the curriculum, regardless of their personal teaching preferences. The standardised curriculum may make teachers feel the pressure to adhere strictly to the curriculum. It seems to limit the chances for verifying and reinforcing comprehension, which in turn hinders teachers from being able to adjust their instruction to meet the specific needs of each student. This is because teachers are constrained by the external requirement to complete the lesson and curriculum within a set timeframe. If the workload was reduced, teachers would likely experience less stress in their working environment.

4.3.2.4 Multi-tiered support: Community engagement

The participants conveyed the importance of adopting a comprehensive approach throughout the school to achieve a more united and uniform way of working. This approach involved multi-level support that required teamwork with colleagues, psychologists, and parents.

Several participants valued parents input: "Collaboration with parents is highly needed in this situation" (Imene). In another conversation I had with another participant, parents' role was also reported:

Fouad: Building good relationship with the learner and his parents helps you to overcome this problem.

Roumaissa: So, you see that collaboration is needed!

Fouad: Yes, it helps a lot...maybe I would say that 50% of this is from parents

Roumaissa: Can you explain why did you say that?

Fouad: Parents know the learner more. H/she spent more time at home, so they know how their kid behaves and they know how to calm him/her when he is hyperactive, I sometimes feel that parents are careless, and they don't do their job adequately

This passage implies that parents' involvement has the potential of bridging the gap between two contexts: home and school. In this case, parents' collaboration may harness teacher's skills and knowledge to involve learners with ADHD inside the classroom and result in a significant and meaningful learner improvement. Therefore, parents are important for the teacher and the learner support system.

Despite the pivotal role of parents reported by participants, they reported less parents' engagement who seem to take less interest in their children's educational progress and improvement. This was featured by a number of respondents:

Parents should collaborate with teachers because they are not playing their roles and are not helping us that's why learners behave freely and are not guided (Ali).

Teaching learners who are inattentive and hyperactive is challenging. When you invite the learner's parents to discuss the problem to arrive at potential solutions, they tend to create excuses for their kid. They don't accept the fact that their kid has an issue that needs to be solved rather they tend to say things like 'it's their age, it's adolescence you know so I can't restrain them from living the moment and enjoying their life'. Teachers can't do everything since they need collaboration from home where the child has grown up. Parents, also, should think about their kids' education. It's a must (Mohamed)

The above comments demonstrate the challenge of communicating with parents as communication with them was sometimes characterised by a low level of parents' engagement and less understanding. This might be indicative of a poor and negative home-school relationship which may cause dependence on teachers who are left possibly alone to deal with the many hurdles in the workplace. The fact that parents are not responsive or engaged in dealing with ADHD students may suggest that there is a stigma attached to this condition in the Algerian context, or it may simply be due to a lack of awareness among

parents about what ADHD is. These sociocultural factors seem to affect parents' reaction to communication.

Unlike other participants, Jalil and Imene shared unique perspectives regarding parents input. They spoke of parent relationship that supported their efforts in the classroom:

Actually, I think that parents I have met have helped me on the way...you know...they know their child so they must have some knowledge concerning how to deal with troublesome [sic] behaviours which they can share with teachers like myself so that we know how to react and how to calm them...actually this is what happened to me... I always invite the parents to discuss and when I finish the meeting, I say oh yeah finally a way that can work for me...

I remember the first ADHD learner was a boy whose name , xxx, he was so hyperactive, and he used to stay at the back of the class, he stopped writing the lesson, he no longer focuses , he talks, and he uses his body language in a way to show that I can talk to my teacher the way I like and he uses his hands and he shouts ... I tried to discuss the problem with him many times ... In this case, parents know more than we do...they know what the child has been through, and they know how their child behave , so collaboration with parents is highly needed in this situation. Parents can help you access some information that will help you to deal with some children. They have been living with their child for long...they know...they know...sometimes better than we do.

Another point that was emphasized regarding collaboration was the importance of working together with psychologists, examples of this include:

Psychologist should collaborate with teachers; we rarely meet and receive support from the school psychologist (Jalil).

I think that expert advice is needed in these situations...they know more than we do...they can help us I don't know by more knowledge understanding... maybe some advice...psychologists...sometimes come to observe the classroom but since they have different classes...they can't do this with each and every learner...so the teacher here plays both roles and tries to understand the situation via searching, reading asking other teachers, etc (Ali)

There was a kind of dissatisfaction with the kind of support teachers receive from psychologists:

Actually, meetings with the psychologist are few. At the beginning of the academic year, H/she gives us a list of students who have certain problems as autism, those with abnormal attention and

hyperactivity...umm maybe certain social issues as students whose parents are divorced, h/she comes to talk to them...but to be honest we don't receive the needed support from experts in terms of teaching strategies, how to manage certain cases (Ali)

Diagnosis for these cases and others are done by psychologists...you just know who has certain conditions...but you have to search and read to understand certain conditions as autism, ADHD, etc...as what you learn and receive may not help in some cases (Fouad)

In fact, we don't meet the psychologist so often, just few meetings or sometimes once at the beginning of the year...(Amina)

Laila suggested:

R: I would like to ask you if you have anything else that you want to add or suggest!

L: um...I don't know, but I suggest that there should be more meetings with the psychologist who helps teachers first, especially less experienced teachers who struggle in their early career, as I did

Amina also reiterated the same sentiment.

we have one psychologist in the school who is responsible for many cases and many classes that's why we can't have regular meetings with them ... I think having more specialists would greatly help us deal with special cases.

Participants stressed the importance of a joined-up approach. This implies a collective responsibility that participants feel toward these learners. They emphasized taking a holistic approach to the support of teachers of learners with ADHD. Cooperation, as reported by participants, helps to remove some weight from teachers' shoulders and promote the inclusion of learners with ADHD through assisting them to face the ongoing challenges. Sharing knowledge, in this context, and taking equal responsibility are emphasised.

Participants have also highlighted the significance of collaboration among teachers. Imene highlighted:

If there are some formal meetings between teachers where they can discuss their experience and areas where they feel they lack knowledge would be helpful for us, teachers, though this is not common in our school ...it would help teachers in a way or another...

Jalil expressed a similar vision toward cooperation between teachers:

Um...To be honest...teachers do not usually formally meet to discuss the challenges they face...maybe we had some informal conversation, but it was not sufficient ...me personally if there are such kind of meetings I'll be glad to join

Ali and Mohammed reported having more favourable experiences regarding collaboration between teachers:

I always discuss the problems I face with more experienced teachers...they share me several ideas ...they suggest some solutions to some problems I face or even advice...

Sharing your experience with others especially teachers sometimes help as a teacher to see whether you are doing the right thing or whether it needs you to reconsider it...you always have this plan 'B' if things do not work...other teachers might help in this case...

The quoted statements above emphasize that, in contrast to other participants, Ali and Mohammed shared positive experiences regarding seeking assistance from other teachers to enhance their professional practice. Overall, teachers' responses revealed mixed results regarding collaboration between teachers. Some teachers explained how appreciative they were of being able to discuss ideas with colleagues, while others expressed dissatisfaction with the level of cooperation between teachers, even though they generally favoured working together.

It was clear throughout some participants' accounts that if teachers do not feel well supported themselves, it becomes increasingly difficult for them to support and meet the needs of learners with ADHD. A number of participants identified receiving no support and care that I interpreted as a need to care for the teachers' well-being. One informant explained:

Unfortunately, we face the problem alone and we solve it alone and we try to find the solution by ourselves to manage and control the situation ...we receive no help neither from the ministry nor from the administration (Laila, FGD 1)

The passage describes Laila's experience as a solitary journey, where she receives no support from any source. This situation can lead to an excessive dependence on teachers' own abilities to handle challenging situations, which may be unsatisfactory considering the

fact that some teachers feel unprepared and lack the necessary expertise and knowledge (see 4.3.2.1).

Amina voiced the same concern “I think all teachers need more support to deal with this category”. Fouad alluded to the notion of care and emphasised teachers’ needs: “I would say psychological care, we also have some needs (laughs) special needs because we are teaching learners who have special needs and who are difficult to deal with”.

It is important to note that, although the teachers in this study expressed a desire for a whole-school approach and consistently spoke about their need for support, they reported feeling disappointed by a lack of community engagement. Their statements indicate that they recognize the importance of collaboration and assistance in dealing with new and challenging situations that may be difficult for some teachers.

Reflective box:

As a previous EFL middle school teacher, I also share the challenges reported by teachers in the present study. I recognise the demands placed upon them in their work with children who have ADHD, as I have worked directly with this population of learners and am able to reflect upon the particular challenges including class size, workload, time-constraint, which capture the reality of Algerian middle school classes nowadays.

The sense that came out for me when I was analysing teachers’ perception of challenges was that they would feel stronger working together. In addition, more opportunities for CPD and self-reflection will assist them in developing themselves.

4.3.3 Teachers’ affective experience

RQ 3: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD?

This theme is positioned around a key issue that has emerged from the data, which is the emotionally demanding nature of interacting with learners with ADHD. Participants started by commenting on the emotions they felt in reaction to the behaviour of learners with ADHD and reported being prone to develop stress-related problems in their early career.

The moment of interaction between teachers and learners with ADHD was often described as having an immediate psychological impact. Their emotive language indicates being through stressful and nerve-racking times especially during the first years of their teaching careers. Apparently, they were honestly forthcoming with their feelings and the most commonly used words to describe their emotional reactions were “anxious”, “stressed”, and “losing temper” “lost, bewildered”. In addition, some positive feelings were also shared including care and reduced stress.

This superordinate theme is divided into three sub-ordinate themes: emotional hardship, time and reduced stress and care/responsibility toward learners with ADHD. The first subordinate theme provides an account of various negative feelings including stress and anger that teachers have felt when confronted with the behaviour of learners with ADHD. The second sub-ordinate theme exemplifies how some teachers’ feelings evolve through time. Participants also conveyed their feelings of care toward learners with ADHD, which is captured in the third sub-ordinate theme ‘care/responsibility’ .

4.3.3.1 Emotional Hardship

Participants reported inability to manage learners with ADHD which increased their stress levels in their early career, so they talked about the hardship in early career and the emotional toll that such experience would bring to them. The challenge of responding to students with ADHD in an appropriate manner ultimately impact their emotional well-being. Teachers’ negative emotions are influenced by ‘disruptive’ behaviour displayed by students with ADHD. Additionally, various environmental factors can interact with each other, resulting in a complex emotional experience for teachers.

Fouad provided a description of his emotional state during an interview:

R: Can you describe your experience with Learners with ADHD? How have you felt about this?

F: (laughs) The first experience I encountered this problem... it was with a boy called xxx... he was so energetic and hyperactive to the point I lost my temper ... I felt so anxious...

For me I can't yell at the student or rush things. I try to understand why he is doing this, what was the problem...maybe I will go and

*... speak to him in a kind way [long pause] as I did with this learner
maybe the first time you encounter this kind of syndrome maybe
you will feel anxious... how to let this child understand[sic]
something... you have to dig and dig deeper in your thoughts ... you
must do some efforts maybe with special treatment maybe with a
special method.*

R: Can you explain why have you felt anxious in the first time?

*F: Simply because I had no idea how to help them, it's a new
experience ... you know...a tricky one that needs efforts and
investigation into the problem to avoid negative feelings. In addition,
I was explaining the lesson that needs concentration and that learner
was moving his chair, laughing with his friends...this lesson needs
concentration, and that boy was doing other things instead of
focusing to understand the lesson... that's why I left the class I felt
this boy is affecting my teaching and the learning of other learners...*

Fouad reflects on his emotional experience as time passes and spoke about the first encounter as being anxiety-provoking. During the first few years of his teaching career, Fouad went through significant emotional distress and anxiety, particularly during his initial interactions with students. He expressed experiencing heightened emotions during those initial encounters.

It appears that his emotional reaction was triggered by the hyperactivity of the ADHD learner and the demanding nature of the first encounter where he felt ill-equipped to manage the behaviour of learners with ADHD. The ADHD learner, in the context of Fouad, interrupted his plan and intention of following the lesson plan. To reduce 'distraction' caused by learners with ADHD, it would be beneficial for teachers to provide opportunities for more physical movement and autonomy in learning, which could result in decreased stress levels and increased learners' engagement.

Similarly, other participants recalled varying feelings of frustration, anger, and stress. Stress levels seem to be influenced by teachers' sense of their own (in) effectiveness in teaching:

*Um...sometimes, I feel angry but even when sometimes feel angry
you can't put it on them...but generally trying to get their attention
gets me angry because sometimes they don't listen to me at all
[...]teaching is a difficult job that demands a lot of effort since you
may sometimes feel emotionally and physically tired ...(Mohamed).*

I remember my first contact was not really positive ... it was not really a positive experience...I lost my temper, I couldn't control myself, I even started screaming, so maybe I saw that screaming and raising my voice can make them, maybe maybe, scared or have that fear of the teacher, but later on it started to be positive . I started [???] them all, sometimes giving them things to do, write on the board, answer the questions, read...it depends...it depends on the situation (Amina)

Overall, the above quotations imply the emotional burden experienced by participants in their initial contact with learners with ADHD. Other respondents were unanimous in their view and sustain the above views:

I felt nervous [...] I remember the struggle I had during my first years of teaching. I once had a learner who wants to move a lot...he once stood up of his place to tie the laces of his friends' shoes. This has driven me crazy that time because I was explaining the lesson and he did this! Sometimes you have to change everything due to this disturbance...you may forget where you are and what you were explaining... The relationship between the teacher and the learner becomes problematic and if the teacher does not control his emotions, the learner may hate the teacher and the session which affects their learning (Ahmed)

As I mentioned classes are crowded, automatically you will feel stressed because we need to control the whole group and to finish the lesson...maybe teaching in less crowded classes would make the teacher feel less stressed, but in a class with 35 and sometimes 40 learners, you will feel lost and bewildered. (Ali)

As can be seen from these qualitative statements, there is a general modality among teachers of negative feelings toward ADHD. Collectively, the excerpts imply the emotional impact of ADHD on teachers in this sample who seem to be always in search of the best method to respond to these learners, especially during the initial years of teaching. Overall, these quotations indicate teachers' willingness to help learners with ADHD. It seems that educators in their early career felt disoriented and overwhelmed by the challenges of navigating their teaching. However, if teachers were adequately supported and if classes were less teacher-oriented, some behaviours would be less problematic.

Ali shared a unique perspective and suggested that reducing class size would lighten the emotional burden for teachers who may feel perplexed and puzzled in large classroom size.

Ali's quote implies that there are other factors that put stress on teachers in addition to disruptive behaviours displayed by learners with ADHD.

Despite being confronted with frustrating events, participants were always thinking of ways to function within the existing environment. They communicated the same sentiment in the FGD:

R: can you describe your experience of teaching learners with ADHD?

F: The beginnings are always difficult Let me tell you something... I still remember the first time I met someone with ADHD (laughs) so back in the day.... It's remarkable... you know...I left the classroom anxious and I (laughs) lost completely my temper... I even left the class; leaving the learners alone...it was really difficult for me.

R: Unforgettable experience. Isn't it?

F: yes, of course...it's a mark on your [???

A: I can relate, at the beginning it was more difficult ...hard for me...I felt anxious, furious, and I lost control (FGD2).

I remember the first time I had an inattentive learner; h/she was so hyperactive he stressed me (Jalil)

These learners interrupt and distract others, so I feel anxious and sometimes sorry for them (Ahmed, FGD1).

I would say a tough task, a stressful journey (Imene, FGD1)

There are several important issues to note within these extracts: participants' initial reaction to learners with ADHD was anger, stress, and frustration. This might be experienced due to the challenging nature of the situation in their early career. They might not be expecting such a level of heterogeneity in their classes. In addition, teachers' feelings that they have been thrown into a situation without having been adequately prepared could have been translated into a feeling of anger and stress.

It seems sensible to assume that mainstream teachers' lack of experience and preparedness, especially in their first year, led to negative feelings such as anger and stress. Retrospectively, participants identified feelings of anxiety and stress that may have resulted from their inner struggle to create ways to manage learners with ADHD and their external struggle with challenging behaviours like hyperactivity. In addition, there was a sense of some external obligations and limitations as classroom size and other challenges, as previously described in 4.3.2, which led to some negative emotions.

The above quotes indicate that teachers who feel stressed by learners with ADHD feel a strong need for external support. It is reasonable for them to feel this way as they have already identified their struggle with a lack of knowledge, leaving them feeling unequipped and powerless to provide proper assistance to these learners. In addition, it is apparent that stress is influenced by teachers' characteristics on this sample. This means that teachers' beliefs about their own abilities to handle and help learners with ADHD seems to influence their stress levels. The lack of training has resulted in unprepared teachers who feel anxious to deal with disruptive behaviours, yet there was a sense of a positive relationship being built that is associated with expressions of empathy, care, and commitment (see section 4.3.3.3), yet this perceived commitment might be responsible for participants' emotional drain.

4.3.3.2 Time and reduced stress

Surprisingly, a few participants communicated an improved ability to control their emotions and manage their classrooms. Therefore, it is important to engage with the passage of time in these extracts to understand the reported changes in participants' feelings.

Looking at the temporal referents in most participants' passages, we can notice that their stories begin with the past tense, so initially one might assume that they are referring back to their experiences in the past where they felt more stressed. They then move to talk about a time in the present where they thought their emotional reactions to learners with ADHD decreased. This is where participants have discussed their views about their changing emotional experience. These extracts drew my attention to the time frame of emotional development. This is an important insight that emerged among some teachers' responses.

A number of teachers managed to reduce their stress; they explained:

It's a matter of getting used to this type of learners, finding ways to deal with them. When you find the key, you feel less nervous because you know how to respond to the behaviour I once have seen 'an unusual one... (Fouad)

(silence) At first, I found it so difficult, in my first year especially, not really my first year...my first month ... first weeks... it was somehow hard for me to deal with these learners, especially controlling the classroom, delivering the lesson [...] At first, I found it difficult, but through experience and through time I could manage how to deal with these learners... I mean time...time is the key, especially when

you face different categories. Someone who talks a lot...someone who moves a lot (Amina)

Fouad's excerpt implies an increasing awareness of the heterogeneity of his classes since he realised the uniqueness of dealing with the behaviours manifested by learners with ADHD. Prior to this realization, he may have had certain expectations of his students that were not met by those with ADHD, leading him to feel negatively towards them. Amina highlighted the importance of time and experience in developing effective teaching skills and developing control over her emotions. Other participants suggested that managing different types of learners and delivering effective lessons is a learning process that takes time and effort:

The beginning is the hardest; through time I can tell you, I succeeded to manage the situation. I have more control now over my emotions... Now I can have more control over my learners...the first session of the academic year I devote it to discussion with my learners so that I know them and know how they learn (Laila)

I remember the first time I had an inattentive learner; h/she was so hyperactive he stressed me. Now after this long experience, I can tell you I am more patient, although I sometimes feel nervous when the learner is stubborn and does not listen to, but I can control this (laughs)... (Jalil)

The above excerpts demonstrate that the negative emotional impact on teachers reduced through time. It is apparent that their feelings are not static, and they evolve through time, when participants gain some knowledge from their experiences. Overall, teachers in the above passages related their reduced stress to their developed ability to manage the classroom. Laila and Fouad weighed up the impact of their experience on their professional development and discussed how it enabled them to have more control over their feelings. Maybe, after getting some experiential understanding, some participants were able to decrease their stress levels.

4.3.3.3 Care/ Responsibility

Teachers' sense of emotional hardship may be related to the extent to which they were invested in the well-being and success of these learners. They experienced stress as a result of feeling a sense of duty towards their students while also feeling powerless to address certain issues.

Imene shared:

It was (silence)... my first experience...umm... it was kind of different and difficult ... I was thinking about this boy even I go home... I panicked 'what should I do' maybe I was not good enough...

The passage above provides insight into Imene's thoughts and feelings and indicates that she may be experiencing guilt for not being sufficiently productive. Additionally, she is actively taking steps to investigate the root of the problem and find solutions. It also implies her care for the boy with ADHD whom she initially encountered.

Fouad describes how he feels toward learners with ADHD:

As a teacher, I should care for individual learners, I can't leave them without understanding the lesson. When I see that a learner is hyperactive or is daydreaming, I try to attract his/her attention. I do my best to involve them... this situation needs extra time and efforts ... I can guarantee you that no teacher does not want his learners to achieve good results...and we feel frustrated when we see that ADHD learners are not understanding and keep moving...we don't only care for the results but also for our individual understanding (Fouad)

The above excerpt indicates Fouad's investment in his relationship with his learners which is characterised by care for individual understanding. He also expressed his concern regarding learners' outcomes that may sometimes lead to frustration. Fouad's thinking about the schooling and comprehension of learners with ADHD seems to create a sense of frustration. This was particularly experienced when Fouad felt he failed to make these learners understand the lesson. Fouad's view is shared by another participant:

As a teacher, I need to be responsible with whoever learner. These learners are not to be blamed since it's something out of their control...as I explained before something genetic or I don't know...It just needs the attention of everyone to get it solved... learners at that age are not to be blamed...we as adults can help them...although it's tough... maybe more understanding and building closer relationships with them helps to minimise the effects of their behaviours... when you understand and share their concerns... listen to them carefully you can make them listen to you and be less disruptive... (Jalil)

The above excerpt implies a sense of responsibility toward these learners. Jalil suggests that through understanding and shared empathy, teachers can help to create a positive and

more productive learning environment for all students, regardless of their individual challenges.

Jalil's excerpt particularly demonstrates a teacher striving to build closer relationships with learners with ADHD and his cognizance of the vulnerability of learners with ADHD. This relationship is characterised by care and a perceived commitment toward learners, and which aims to break down boundaries between the teacher and the learner leading to more understanding and fewer disruptions. Imene also voiced care toward learners through being considerate of their feelings:

I try to discuss the problem with them individually, I never make this kind of pupils feel that they have a problem, or they are different, especially in front of others... I always avoid embarrassing him/her...to be honest I feel sorry for them that's why I chose to discuss and talk , but not only face to face because... my Facebook account is not really personal... I use it to help my pupils because sometimes you find that a pupil can't talk face to face... so I chose to talk to them in messenger or via phone...they call me and sometimes we hang out together ; for instance, one of my pupils whose name xxx was so hyperactive, he always had problems with his classmates. After discussing with him, he opened up to me and now I know how to let him concentrate (Imene)

The extract above shows Imene's relational engagement with her pupils to build trust between the teacher and the learner. She also described a feeling of empathy toward these learners that might have motivated her to discuss this with the learner in order to create a social and a close bond with him. This might implicate that Imene was not able to truly identify the needs of one of her learners until she was able to forge a relationship with him.

The responsibility and care teachers held for their learners with ADHD was also common across a number of respondents:

I feel bad sometimes...so I keep telling my self maybe I did not do enough or I didn't give such learners much attention...I do my best to involve them...I do further reading I ask colleagues to try and help my learners understand especially those who have autism or ADHD.

He added:

I do my best to provide equal attention for my learners. For example, I sit learners who are inattentive and hyperactive in front of me...so maybe the first or the second table...because I feel they are in need

of a special care... they need to be contained and looked after...they are teenagers...in a very sensitive period in their life... (Ali)

My duty as a teacher urges me to care for every learner...everyone matters and should be made feel that they are valued...You can't just ignore someone just because you feel that it is difficult to deal with...they should be given equal importance (Jalil)

I would be selfish if I say I don't like to teach this category because I need to be responsible with whoever learner. These learners are not to be blamed since it's something out of their control. It just needs the attention of everyone to get it solved (Laila)

These excerpts portray teachers, on this evidence, as thoughtful and responsible agents who take interest in learners' education, including learners with ADHD. However, they are still navigating through their work, without assistance and guidance.

Reflective box:

All those feelings are wrapped into one reality : teachers' challenge of dealing with learners with ADHD due to the lack of preparedness to teach these learners. They are embedded in a teacher-learner interaction and offer different perspectives of looking at the journey of serving learners with ADHD.

I shall argue that although some participants perceived themselves as more capable of controlling their emotions of stress and anxiety through time, one possibility would be that the whole 'problem' of having learners with ADHD in their class has become normalised, so it does not stress them anymore.

4.3.4 Experience and time

RQ4: How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers describe the impact of their experience of working with EFL learners with ADHD?

Educators who participated in the study reported having both positive and negative experiences in teaching learners with ADHD. This theme reflects upon the challenges that teachers face in teaching students with ADHD, but also acknowledges the positive impact of their experience. They described a process of learning how to effectively teach learners with ADHD through trial and error, which resulted in some perceived improvements to their

professional practices. This learning process involved reflecting on past experiences and developing some strategies for dealing with learners with ADHD. This captures how teachers navigate their learning in the absence of formal instruction and guidance.

4.3.4.1 Reflecting upon past experiences

Almost all participants were reflecting on the hardship of teaching learners with ADHD, when asked to describe their experiences. The following quotations serve to sustain the viewpoint that they were reflecting back on their experiences in the interviews and the group discussion:

At first it was not easy and negative to a way you can't imagine, especially the first month of the year...let me explain you something... the first weeks of September is a nightmare because it's our first contact with learners, so we are on our way to discover learners, who is calm who has attention and hyperactivity issues. We are discovering... (Amina)

Imagine you are given a training on teaching ...when you come the first time to the class you see that the methods you have learned do not work for all learners...you realise that these learners needs [sic] extra effort from the part of the teacher...maybe a special or a new method...you are novice, here, you don't know how to react...afterwards you may succeed dependent on your own motivation. It really depends...but I think the start of the teaching career is demanding and difficult especially when you have learners with different abilities (Jalil)

Amina and Jalil described their first experience as an occasion of realisation and discovery. Amina's quote implies that she had difficult times. During this period, Amina had to get to know her learners, understand their personalities, behaviours, and learning needs. She is explaining that this process of discovery and understanding was not easy and required a lot of effort and patience from them as a teacher. The symbolism in Amina's description of her nightmare emphasizes the negative impact of her experience on her mental well-being and overall comfort. It appears that Amina's initial interactions with her students were somewhat disheartening or discouraging. Based on Jalil's statement, it suggests that he was dissatisfied with the calibre of his pre-service training, which did not adequately prepare him for the practical aspects of teaching in the classroom. This implies that teachers might not be fully aware of their own limitations in knowledge and how these deficiencies could affect their effectiveness as educators before they actually start teaching. In other words,

they may not realize the extent of their knowledge gaps and the potential negative consequences these gaps could have on their ability to teach effectively until they are in the classroom.

R: Can you describe your experience of teaching Learners with ADHD?

Fouad: Let me tell you something... I still remember the first time I met someone with ADHD (laughs) so back in the day.... It's remarkable... you know... (Fouad, FGD1)

It was (silence)... my first experience...umm... it was kind of different and difficult ... I was thinking about this boy even I go home... I panicked 'what should I do' maybe I was not good enough... (Imene)

In response to the question about his experience teaching learners with ADHD, Fouad pauses and reflects for a moment. He then starts to describe his first encounter with a learner with ADHD. Fouad's laughter suggests that the experience was memorable and possibly unexpected. By describing the encounter as 'remarkable', he may be indicating that it left a lasting impression on him and potentially shaped his subsequent experiences of teaching learners with ADHD. Imene when describing her first experience, she pauses and remains silent while reflecting on it. She goes on to explain that her initial experience was challenging and left a significant impact on her. She admits that she was preoccupied with thoughts of a particular student even after leaving school and felt anxious about how to handle the situation. She expressed doubts about her abilities as a teacher, suggesting that she may not have been adequately prepared or skilled enough to handle the challenges she encountered. This may also suggest a sense of commitment toward her learners.

Reflecting back on the hardship teachers face in their early career. Mohamed explained:

For example, you are given a car to drive for the first time ...at the beginning you automatically find it difficult... what is needed here is practice and experience to do this properly...the same is for ADHD learners.

Mohamed gave an analogy to explain that teaching learners with ADHD can be challenging at first, much like driving a car for the first time. Just as someone who is new to driving may find it difficult and unfamiliar, with time, practice, and experience, they can learn to operate the car proficiently. For Mohamed, this is similar to teaching learners with ADHD, where there may be initial difficulties and obstacles. However, with patience, perseverance, and experience, teachers can develop some strategies and techniques to support these learners

in achieving their potential. Therefore, Mohamed emphasizes the importance of patience, perseverance, and experience when it comes to teaching learners with ADHD.

4.3.4.2 Perceived improvements

Teaching learners with ADHD may seem an exhausting thing to do. Unexpectedly, teachers identified some positives from in-job experience. Overall, they reported an increased ability to manage the classroom, through time. They reported a number of positive attributes of their experiences including management strategies and an increase in self-confidence. This theme details some few positives that teachers have ascribed to their experiences.

Laila's description of her experience conveys a similar mutuality:

R: so, in what ways has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?

L: um....yeah, a lot I got used to this category of learners and I treat them like brothers and sisters so that they won't have that feeling they are different...I now know how to calm them and involve them. I learned some strategies that I found them helpful to ADHD learners. I try to break the routine from time to time since I know learners with the problems of inattention and hyperactivity get bored easily

I felt that Laila became more conscious of her experience and reflections which had only come fully to mind as a result of her thinking about it within the group context. By saying "I got used to this category of learners", she might be implying that having these learners in class became normalised as time passes.

Similar to Laila, Fouad, on this evidence, communicates the same feeling:

It's something new for the teacher...something positive because when you face this problem in the future you will know how to deal with it and advise others how to overcome this...It's a win-win situation. The learner will have proper schooling and you will have an increasing experience, developing yourself (Fouad)

Fouad's account indicated that teachers reflect on their practices by taking a moment to step back and analyse a situation when faced with a similar issue in the future. As the interview progressed, his depiction of the experience became more optimistic in tone.

Imene concurs with Fouad. she relates:

After some time, you will discover that you developed the ability to solve problems...how to face different difficulties and how to deal with different learners...when you have, for example, hyperactive learner... you may use the knowledge you acquired via your previous experience with another hyperactive learner to react in a good way... yeah... I developed my own way of teaching so that if I faced [sic] this problem in the future I would know how to react and deal with the situation ...xxx was a good experience that motivated me to change my method of teaching with this type of learner.

Imene's quotation implies that she did not recognise the ability to solve problems until she felt some success. In retrospect, she realizes that her experience teaching learners with ADHD has influenced her teaching approach with those students, and she has developed her own techniques. It suggests that she is currently not receiving external assistance and is relying on her personal experience to determine the most effective methods for her students.

Amel's experience was similar to other participants:

The only thing that helped me to develop ways to deal with ADHD learners is my experience ... because in our schools, in Algeria, and even universities we were not taught about this category and how to deal with them, neither theoretically nor practically.

Based on Amel's description, it appears that her experience was instrumental in enabling her to effectively support learners with ADHD.

Speaking about how hardship wanes through time, participants also talked about developing more patience. Jalil communicated:

I remember the first time I had an inattentive learner; h/she was so hyperactive he stressed me. Now after this long experience, I can tell you I am more patient, although I sometimes feel nervous when the learner is stubborn and does not listen to, but I can control this (laughs)...

Laila shared the same idea in the FGD, and she perceives herself as becoming more patient:

My experience with ADHD learners was not that easy at the beginning...though it helped me to become more patient. I learned to be patient through time; I learned how to deal with ADHD learners (silence) I learned to react to this behaviour in a thoughtful manner with more understanding...experience helps you to build

trust between you and your learners... you can develop an understanding of the job demands...

Laila reflects on her experience working with learners with ADHD and acknowledges that it was initially challenging for her. However, she also expressed that this experience helped her to become more patient and develop a better understanding of how to work effectively with these learners. Over time, she learned to react to 'disruptive' behaviours caused by ADHD in a thoughtful and understanding manner. Overall, participants suggest that this kind of experience can help teachers build trust with their students and gain a better understanding of the demands of their job.

Experience, for Ahmed and Mohamed was a chance to revise their teaching methods:

I remember I had a learner [xxx] who is disruptive and hyperactive compared to other learners...I put him at the back of the class, so he won't disrupt other learners. However, this did not help... I discovered that I did a mistake by moving them at the back of the class...since when I moved him at the front...I could notice that he is more attentive...I can see all what he's doing when he is in front of me...by giving them attention...making them feel he matters they tend to be more attentive...this is what I have noticed... I think they need care, and they feel to know that they are valued (Mohamed)

As highlighted by Mohamed, in the above quotation, he discovered that seating learners with ADHD at the back of the class would only exacerbate the situation, suggesting that this approach was not effective. Similarly, the following excerpt tells of an instance whereby Ahmed evaluated the effectiveness of his teaching practices:

Ahmed: (laughs) I still remember my first years of teaching ADHD learners in 1990 where I used a stick to punish learners whenever I notice someone who is hyperactive and inattentive, but I found no positive effect of this strategy... Via time, I switched to another method: reward to motivate learners to pay attention (silence) my experience has had a positive impact on my development as a teacher.

(FGD1)

Ahmed's analytical evaluation of his own teaching practices has resulted in a change from punitive, which did not work for his learners, to more positive and rewarding teaching methods. This change seems to happen through time after some critical assessment of his instructional approaches in relation to learners' outcomes, weighing up the merits and the

demerits of punitive strategies to bring the learner back on task. Experience, on this evidence, allowed the teacher to self-evaluate and assess his teaching methods and led him to find out more and explore his teaching practice. There was a sense of understanding of learners' needs being built and Ahmed adapting his teaching methods accordingly.

It seems that in light of the absence of formal training and cooperation in the workplace, participants choose to use their experiences as a source to find ways to function and influence the surrounding environment. They are actively thinking about ways to improve their experience via investing efforts to understand their learners as much as they can. With experience, a teacher may have a better understanding of the material they are teaching, as well as some strategies that can be used to effectively teach it. It seems that their experience offered a chance of professional discovery.

Participants' continuous thinking about their teaching implies that they are very pro-change when it benefits learners. Their continuous consideration of past events and reflecting on them, in the interviews and the group discussions, to see what works and what does not work for their learners indicates their constant search for the most effective strategies to engage and educate learners with ADHD. Their accounts showed disparity in their retrospective and current views on ADHD and how this affected their understanding. They suggest a strong sense of an active role being played by teachers who do not passively accept the status quo and their feelings of helplessness. Rather, they look for ways to improve their practice and develop themselves. They identified some strategies that they found useful in engaging learners. They mentioned:

Problems help you to develop some strategies and methods to use to provide good schooling for these learners, so, in my opinion, I use the strategy of rewarding as a solution maybe sweets, adding extra points and I also tend to build strong relationship with them and their parents also because they are the key to everything (Fouad)

Laila: sometimes, I devote all the session for games to break the routine

Ahmed: for me, I can't find time to use games. If I do, I will not finish the program. For me, I sometimes start the lesson by a joke to keep learners' attention ... I also reward these learners to reinforce good behaviour

Imene: for me, I try to engage learners in some activities like disturbing [sic] the copybooks to their classmates, worksheets, etc. I also use L1 to attract their attention. These learners need to be engaged in some activities as: football, basketball, etc.

(FGD1)

The passage shows that these teachers apply a range of CMS_s to learners with ADHD, including reactive and proactive strategies. They try to engage them proactively in games and activities to foster their attention and to harness their energy in a productive manner. Other ways of ensuring positive experience included the use of reactive behavioural classroom strategies, through reinforcing their behaviours, to increase the occurrence of a more positive behaviour. They could more or less manage the situation and find potential solutions. However, these behavioural strategies for motivating learners involve making assumptions about their motivation levels.

4.3.4.3 Confidence and experience

Participants who had more experience teaching students with ADHD shared a unique perspective that their confidence in their teaching abilities increased as they saw success from implementing management strategies. This perspective is essential to gain a better understanding of the experiences of these participants and to remain committed to the idiographic nature of IPA. Some responses included:

At the beginning of my career, I still remember that I had no trust on my skills. Now I can tell you that I am more confident...through time you will develop your self-worth when you see yourself overcoming difficult situations... now after 14 years of teaching I am more confident, but I am still learning ... I can't say the opposite...but when you are more confident, you know you can get there... I always say this to novice teachers ' You will keep learning till the last minute ... this is not a weakness, yet it helps you to become more confident ...
(Mohamed)

The last sentence in Mohamed's quote 'you will keep learning till the last minute' implies that he did not achieve the required level of understanding. His account is noteworthy in that despite their extensive teaching experience, they still have a strong desire to learn more. This was also observed in 4.3.2.1 where many participants expressed a need for additional training. This suggests that although teachers may experience positive growth

through gaining more experience, they still have reservations about the accuracy of their understanding, which is largely acquired through their own experiences. Furthermore, the above excerpts demonstrate that teachers had the ability to adjust their teaching practices based on the needs of their learners, indicating that they are willing to adapt their approaches to best meet their students' requirements.

Jalil describes his experience as a chance for self-discovery and an opportunity to work on weaknesses to develop confidence in one's abilities:

Although we faced and we still face some difficulties with ADHD learners, yet these difficulties may lead you to discover your strengths and weaknesses that you can work on to develop yourself... through time you will be more confident ...you will know that you can face any obstacle because sometimes our fear of difficulties may affect our ability to respond appropriately... even when you fail it's not the end of the world... me after a long experience I still face many hurdles, but I just try to think positively about them and I carefully look for solutions...

Jalil's quote implies that there is a sense of a manageable challenge that can be contained if teachers develop confidence and reflective thinking to manage the situation. This stresses the importance to focus on developing teachers' confidence about their own abilities or their self-efficacy.

Ali shares Jalil's and Mohamed's views on the positive role of confidence, yet he brought another aspect which was not previously discussed:

R: In which way has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?

Ali: My experience helped me to get used to this disorder and overcome many problems I found in teaching ADHD learners.

R: Can you explain why did you say that?

Ali: Through time, you will develop confidence that is necessary for the teacher to deal with any situation, including the case of ADHD learners, which might seem tough and time-consuming. For me, confidence helped me to manage stress.

The phrase 'for me' indicates Ali's commitment to describe a personal experience which may not necessarily be shared by others. Like other participants, Ali spoke about the natural process of building confidence and the pivotal part it might play in overcoming challenges,

yet he was the only participant to suggest the link between confidence and stress-management. Developing more confidence buffered him against experiencing emotional strain.

Ahmed's view supports previous responses:

R: In which way has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?

A: My experience helped me to understand my pupils' needs and feelings ...it helps you to be more confident when you acquire the skills needed... confidence is a magnet that attracts success

The last phrase in the above quote and the participant's use of the metaphor 'confidence is a magnet that attracts success' implies that Ahmed wants to make a case about confidence. It is likely that this metaphor has been used as an exaggeration to emphasise the importance of confidence for a teacher's career. Laila highlighted:

At the beginning, I used to doubt my abilities whenever I'm confronted with some learners who are not easy like inattentive and hyperactive learners especially because we were not trained about this problem but now, I believe I'm more able to deal with tough learners... through time you train yourself you learn to work under some circumstances that needs personal effort since solutions cannot be otherwise found.

The above excerpt underlines Laila's sense of self-confidence being built, where she seems to develop more job satisfaction.

It seems clear from participants' accounts that their experience of working with learners with ADHD has some personal implications as they described a growing confidence in their skills. The relationship between teachers' experience and their confidence is complex and can vary depending on the individual. Generally speaking, it can be said as teachers gain more experience in their field, working with different types of pupils, they may become more confident in their ability to manage the classroom. This may result in more confidence to handle some classroom challenges that may come up.

It is important to highlight that this perspective is shared by a few participants who had more experience of teaching learners with ADHD. Others may still navigate through their own experience with uncertainty. Therefore, establishing a compromise between different

modes of learning, formal and informal learning, would help teachers to function more effectively.

A final reflection and note on teachers' journeys:

On the surface, it seems that teachers have felt some positive side of their experience. Time is an important factor because it is the only thing that allows opportunities to emerge. Over time, the participants seemed to adapt to the behaviours of learners with ADHD, which became more normalized and less stressful for them. They also talked about developing 'their own way of teaching' which implies that they are, to a large extent, teaching in silos, without much collaboration or coordination with others. Their comments regarding their perceived challenges imply their needs for an additional help. Their level of understanding and knowledge of ADHD is still inadequate, and the difficulties associated with teaching learners with ADHD are still present. Therefore, significant changes are required to provide better conditions.

Instead of traveling the road of personal and emotional struggle, teachers' preparation may protect them against feeling ill-equipped to face the ongoing challenges. Therefore, support is always needed to persevere with their endeavours.

When participants were encouraged to think back and consider their past experiences, they saw reflection as beneficial, so if there were regular CPD sessions, along formal opportunities for development, to reflect on their own practice and share experiences, this would have speed up their development.

4.4 Summary of the chapter

This chapter presented the analysis of data related to the four questions which undergird this study. Algerian EFL middle school teachers who took part in the present study, confirmed by my own experience, seem to have limited knowledge regarding ADHD, yet they still have a desire to learn more about it via some kind of formal training and opportunities for CPD. This would allow them to function more effectively in the school context. Even though working with learners with ADHD presented them with some challenges, by the end they spoke positively about the role of their experience. They

stressed the role of a whole school intervention which would help to provide a better schooling for learners with ADHD and improve their experience of working with these learners. It seems possible to assume that the local authority and government are not doing enough to facilitate the inclusion of learners with ADHD. This could lead to the conclusion that there is a real need to revisit the education of learners with ADHD by providing more attention to learners with ADHD. There is also an urgent need to empower teachers by providing the necessary support they need to accommodate such learners. It must be conceded that teachers' desire to function within the existing environment appears to be laudable given the amount of support they receive. In the next chapter, I will critically discuss the findings in relation to previous literature, relating them to the wider context of research and the theoretical framework.

5. Chapter Five: Discussion of Findings

5.1 Introduction

Several themes were identified through the analysis of participants' experiences, which were then grouped together to address the research questions. This chapter provides a further interpretative analysis of those themes by reflecting on the theoretical stance and previous literature. I will start by summarising the results of the interpretative phenomenological study and examining how my research aligns with the broader literature and Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory. I will utilize not only the data obtained from the accounts of the participants but also draw upon my own reflections and experiences as someone who was immersed in the context.

It is important to highlight that Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory (1990) enabled me to conceptualise teachers' experience in the wider context. In addition, it helped me to understand the individual traits that teachers could bring to the task of their development which can be taken into account in further formal training. This theory aided us in drawing a holistic picture of how healthy development can take place. After immersing myself in teachers' narratives, I employed this theory as a framework for understanding and situating their experiences within the broader context.

5.2 A snapshot into major findings through the lens of Bronfenbrenner's theory

The decision to use this particular framework was not based on the preferences of the researcher or any other external factors. Rather, the framework was chosen because it was deemed to be the most useful and relevant for understanding the experiences of teachers as they had described them in interviews and group discussions. During the analysis, teachers were relating their experiences to others including internal and external factors within immediate and remote environments. In addition, personal and time-related factors played a significant role in integrating their narratives. Therefore, the PPCT model was selected to ensure that their experiences and their needs were accurately and effectively represented. Understanding the various levels of influence on teachers' experiences can help to develop more effective strategies to support them and improve outcomes of learners with ADHD.

The microsystem represents the lowest system or teachers' immediate environment and their interactions with pupils with ADHD. The mesosystem was epitomised by teacher-parent interactions. The results of this inquiry revealed some factors in the exosystem (the training system) which found their way into teachers' immediate environments. Teachers expressed their dissatisfaction with the quality of training where the parameters of development appear to be defined by external parties. In addition, curriculum requirements are external factors that shape the context in which they work and influence their interactions with learners. These policies and requirements are developed at a higher level, such as at the national or regional level. In Algeria, the national curriculum standards serve as a blueprint for educators to follow in their teaching approaches (macrosystem).

The interaction between different systems, namely the microsystem, mesosystem and exosystem, has uncovered different challenges at different levels. Participants described different levels of interaction where different factors within the environment seem to affect their experience. Undoubtedly, they shared relevant information regarding other parties which can be used to enhance their effectiveness in dealing with learners with ADHD. Therefore, the following discussion dwells both on the factors that impede and also that mitigate the challenge of teaching learners with ADHD, as expressed by participants in the present study. Overall, their actions and socialisation seem to be shaped by the characteristics of the surrounding environment which is important for their professional growth. Bronfenbrenner (1994) put forth that ecological systems are valuable in human development as they "support and guide human growth" (p.37). Therefore, creating a supportive environment is highly crucial.

In addition to the social aspect, the person dimension is also reflected in teachers' accounts. Different environmental barriers had a negative impact on teachers' knowledge level (*impeding resource*) and their emotional well-being through expressing heightened emotions engendered from interacting with learners with ADHD. However, they showed perseverance and acted on care to bring about favourable outcomes (*force*). The complex nature of teaching learners with ADHD requires the ability to provide effective instructional support for these learners while also managing their emotional responses to difficult situations, such as dealing with disruptive behaviour or managing their own frustration or stress. Overall, it requires teachers to develop emotional regulation strategies and seek

support from colleagues. They actively *demand* establishing connections with other stakeholders due to the challenging nature of educating these learners.

The study also found some positive outcomes developed through *Time* via experience (*resource*), as some teachers reported an increase in their confidence levels and a decrease in their stress levels over time, in addition to some perceived development. In general, the teachers' experiences were contextualized within various time frames, including comparisons between their past and current experiences, as well as their future aspirations. In addition, their experience toward career development was influenced by a variety of factors including personal characteristics such as their dispositions, resources and demands. Furthermore, environmental factors such as class size, collaboration, and training opportunities as well as curriculum played a significant role in shaping their experiences.

The above-mentioned *person* characteristics are suggestive of teachers' agency and their initiatives navigating their own professional career development. Although the study reveals some agency from teachers to address the limitations in the workplace, it is to some extent constrained by the multi-layered ecological systems and different factors at micro-meso-exo and macro systems. Their interaction with pupils in the microsystem influenced their well-being and put them under great pressure. Additionally, they faced challenges due to a lack of collaboration with colleagues and parents in addition to inadequate training opportunities (exosystem), and the overall framework for teaching (macrosystem), including the highly prescribed curriculum. They appear to work in silos due to lack of cooperation among various stakeholders.

Key messages in Bronfenbrenner's Propositions	Key findings
<p>Proposition 1: individual development is shaped by objective as well as subjective experiences</p>	<p>Environmental factors (class size, lack of training, lack of collaboration) as well as subjective experiences (beliefs about ADHD, doubts, feelings, hopes and the sense of duty) shaped teachers' development.</p> <p>Both positive and negative experiences shaped teachers' development and ability to teach effectively</p>
<p>Proposition 2: proximal processes become progressively complex as a result of interaction between the person and their immediate and external environment</p>	<p>Teachers' development became more complex as other external factors come into play including class size, training, collaboration with colleagues, time constraint, and curriculum requirements.</p>
<p>Proposition 3: the form, power, content, and direction of the proximal processes vary systematically as a joint function of the characteristics of the individual and their environment.</p> <p>It highlights the importance of the reciprocal interactions that occur between an individual and their immediate environment in shaping their development. The quality of these interactions can have a significant impact on the individual's growth, learning, and well-being.</p>	<p>The quality of interaction between teachers and their environment (including pupils, colleagues, psychologists, and external commitments) had a negative impact on teachers' growth. Their knowledge level seems to be low due to lack of appropriate training. Other environmental factors including class size, lack of time and the benchmarked curriculum shaped their experience of teaching learners with ADHD and their career development.</p>

Table 4: Bronfenbrenner's theory propositions and their alignment with teachers' journeys

5.3 Teachers' conceptualisations

An initial objective of the project was to explore how Algerian EFL teachers perceive ADHD. With respect to this objective, it became evident that participants held varying perspectives on ADHD. Based on the teachers' responses, it appears that most of them are adjusting their teaching approaches to accommodate students with ADHD in their classrooms, despite their emphasis on factors within the child that could potentially contribute to ADHD.

When I was reading teachers' responses regarding their conceptualisations of ADHD, it appeared to me that, while they used medical terminology to describe what ADHD is, none of them recommended a medical response to ADHD. They acknowledged that it is their own duty to make learning accessible for learners with ADHD and emphasized the importance of utilizing their own agency and personal experiences to achieve this. They exhibited a proactive mindset and openness to adapt their teaching methods to meet the requirements of students with ADHD. This means that they are using the social model to respond to the needs of these learners. They also acknowledged the external influences on ADHD and made sense of it through educational barriers that restrict the learners' freedom.. In other words, the environment of the learners' schooling may adversely affect their experiences and may create an impaired belief in their own potentials. This is in line with the literature as researchers have observed the significance of contextual challenges, such as the difficulties that school environments present for children with ADHD, as these settings are commonly characterized by noise and numerous distractions (McLaren and Antle, 2017). All participants described employing a number of classroom management strategies (CMS_s) to tailor the learning environment according to learners' requirements. The strategies employed seem to be learnt through experience, through reflection, trial and error. It is important to note that the strategies reported by participants are not specific to ELT but were general classroom strategies intended to foster learners' engagement. Turketi (2010, p.18) suggests that since learners with ADHD enjoy playing games they can easily "release their hyperactivity, take a break from the learning routine and even stay focused on their learning goal much longer", and adds that games are beneficial because they improve "their interactive skills, fostering communication and cooperation". Games that involve the use of English are a good way of consolidating understanding and developing skills. They are more engaging for learners as they involve movement. Although using games as a tool to engage

learners with ADHD and promote language development can be advantageous, it is important to note that only one teacher reported using this strategy in their classroom. A variety of techniques should be considered in an EFL classroom in addition to varying interaction and classroom activities patterns through employing whole-class teaching, group and pair work, using both open and closed questioning techniques, encouraging choral responses, and assigning individual tasks (Scrivener, 2012).

There is also an 'othering' at work, surrounding participants' views regarding ADHD, that runs the risk of viewing the experience of disability as something fundamentally different from other ways of being in the world, which could result in a form of discrimination where people with disabilities are perceived as typically different or 'other'. They viewed their behaviours as a form of deviation or disturbance from what is considered normal. In their description of what ADHD is, participants predominantly emphasised hyperactivity, overlooking the aspect of inattention. It is possible that hyperactivity is more outwardly observable, making it a more salient feature in their perceptions. Additionally, societal stereotypes and popular representations of ADHD (see page 167) may also play a role in biasing participants toward highlighting hyperactivity over inattention. Alternatively, individual experiences and awareness levels regarding different aspects of ADHD might vary among the participants, influencing their focus in the descriptions provided.

Learners with ADHD might be abnormal in the sense that it is not the norm: the number of school pupils is not the majority and so is not the norm. However, the term abnormal can have some negative connotations, implying that their behaviour is undesirable and goes against the expectations of the teacher or even the society for a calm and an orderly classroom environment. Labeling the behavior of learners with ADHD as 'abnormal' may suggest that teachers anticipate these students to conform to the classroom environment. Boudida and Rouag (2018) highlighted the influence of culture within Algerian Arab-Muslim society, noting that adults in this cultural context tend to display a certain level of acceptance toward the physical restlessness of children. In a similar vein, Timimi and Timimi (2015) argued that individuals who share similar cultural values and beliefs work together to collectively influence and shape their perception and understanding of the world that surrounds them. This suggests that participants' views of what 'ADHD' is may not solely determined by individual perspectives but are rather constructed through shared cultural

influences. Consequently, the perception of what is deemed 'abnormal' is shaped by cultural norms and may not necessarily imply the teachers are expecting learners with ADHD to conform to the classroom norms as they genuinely strive to support and engage these learners, even though they face challenges due to limited knowledge and training.

Cultural acceptance of some behaviours should be taught as describing someone's unique experience as 'abnormal' can lead to stigmatization. In other words, using this term to refer to individuals who have experiences that differ from the norm can cause them to be labelled negatively or perceived as deviant (Sonuga-Barke *et al.*, 2023). There is a potential for stereotypes to infiltrate the classroom if learners with ADHD continue to be labelled as 'deviant' or 'abnormal'. On that account, Demetriou (2022) claims that it is advisable to refrain from using strong and stigmatizing labels in language. Instead, language should be inclusive and devoid of societal norms or biases. Policies can also promote inclusive language practices by encouraging the use of neutral or non-discriminatory language. They hold the authority to shape and influence language, thereby impacting the cultural mindset as indicated by Fiala-Butora and Stein (2016). In other words, they have the ability to shape and control the language used within a society or culture. The language, in turn, has a significant impact on the mindset and beliefs of people within that culture.

It seems sensible to assume that if these learners are provided with more opportunities to move and harness their energy, their behaviours would be less 'problematic'. Metzger and Hamilton (2021) argue that in an educational setting that encourages children's physical movement, provides opportunities for free play and outdoor activities, and operates under the belief that children are innately active, teachers would have a more positive perception of children with ADHD compared to environments where young children are expected to sit still at a desk for most of the day. A reasonable conclusion can be made that if teachers were given training in more inclusive methods, as well as responsive and stimulating English Language Teaching (ELT) techniques, they would probably have a less negative view of these behaviours. However, teachers' training seems to prioritise theoretical content in order to complete the curriculum and meet the objectives of each lesson. The approach to teaching in Algeria is still largely teacher-centred, with the teacher playing a central role in directing and controlling the learning process, while the needs and preferences of learners are given less emphasis (Bellour, 2017). In a traditional classroom environment, children with ADHD

are under stimulated and get bored easily (Maisel, 2022). Therefore, a shift to more learner-centred approaches is required to create a more inclusive and engaging environment for learners with ADHD.

It is important to note that I sensed a degree of ambiguity from some participants' short responses, silences, and long pauses when it comes to conceptualising ADHD. This implies a lack of understanding of ADHD, and it may be indicative of teachers adopting a unitary conceptualisation without fully understanding it. From a bioecological perspective, the person dimension, at this level, reflects teachers experiencing environmental barriers in terms of shortage of knowledge. Bronfenbrenner (1976) explained that what happens or fails to happen in any given environment relates to events and interrelationships with other systems (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). He also claimed that individuals do not live in isolation from their surrounding environment and are impacted by it. In Algeria, inspectors are responsible for disseminating critical information to teachers through training workshops (Ghedjghoudj, 2014). From a bioecological perspective which addresses the reciprocal impact between different systems and person dimension, it appears that the 'inadequate' training, delivered by inspectors, is responsible for their lack of knowledge. In other words, the use of the bioecological model in this study helps to explain how the lack of support and guidance, in the form of training and opportunities for continuous professional development, can contribute to disparities in teachers' knowledge and understanding of ADHD.

Educators' lack of knowledge could be attributed to the lack of training on additional support needs education, neither in in-service nor pre-service training. Their shortage of knowledge and negative perceptions of ADHD is unsurprising given the little, if any, training participants have received. Different studies echo a similar finding as they reported that teachers had no prior training on ADHD (Alanazi and Al Turki, 2021; Guerra *et al.*, 2017; Melhem, 2020; Mohr-Jensen *et al.*, 2019). In addition, there is evidence in the data that teachers did not get information through formal learning rather they sought knowledge through informal modes of learning such as reading searching the internet and learning from experience, as opposed to formal education channels. This finding echoes findings from previous studies which highlighted teachers' tendency to acquire knowledge through

informal means (Alanazi and Al Turki, 2021; Cabaroğlu and Tohma, 2021; Dessie *et al.*, 2021; Kern *et al.*, 2015; Lawrence, Estrada, and McCormick, 2017).

To better support teachers in teaching learners with ADHD, it is important to address their training needs and knowledge gaps. Therefore, there is still a need for additional competence enhancement courses to augment and transcend the basic knowledge teachers have about ADHD. By doing this, teachers would feel more supported and equipped to provide effective instruction and support to learners with this condition. Previous literature demonstrates that teachers who have received prior training on the subject have demonstrated greater knowledge and are more capable of providing assistance to students with ADHD (Alkahtani *et al.*, 2013; Sciutto *et al.*, 2016).

5.4 Teachers' perceived challenges

The experience of teachers in teaching learners with ADHD appears to be influenced by specific aspects of the microsystem, or classroom context. This suggests that certain features of the classroom environment can have an impact on how teachers perceive and approach teaching learners with ADHD. Bronfenbrenner claims that individuals are influenced by characteristics of the microsystem context (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). According to the study, teachers expressed dissatisfaction with the class size as it posed challenges to their teaching experience, also negatively impacting students who may fall behind in such an environment. The study suggests that large class sizes can have a negative effect on teachers' abilities to address individual educational needs. Teaching in general becomes particularly difficult in crowded classroom.

Overall, it seems clear through looking at teachers' views regarding the classroom structure that there is much that can be done to tackle issues within these classroom organisations. Large classes in small classrooms might influence learners and teachers negatively. Blatchford and Russel (2020) state that teachers struggle to provide individualised attention in large class size. Naude and Meirer (2019) shared this view and added that large class size presents a challenge to inclusive education in the South African context. Similarly, teachers who contributed to Gaastra *et al's* (2020) study perceived class size and lack of time as the main barrier for the successful accommodation of learners with ADHD. In line with the above findings, Braude and Dwarika (2020) interviewed seven South African teachers to

explore their experience of supporting learners with ADHD and found that large class size was among the barriers to the successful accommodation of learners with ADHD. The comments made by teachers regarding the classroom structure appear to be applicable to any subject, not only the EFL context. However, more research is needed to confirm this conclusion.

With reference to the ecosystemic theory, microsystem is represented by teachers, their colleagues, and learners with ADHD. Within the immediate microsystem school level, teachers exist within complex relationship between people which impacted their experience and the course of their development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Teachers described various proximal interactions, including interactions between teachers and students, interactions with colleagues and psychologists. Some teachers who engaged in reciprocal interaction with colleagues found it instrumental to find solutions to some issues they face. Accordingly, teachers described instances where they felt other colleagues helped them to deal with some challenges. These processes if they occur through extended periods of time may help teachers to develop their practice (Rosa and Tudge, 2013), yet they were not so much permanent and sometimes prevalent in the teachers' work experience. This explains why teachers called for increasing opportunities for peer-tutoring. Creating opportunities for professional learning communities is core to providing authentic networks of support within the profession.

Figure 2: Bidirectional interactions that are crucial for teachers' development.

Participants believed in working in partnership with colleagues , psychologists, and parents for a positive school microsystem. Ainscow (2016) views that shared experiences among different stakeholders in an inclusive setting enable colleagues to challenge their own assumptions regarding their practice. This means that school can provide an opportunity for teachers to develop professionally via presenting personal testimonies of how different teachers make it work so that less experienced and knowledgeable teachers would benefit from such an interplay.

Mesosystemic interactions were also described by participants including parent-teacher interaction. Teachers' role at this level is a mediator between school and home. Overall, these meetings also seem to take place when difficulties arise. In addition, teachers sought parents' support in those meetings. Participants reported that supportive parent-teacher interaction would ease their understanding of the behaviour exhibited by learners with ADHD as well as their needs. Thus, maintaining supportive links with parents is critical for teachers' functioning in the school context. This supports the findings of Lawrence et al. (2017) and Hapsari et al. (2020), who discovered that participants emphasized the importance of involving various stakeholders, such as parents and psychologists, in effectively addressing the needs of learners with ADHD.

Although participants seem to acknowledge the crucial role of parental involvement, yet they reported negativity and disengagement within their relationship where misunderstanding characterised this bidirectional interplay. Parents, in those meetings, took less interest in their children's education. They seem to rely upon the school for the progress of their children as they did not take an active role in the education of their learners. This explains why teachers recommended getting more assistance from parents. Less parents' involvement may indicate less parents' efficacy in their ability to help the learner with ADHD academically. One possibility could be that the behaviours of learners with ADHD make it challenging for parents to support their learning activities, so they choose to be less engaged in their child's education since they could not help them. This might cause overreliance on teachers' skills and knowledge to improve the schooling of learners with ADHD.

A disconnect between home and school, which seems to concern teachers in the present study, has been associated by previous research with negative parent-teacher relationships

and difficulties in communication (Gwernan- Jones, *et al.*, 2016; Michel *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, parental involvement was identified as a significant challenge by the study's participants. Their views regarding parents' involvement suggest that this latter is an important aspect of the microsystem that can have an impact on the experiences of teachers of accommodating learners with ADHD. The lack of parental involvement and support may make it more challenging to effectively address the needs and challenges of students with ADHD and may contribute to a more negative experience for both the teacher and the student.

As I have previously explained, parents' involvement emerged as a challenge for the participants who described how careless/ helpless were parents for their ADHD children' education. This resonates with Braude and Dwarika (2020) who reported a lack of parental involvement and support for their students with ADHD. Understanding how to improve communication between parents and teachers may be crucial for the inclusion of students with ADHD and supporting teachers in their efforts to effectively teach and support these learners.

Ward *et al.* (2022) highlight the importance of training interventions for teachers regarding ADHD. Such interventions can help to enhance their knowledge and understanding of ADHD, enable them to create a classroom environment that is conducive to the needs of students with ADHD, and equip them with effective strategies to manage the classroom. However, through looking at teachers' responses, it seems that they were not adequately prepared to handle the diversity present in their classrooms. Teachers' sense of being ill-equipped to handle learners with ADHD in this situation appears to be related to lack of training. It seems that the training program that these teachers attended lacked an essential feature of practicality and did not emphasize the importance of inclusive education, particularly in regard to teaching students with ADHD. This finding reflects those of Stites *et al.* (2018) who also indicated that there was a need for teacher preparation programs to place greater emphasis on preparing teachers for the realities of inclusive classrooms, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively support students with diverse needs. It is also in line with Ward's study (2020) which reported that some participants who received pre-service training found it ineffective to deal with ADHD since it did not focus on learners with ADHD. It also corroborates Liang and Gao's study (2016)

which found that teachers, in their study, perceived the training they received insufficient to provide a good accommodation for inattentive and hyperactive learners. They identified lack of knowledge and pragmatic experience as barriers to a proper accommodation of learners with ADHD.

Teachers in the current study reported a lack of knowledge and training in relation to teaching and accommodating students with ADHD, which suggests that there may be a broader issue of inadequate preparation for inclusive teaching practices. In other words, the lack of knowledge and training reported by the teachers in the current study may reflect a broader trend of insufficient support and resources for teachers to effectively accommodate the needs of students with disabilities or other additional support needs in mainstream classrooms. This highlights the need for further research and programs to improve teacher training and support in relation to inclusive teaching practices, particularly in the context of teaching learners with ADHD. This finding appears to be consistent with previous studies which have underscored the necessity for further professional development (Barkley, 2015; Cabaroğlu and Tohma, 2021; ComRes, 2017; Greenway and Rees Edwards, 2020; Guerra *et al.*, 2017; Gwernan-jones *et al.*, 2016; Lasisi *et al.*, 2017; Lawrence, Estrada and McCormick, 2017; Mohr-jensen *et al.*, 2019; Sciutto *et al.*, 2016; Soroa, Gorostiaga and Balluerka, 2016).

It seems that teachers are taught following traditional PD, usually an expert delivers a set of technical skills. This type of professional development focuses solely on imparting a set of technical skills without taking into account teachers' preferences. Overall, it seems to be driven by narrow aims and is more theoretical in nature, failing to acknowledge how they can apply these skills in practice (Kennedy, 2005). Teachers reported receiving instruction on prescriptive teaching frameworks namely the PPP which assumes a mechanical process of learning and teaching. According to Prabhu (1990) (cited in Maley, 2018), while imposing a specific methodology may be useful for ensuring a uniform approach to education systems and textbooks, it is not the key factor for successful teaching and learning. Teachers tightly control the PPP approach; they typically follow a structured sequence of steps: presenting new Information, providing guided practice, and then expecting students to independently produce the language or demonstrate their understanding (Bryne, 1986). Following this method of instruction, teachers take on a dominant role, and learners are positioned as passive recipients of the teachers' commands (Willis, 2003). This rigid structure can limit

students' autonomy and discourage them from actively engaging in the learning process. In addition, learners with ADHD frequently face difficulties in a classroom environment, which typically requires them to adhere to regulations, remain seated, and sustain attention (Kendall, 2016). On the other hand, they tend to demonstrate improved performance in subjects that involve physical and practical activities, suggesting that instructional methods incorporating movement are likely to be beneficial for them (DuPaul and Stoner, 2014; Imerag *et al.*, 2013). My findings corroborate the conclusion I made in chapter two (see section 2.9.2) which suggested that adopting a more communicative teaching approach that encourages students to actively participate in genuine and meaningful exchanges, following a student-centred approach, is likely to foster a more inclusive environment for learners with ADHD. Therefore, to improve the effectiveness of language education and foster the engagement of these learners, it is important to implement more communicative and less prescriptive methods such as TBLT and PBL which involve learner-centred activities and experiential learning (Kokotsaki, Menzies and Wiggins, 2016). By implementing teaching methods that prioritise learners' needs and move away from rigid and structured teaching methods towards more interactive and engaging approach, there is a possibility to encourage learners' participation and active engagement.

It is important to highlight that the motivation of both the teachers and the learners plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of teaching and learning. In other words, the needs of teachers and students are more important than the strict adherence to a particular methodology. The participants expressed the necessity for training to address their practical challenges and requirements, closing the divide between theory and real-world application. Therefore, addressing knowledge gaps can be better achieved by providing training that is tailored to teachers' needs and practical experiences. Training should focus on giving teachers a voice and allowing them to decide on their preferred mode of instruction, as well as the particular subjects they wish to study in these professional development sessions. By incorporating teachers' feedback and preferences into training design, it can be more engaging and relevant, leading to more effective implementation in the classroom. In addition, this approach can help to generate empirically validated knowledge that is grounded in the experiences and needs of teachers and learners, bridging the gap between theory and practice.

Overall, a tailored approach to teacher training can help to address the knowledge gaps and misconceptions about ADHD, leading to better support and outcomes for learners with this condition. Boud and Hager (2012) argue that teachers' professional development should be incorporated in their daily practice. Therefore, off-site training is less relevant to the changing classroom context (Kennedy, 2005). Staged CPD offers the possibility to address and surpass the limitations commonly associated with traditional, one-time CPD programs (Goodyear, 2017). Accordingly, I suggest that promoting a culture of ongoing learning and inquiry would assist in tailoring more evidence-based instruction for teachers, thus promoting an inclusive environment for all learners. In addition, a rigorous assessment of teachers' professional development needs is also important. Furthermore, opportunities for peer-learning, critical reflection, discussion and evaluation of existing academic literature, and other forms of CPD might be beneficial. Reflective teaching is a significant approach to bridging the gap between theory and practice. By engaging in reflective practice, an individual can identify and articulate various forms of thought and theoretical concepts that are present within the context of their work. This process enables them to recognize the connections between theory and practice and integrate the two in a meaningful way (Mathew, Mathew and Peechattu, 2017).

It is evident that the educational instruction provided to teachers primarily centred on teaching fundamental concepts that catered to the needs of the majority of students. As a result, learners with ADHD may have been overlooked in the education system. The data suggests that the training teachers received was primarily lecture-based and focused on meeting the objectives of each lesson rather than on inclusion or ADHD. This might imply that teachers were trained to teach in a very traditional, teacher-centred approach where students are passive recipients of knowledge rather than active participants in the learning process. According to Bellour (2017), Algerian classes are predominantly focused on the teacher, with comparatively less attention given to the needs and requirements of learners. In addition, it is observed that teachers tend to strongly adhere to traditional teaching methods, specifically the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), as noted by Benmoussset and Benmoussset (2018).

The approach of viewing learners as passive recipients of information may not be appropriate for students with ADHD, as they may require more active engagement and

movement to facilitate their learning. Instead, they would benefit from utilising their energy and movement in the learning process. On the other hand, learner-centred approaches that promote autonomy and engagement may be more effective for these students. By empowering them to have more ownership of their learning and creating opportunities for movement and physical activity, teachers can better accommodate their unique learning needs and support their engagement and participation in the classroom.

The above discussion suggests that alternative approaches to teaching, which prioritize learner-centred methods and support the active participation of students with ADHD, would be more effective in promoting their learning and success in the classroom. CLT moves away from traditional lesson to activities that foster learners' engagement through role plays, group work activities and project-based learning (Richards, 2006). Teachers can vary interaction patterns in EFL classes to encourage learners' engagement and interaction through engaging the entire class, organising activities in pairs and groups, and assigning individual work, as suggested by Scrivener (2012). Through encouraging learners' engagement, CLT would be more inclusive of diverse learners, including those with ADHD, as it involves them in practical situations. Thus, a shift towards more communicative approaches would likely benefit learners with ADHD.

The influences at the macrolevel relate to the workload and the responsibility to abide by the top-down imposed curriculum. The participants reported feeling burdened by the pressure and responsibility of meeting the objectives of each session and completing the curriculum. The implication is that teachers may feel constrained by the curriculum, and that this can hinder their ability to provide a quality education for all students. In addition, the pressure to meet curriculum objectives can be a significant challenge for educators, as it can affect their emotional well-being and ability to effectively teach and engage with students. Teachers in the Algerian context are tasked to comply with a national curriculum (Law N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008, Article 20). They are not included in the planning of curriculum reforms, which can lead to feeling marginalised and lacking sense of ownership over the process (Gherzouli, 2019). Findings by Boudouaia (2021) indicated that Algerian middle school teachers in their study felt obligated to get through the curriculum content in a specific order and had limited flexibility and independence in modifying it to suit learners' needs. Therefore, incorporating the perspectives and the experiences of teachers in the

design of the curriculum can help to ensure that the needs of both learners and teachers are taken into account. On the other hand, receiving a ready-made curriculum to be endorsed and followed is likely to leave little room for the teacher to fashion their classes according to the requirements of certain contexts. Prescribing what should be taught may reinforce power imbalance between the 'elite' (theorists or policy makers) and the 'consumers' of teaching practices (teachers, and learners). In addition, this prescribed approach may not leave space for differences that exist across classrooms. The top-down approach to curriculum design blissfully disregards teachers' beliefs and their contextual knowledge. However, teachers should be actively encouraged to take responsibility of their teaching (Nghia *et al.*, 2020) and disempowering teachers should be resisted at all costs. This stresses the need to hear teachers' voices regarding some decisions that affect their teaching path before implementing any reform.

Having to follow a pre-determined syllabus implies that English teachers cannot teach from a very subject-centred viewpoint only due to the added responsibility of meeting the overall goals of the syllabus. These are the symptoms of what Littlejohn (2012) called the McDonaldised approach to material development which leaves little room for creativity, personalization, and adaptability, as teachers are expected to follow a set script and stick to a strict schedule. This may erode the fundamental role of inclusive education which aims to make the learning environment more responsive to learners' different needs. I shall argue that although teachers seemed to be constrained by the prescribed curriculum, they used some CMSs to involve learners with ADHD. However, there is a need for a *de facto* recognition amongst higher level decision makers of teachers' voices.

In addition to the constraints imposed by the national curriculum, teachers feel burdened by the workload associated with achieving these goals. They expressed their concerns about the insufficient amount of time. This finding supports the research conducted by Hoadjli and Latreche (2020) which revealed that middle school teachers in Mila province, Algeria, expressed dissatisfaction with the amount of work they have to handle. They argue that the workload that Algerian middle school teachers are facing represents a difficulty for their professional development, and it also has an impact on the quality of their teaching.

Teaching according to standardized requirements that are imposed from above implies the existence of a uniform student population with similar educational requirements. The one

size-fits all curriculum may inhibit teachers from embracing learners' experiences (Symeonidou, 2022). There is a need to rethink the curriculum provided for teachers to allow for a more learner centred and differentiated approach to teaching. This issue of the curriculum coupled with large class size may place a significant burden on both teachers and students. In such conditions, it may be challenging for them to make the appropriate adjustments to support the needs of learners with ADHD, who may be expected to adapt to existing norms and conditions that may not be optimal for their learning needs. Given these hindrances, it is important for policymakers to recognize the importance of addressing such concerns by making changes to the curriculum and educational policies to support more effective and inclusive teaching practices. By creating policies that prioritize the needs of learners with ADHD and providing the necessary resources and support for teachers, it may be possible to foster a more responsive and effective pedagogy that better accommodates the needs of all learners. Teachers' experiences would serve to bridge the gap between theory and practice.

Overall, participants revealed that a cultivation of good practices by all stakeholders to reflect the best interest of children with disabilities would go a long way to improve the situation of teachers and also learners with ADHD. Bronfenbrenner (1990) recognised this nested dimension of interaction as an important tool of human development. For teachers to develop optimally in their early career, there should be a consistent communication between different stakeholders who can push the inclusion of learners with ADHD forward. The environmental factors seem to be responsible for teachers' early career struggles. Bronfenbrenner (1993) recognized certain negative aspects of the environment that can lead to dysfunction and highlighted the crucial role of a positive and supportive environment in fostering healthy development. Participants described the interrelatedness between different layers of the society and suggested the need for more partnership.

Within the existing conditions including the shortage of knowledge, the inadequacy of training, the limited time frame and crowded classes, teachers, especially in their early career, may not be able to develop and accommodate learners with ADHD properly. Through examining the interrelatedness of different systems, I concluded that educators are left possibly frustrated and at loss to cope with learners with ADHD, especially in their early career. They did not indicate a mutual responsibility between different stakeholders

including parents, psychologists, and other stakeholders. Instead, they stressed the need to foster communication between different parties. Bronfenbrenner (1999) argued that when individuals are exposed to negative environments that are marked by a lack of consistent communication between different systems, their development may be hindered. This idea can help to explain why teachers often feel like they are not succeeding in the early stages of their career.

They iterated that the success of accommodating learners with ADHD was hinged on the interrelatedness of different systems, including colleagues, parents, ministry of education and government. The fact that teachers valued cooperation with other stakeholders, an important aspect of the bioecological systems theory, I would argue that a whole school development approach is necessary for teachers to deal with learners with ADHD. Hughes and Cooper (2007) suggested that ADHD is a complex condition that arises from multiple factors, and its effective management requires a coordinated and collaborative approach involving parents, teachers, and educational psychologists. In addition, Bessai (2018) believes that involving parents is an important factor in the success of inclusive education in Algeria. Hoadjil and Latrache (2020) conducted a study on middle school teachers and found that they recognized the need for support from the Ministry of National Education, particularly in the form of training and assistance to better engage students with diverse needs.

5.5 Teachers' feelings toward learners with ADHD

Teacher-learner interactions seem to be characterised by emotional strain. Teachers' use of emotive language such as 'anxious' and 'stressed' imply that their journey of teaching learners with ADHD appear to be emotionally challenging. Participants reported feelings of anger, stress and frustration that resulted from their working with learners with ADHD. It is important to note that participants felt emotionally worn-out during their initial years of teaching due to the behaviour manifested by learners with ADHD. Their accounts of their psychological experience were broadly congruent with the existing research in the field (Greene *et al.*, 2002; Lawrence, Estrada and McCormick, 2017; Mulholland, Cumming, and Jang, 2015; Mulholland, Cumming, and Lee, 2023; Roger *et al.*, 2015). The different ways through which learners with ADHD were described implies that the interaction between teachers and these learners is complicated. According to the data, teachers hold the belief

that learners with ADHD create disruption and divert the attention of other students. Consequently, they perceive the presence of learners with ADHD to cause annoyance and distraction. Previous literature has indicated that teachers have perceived learners exhibiting ADHD-related characteristics as disruptive and bothersome to both themselves and other students (Aldrup *et al.*, 2018; Cuelli *et al.* 2020; DuPaul *et al.*, 2004). As noted by Mullholland *et al.* (2015), this can lead to negative attitudes toward learners with ADHD. teachers develop negative attitudes when they try to regulate the behaviour of learners with ADHD. It also appears that teachers' negative feelings, in the present research, emanate from their struggle with discipline problems including learners' misbehaviour, non-compliance and disruptions.

The above discussion echoes strong evidence for the behaviours of learners with ADHD as one of the main sources of teachers' emotional exhaustion. To reiterate, it seems clear that the presence of learners with ADHD in the classroom had a significant psychological impact upon teachers and contributed to their stress as they may find it more demanding to teach these learners. The increasing workload pressure of accommodating learners with ADHD within the classroom interfered with the teachers' emotional stability especially during the initial years of teaching where they reported feeling mentally and psychologically washed-out. In other words, teachers may feel an added emotional strain when they have students with ADHD in their classes.

The negative attitude toward learners with ADHD could be also explained by the participating teachers' lack of training and knowledge regarding ADHD in addition to other factors including class size, lack of time and the benchmarked curriculum which make them unable to respond to the behaviour of learners with ADHD more effectively. Therefore, another potential explanation for stress triggered by learners with ADHD is teachers' inability to decide on which teaching approach or methodology best suits learners with ADHD. This is unsurprising when teachers invest more than they receive, knowing that previous findings indicated their lack of training on additional support needs, here ADHD education. Teachers have previously shared their concerns regarding their training which failed to prepare them adequately to deal with learners with additional support needs including those with ADHD. Consequently, different factors seem to influence and shape teachers' attitudes or emotional experience. Price and McCallum (2015) noted that

ecological factors including classroom challenges and lack of preparation impact teachers' well-being and ability to maintain reciprocal interactions. Teachers expressed a tension or a conflict between institutional requirements to follow the mandated curriculum and their compassion toward learners with ADHD. Hochschild (1983) claimed that teachers may experience emotional labour as a result of the tension between the job requirements and their internal feelings. Emotion labour, in this study, manifested as feeling of anger and stress in relation to dealing with learners with ADHD, but also feelings of care and empathy toward these learners. The emotional labour of the participants was also initiated by the behavioural challenges posed by learners with ADHD. This aligns with Humphries' research (2020), which indicated that learners' inappropriate behaviour and conduct have led to emotional labour for teachers. Similarly, Zaretsky and Katz (2019) contended that teachers consistently experience emotional labour because of a greater occurrence of challenging behaviours in the classroom in comparison to other professional contexts.

Teachers' emotions, in this study, can be conceptualised not only as an individual reaction to learners with ADHD or their psychological state, but also as signals of broader institutional issues. Consequently, emotional labour serves as an indicator to teachers that the issue lies not in their inadequate performance, but rather in existing regulations or policies that are triggering emotional labour. Benesch (2020) argued that teachers' emotional struggles mirror the difficult circumstances they encounter within classrooms, schools, and the broader societal context. Addressing these concerns should involve discussions with colleagues who might also be facing similar stress and uncertainty regarding fulfilling their duties. The emotional labour revealed in the research presented in this thesis may signify that the policy is not functioning optimally and requires restructuring, incorporating insights from those directly impacted by it.

Like those interviewed in Miller and Gkonou's (2018) study, the teachers I interviewed were dedicated to an approach of 'teaching as caring' and keen to build robust relationships with their students (Miller and Gkonou, 2018, p. 54). Another finding was that as they gained more experience, teachers improved their emotional management skills by acquiring the ability to create emotional or physical separation from demanding circumstances.

5.6 The impact of teachers' experience

Through their accounts, teachers revealed a reflective mind and a conscious belief in their weaknesses and perceived strengths, that can be responded to in future professional development. I became highly interested in hearing and invoking their personal narrative of struggle and reward. Primacy was given to participants' voice is reciprocal as participants shared their aspirations and recommendations. I felt the responsibility to ensure anonymity and confidentiality since participants trusted me for their stories.

When participants were prompted to think back and consider their past experiences, they demonstrated an ability to introspectively recognize both their strengths and weaknesses, as well as the positive and negative aspects of their experiences. They identified through self-reflection, their strengths, obstacles, aspirations whilst being in circles of influence. They also shared ideas and recommendations about how their teaching can be improved and stressed the need for further development. They voiced their demand for establishing a solid network between different stakeholders to actively build their development. Reflective practice is an important asset that "enables teachers to stop, look, and discover where they are at that moment and then decide where they want to go [professionally] in the future" (Farrell, 2012, p. 7).

Bronfenbrenner and Morris (1998, 2006) noted that positive and negative subjective forces experienced in the past may contribute in meaningful ways to shape the developmental process. Looking retrospectively, teachers' experience of teaching learners with ADHD had a more negative influence on teachers especially at the beginning of their career where they felt unprepared to teach learners with ADHD, resulting in feelings of stress and anxiety. They experienced psychological changes at the level of their emotional reaction to learners with ADHD. In addition, It is worth noting that they reported gaining more confidence and could perceive themselves as capable of enacting changes. Due to the dedication and care (*force*) teachers have to their roles and their students , they were continuously looking for ways to accommodate learners with ADHD through seeking additional support or using their own experiences. Their experience of working alongside ADHD seems to be evolving in the sense it helped them to act on care to bring about some improvement in their practice. It could also be sensed that they felt a responsibility toward these learners which is evidenced in their attempt to respond to the ongoing demands of classrooms with learners with ADHD. It

also demonstrates that Algerian EFL middle school teachers, in the participant sample, strive earnestly to accommodate the needs of learners with ADHD.

Some teachers seem to build greater resilience to negative consequences by acquiring problem-solving skills and cultivating patience. They choose to surpass their limitations and persevere to deliver satisfactory outcomes, driven by their dedication, commitment, and concern for their students. In addition, they could demonstrate some strengths and perseverance in circumstances that threaten their professional stability. Of critical importance, it seems that persistence and commitment were key to teachers' efforts to find ways to function within the existing conditions.

Thinking through the lens of continuity of proximal processes helped me to notice the ways through which teachers' biographies impacted their practice, and current experience. It is widely believed that teachers' past experiences influence their current practice (Harkonen *et al.*, 2017; Naraian, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, teachers in the current research admitted that they gained some in-service experience of working with learners with ADHD. Their meaningful engagement with these learners helped them to develop some proactive and reactive strategies, which might be indicative of a positive and a proactive mind-set. Littlewood (2014) describes teaching as a process of exploration where teachers act as researchers who experiment with various teaching methods, instructional techniques, and approaches to engage students and enhance learning.

If teachers were provided with regular CPD sessions that encouraged them to reflect on their own experiences and practices, they would have benefitted from such initiatives which would enable them to exercise their agency more effectively. By saying this, I do not mean to underplay the importance of formal training since teachers themselves conveyed a need for more training on ADHD, which would help them deal with learners with ADHD in their early career. Teachers are always in need of more expertise. Training or any form of CPD might protect teachers from feeling stressed looking for the best way to include these learners. However, this would be more fruitful if combined with reflective courses that can help to bridge the divide between theoretical knowledge and practical application. According to Canh (2014), it is recommended that teacher education programs incorporate a component focused on reflection, which may involve instruction in various skills such as "observation skills, self-monitoring skills, and self-evaluating skills" (Canh, 2014, p. 217)

which is crucial for teacher performance. It is natural and expected for human beings to develop and evolve their sense of self over time. This is in line with the process of human development which involves continuity and change (Bronfenbrenner, 2005).

The above views are aligned with IPA which postulates that human beings are thrown into a world of objects and relationships (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This belief is manifested in the way teachers are influenced by various factors in the environment (referred to as ecological systems in Bronfenbrenner's theory). Additionally, IPA, inspired by Heidegger's philosophy, acknowledges that "being in the world" is always relative to a particular perspective and time frame (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009, p. 18). The passage of time played a crucial role in how teachers interpret their own experiences and emphasizes the dynamic nature of their professional development.

Li and Ruppert (2021) suggest that there is no set criteria or established traits that define inclusive education professionalism. Rather, it is important to take into account a variety of experiences, both formal and informal, that contribute to a teacher's professional identity. In order to fully understand the concept of inclusive education professionalism, a comprehensive approach is necessary, one that considers all relevant experiences that have shaped a teacher's professional development.

Teachers' experiences can be seen as a process of getting influenced and exerting some influence on the environment. The main feature of these experiences, as put by Bronfenbrenner, is that they alter the existing relations between the person and the environment. It became clear that teachers have an impact on the development of the learning environment by fostering social connections through interactions with their students, implementing various classroom management strategies, and thriving to maintain positive relationships with their students using a combination of proactive and reactive approaches such as rewards, token economies, punishments and physical activities like having them distribute copybooks to their classmates and seating them closer to the teacher.

Teachers' efforts in making a contribution are laudable within the existing environment. In addition to this aspect of change, pedagogical improvement has been noticed by teachers via the implementation of some classroom-based strategies, that were primarily learnt from

experience. What piqued my interest was teachers' awareness that CPD would help them to increase knowledge and understanding of ADHD. In other words, participants expressed a vested interest in improving the status quo via more training that would develop teachers' knowledge and understanding of ADHD, thus promoting the learning of learners with ADHD. Following teachers' recommendations, there is an urgent need for teachers to be provided with a good atmosphere that fosters their own development. This might include preparing them to accommodate different learners with different needs.

To sum up what has been said so far, previous findings suggested that teachers have not received an adequate formal education and enough opportunities for CPD to improve their teaching practices, yet they could develop some experiential knowledge about ADHD. Their reflective, honest, and introspective examination of their own experiences demonstrates a responsible conviction to advance the education of learners with ADHD. They also expressed a desire to know more about ADHD and showed the ability to adjust their teaching to accommodate the diverse needs of learners. The lack of input has resulted in participants relying solely on their own agency and experience as the only recourse to lead changes and working out solutions, depending more on their developed skills to manage the situation. This provides future trajectories to be considered for teacher development. It is undeniable that the analysis portrays teachers' awareness of their needs, weaknesses, and strengths, yet their beliefs and conceptualisations about ADHD were rather muddled and contradictory. This implies that allowing teachers to form their own beliefs about ADHD and how to handle it through personal experiences alone (referred to as 'solo proximal processes', Bronfenbrenner, 1989) may not be enough and could potentially lead to incorrect understanding and actions. I have identified several gaps in teachers' education that contribute to their challenges in dealing with students with ADHD. Teachers' sole reliance on self-directed learning would limit their engagement in more complex activities. A comprehensive approach is necessary to address the challenges faced by teachers in accommodating learners with ADHD when the various ecological systems are not functioning harmoniously. Teachers' perceived beliefs about their emotional development might indicate that they get used to the struggle of accommodating learners with ADHD. Their individual initiatives may be coupled with more structured input on how to reflect effectively. This would help to clear any misconception about the condition being studied.

Boudersa (2016) emphasized the significance of encouraging active participation and reflective teaching among teachers in Algeria.

It is worth highlighting that change, according to Bronfenbrenner, and adjustment is the result of continual reciprocity of interactions between past and present experiences. This stresses the need to implement the voices of teachers in different aspects of pedagogical practice. The study pointed to how *person* characteristics of participants, including knowledge, experience, and confidence, can affect the course of development. It also shows the impact of different environmental factors that affected teachers' experience in different ways. However, this *person* characteristics should not be considered separately from their environment as human bioecology signifies the interplay between the environment and an active individual (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). Similarly, teachers' reported perceptions about cooperation in the school context raises questions regarding the level of awareness of different stakeholders who should give a hand to build successful inclusive classrooms for learners with ADHD. This is in line with Bronfenbrenner's argument (1989) who claims that human development should be thought of as a joint enterprise between the person and their environment. Besides, collaboration and teamwork were identified as significant factors in the successful inclusion of learners with ADHD (Carrol and Hurry, 2018; Lawrence *et al.*, 2017; Ward, Kovshoff and Kreppner, 2021).

A system theory has provided a rich framework through which to describe and explain teachers' experiences. It has helped to enrich the understanding of participants' experiences and it revealed dilemmas the teachers face and experience within a single and different layers of the environment. The study concluded that in order to promote teachers' development, interventions focusing on school engagement and support (proximal processes) and addressing teacher education through different forms of CPD will be most effective and beneficial. I contend that development is a cumulative result of various influences, including immediate, remote, and individual factors. It is crucial to recognize that support can be obtained from both close, immediate as well as distant and remote environments. At an innermost level, whole school ethos may help to reinforce teachers' development and forge ahead beyond the confines of the existing conditions. For example, a successful teacher-parent partnership would be one where both share the interest of enhancing the situation of learners with ADHD. In addition, building communities of practice

where teachers share the goal of professional growth may help to foster their development. The rationale behind the establishment of professional communities of practice often lies in providing teachers with opportunities to engage in critical discussions, exchange ideas, and address any misconceptions or uncertainties they may have (Robinson, 2017). Furthermore, an engaging ministry of education which listens to the voices and includes the needs of teachers in the training would push teachers' development forward. Bronfenbrenner (1979) noted the importance of goal consensus between different settings in facilitating individual growth and development. Therefore, different parties need to share a vision toward ADHD. If teachers receive support from immediate and extended contacts, their experience of teaching learners with ADHD would have been less negative and the impact of different support links would have been optimised for them, especially in their early career.

I would argue that ELT methodologies are rich and are likely to help teachers engage learners with ADHD more effectively. CLT approaches, namely TBLT and PBL, involves learners in genuine scenarios, role-playing, games, and group activities, while teachers act as facilitators and learners take ownership of their learning (Littlewood, 2013). It uses small-group activities, which involve kinaesthetic activity, through different activities including information-gap, jigsaw activities, games, running dictation. This approach would be particularly helpful for learners with ADHD as it enables them to channel their energy positively as it increases their participation in the classroom. Therefore, implementing the strong CLT methods, in this context, including TBLT and PBL can be advantageous for them. In addition, teachers would feel less stressed as learners will feel more engaged in activities that are interesting and enable them to reach their full potentials. Conversely, activities that require prolonged sitting and listening can be uninteresting and cause them to lose focus as learners with ADHD have a limited attention span and cannot sit still for extended periods (APA, 2013). In a nutshell, reviewing current teaching methodologies and improving the support given to teachers would be advantageous for students with ADHD and would promote the agenda of inclusivity.

5.7 Teachers' experience in a nutshell

Figure 3: A snapshot of teachers' experience

Teachers' previous experience has affected how they are now. First, they realised their prior training experiences were not sufficient to prepare them for their current roles. Therefore, it is possible to think that the transition from pre-service training does not seem to be successful. They thought back to the difficulties and emotional challenges they experienced, particularly in the early stages of their teaching career.

Dewey (1938,1997) suggested that experience is located on "an experiential continuum" (p.33). Participants' present experiences are influenced by their past experiences. The events, interactions, and circumstances that they encountered in the past contributed to their knowledge, beliefs, skills, and perspectives. This ongoing cycle of experience demonstrates that participants are continually evolving and adapting based on the cumulative effects of their past experiences. Overall, the teachers' experiences were framed within different timeframes, encompassing reflections on both their past and present encounters, along with considerations of their future aspirations, constrained by the mandated curriculum.

Teachers described an ability to critically reflect on their own experiences, understand their impact, and make informed decisions based on this awareness. This suggests that teachers can exercise their professional judgment and adapt to their specific educational contexts, considering societal influences without being completely bound by them. Similarly, Herbert and Rainford (2017) maintain that meaningful CPD occurs through reflection and experiencing. This perspective underscores the importance of agency and critical reflection in teaching practice. The educators participating in the study expressed their opposition to the inequities present in the state-mandated education curriculum. The study also identified a tension between teachers' acceptance of the new curriculum standards and the practical implication for their teaching. Teachers, in the present study, voiced concerns regarding the inadequacies in teacher education that hinder the progress of inclusive practices for

learners with ADHD. Teachers' adaptive orientation and resistance to maintain the status quo are different aspects of their agency (Emirbayer and Mische, 1998; Pyhältö et al., 2012; Vähäsantanen, 2015).

Behind each curriculum, there exists a politics of knowledge that determines what is included or excluded, shaping the content based on decisions about which knowledge, cultural experiences, and perspectives are incorporated. The Algerian education system is governed by a top-down curriculum, mandated on all teachers (Law N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008, Article 20). This is characterised by a neo-conservative tradition which portrays the curriculum as a predetermined compilation of subject knowledge meant to be conveyed through the institutionalized processes within schools (Alvunger, 2018). However, teachers seem to exert efforts in tailoring the curriculum to meet learners' learning needs through a number of activities that help learners with ADHD to use their energy in meaningful ways. It is important to note that most of the approaches shared by participants were not exclusive to English Language Teaching (ELT); instead, they were general teaching strategies designed to assist learners by enhancing engagement and attention. This aligns with the research conducted by Cabaroğlu and Tohma (2021), which highlighted that ELT professionals, as observed in their study, did not employ strategies exclusive to the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context. Instead, they utilized strategies aimed at assisting learners with ADHD in managing movement and attention.

Overall, the confluence of their past and their present experiences raised their awareness of their needs for a healthy environment where different stakeholders share mutual responsibilities. They were cognizant of their needs for more CPD. Rather than struggling to teach learners with ADHD by going above and beyond and relying solely on their own efforts, teachers could benefit from a coordinated approach and opportunities for professional development.

5.8 Answering the big question: what is like to have a learner with ADHD inside the classroom?
Having a learner with ADHD presented a unique set of experiences, which were marked by a mix of emotions, at different intensities, encompassing stress, anger, care, confidence, and a sense of duty. Their journeys were also filled with different challenges including the crowded classes, lack of knowledge and training, in addition to the lack of support and partnership.

Reflecting on their teaching experiences, educators found that instructing students with ADHD was a particularly challenging, especially during the initial stages of their careers when they felt ill-equipped to handle such learners, leading to heightened stress and anxiety. This was accompanied by psychological changes, particularly in how they emotionally responded to students with ADHD. The idiographic commitment of IPA helped to capture moments of joy, anger, and stress in teachers' journey of accommodating learners with ADHD.

Notably, these teachers mentioned that once they developed some expertise in teaching learners with ADHD, they experienced a boost in confidence, perceiving themselves as more adept at implementing positive changes. Driven by their commitment and concern for their roles and students, teachers consistently sought ways to support learners with ADHD, either by seeking additional assistance or drawing upon their personal experiences. They implemented caring practices and worked to enhance their teaching methods. Their sense of responsibility toward these learners was evident in their continuous efforts to address the ongoing challenges within classrooms that included students with ADHD. This illustrates the sincere dedication of Algerian EFL middle school teachers in the participant group to accommodate the specific needs of learners with ADHD.

5.9 Summary of the chapter

Teachers' experience seems to be an aggregate of personal and environmental influences which should be considered in future research. While there is a clear individual influence on teachers' own experiences, the presence of teachers within various layers of society cannot be disregarded, as it can either help to address ongoing challenges in the workplace or potentially exacerbate the whole situation. Thus, I would postulate that in order for teachers to develop optimally, their ecological systems need to be considered. It seems that teachers are learning to cope with the situation from their experience through experiential learning. However, they seem to recognise the role of cooperation with other teachers, parents, and psychologists to accommodate learners with ADHD and meet their needs. This raises concerns regarding the awareness of different stakeholders. Drawing on the responses of teachers, a key recommendation was increasing cooperation between colleagues and other stakeholders. It is also essential to give careful thought to how

teachers can influence and guide their own professional growth and progress. Altogether, these may promote a comprehensive understanding of teachers' career requirements.

6. Chapter Six: Concluding Chapter

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapter presented the analysis of data in relation to each question and discussed the findings against the existing literature. As evidenced in the literature review,

there is a void in the literature associated with the experiences of Algerian EFL middle school teachers when it comes to teaching learners with ADHD. The rationale behind this study was to fill in this void by giving voice to their experiences. The study aimed to investigate teachers' conceptualisations and challenges, as well as their feelings and the effect of their experiences. The analysis of data yielded interesting findings in relation to those themes. In this chapter, I will first evaluate the extent to which the study has answered the research questions which underpin this study. I will also summarise the key findings related to each question to identify the strength and the limitations of the present research. Second, I will present the contribution to knowledge that the study has made. I will then discuss the limitations of my study. This chapter culminates in recommendation for future research and actions, as well as some personal reflection on the PhD journey.

6.2 Summary of the findings

The following section presents a summary of the findings in relation to teachers' conceptualisations, perceived challenges, and feelings as well as the perceived impact of their career paths.

6.2.1 How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers conceptualise ADHD?

Understanding how teachers conceptualise ADHD contribute to knowledge by identifying some misconceptions and any negative perceptions toward ADHD. Regarding the aim of examining how Algerian EFL middle school teachers perceive ADHD, it was discovered that participants have varying conceptualizations of ADHD, as each participant holds distinct perspectives. From the analysis, ADHD emerged as a heterogeneous disorder demonstrated through the unique and conflicting perspectives of teachers that capture the debatable nature of ADHD. The idiographic nature of IPA allowed me to capture the heterogeneity of teachers' responses regarding their understanding of ADHD.

Previous research has taken different views on the causes and conceptualisations of ADHD. In this study, and participant sample, Algerian EFL middle school teachers' conceptualisations of ADHD seem to be wide-ranging. Although participants provided different conceptualisations into how they see ADHD, their responses convey a sense of doubt. The data I gleaned from their responses regarding their understanding of ADHD enabled me to build some conclusions, yet their responses were unsatisfactory and lacking a

thorough explanation. They used vague language which failed to show a good command on the topic of ADHD. This lack of detailed responses and doubt is not surprising given the lack of input and professional knowledge about the condition among participants who took part in the study, which they identified as one of the challenges they face. Some focused on the biological attributes of ADHD, yet they display a lack of detailed knowledge about these factors. They typically refer to these causes as being related to genetics or the brain. Consequently, ADHD for them is a 'disorder' that might be attributed to biological, neurobiological, or hereditary causes, yet just few participants expressed their views deliberately regarding the use of drugs to 'treat' ADHD. This indicates that teachers are using the social model to respond to the needs of learners with ADHD and are nevertheless willing to modify the classroom setting to better suit the needs of learners with ADHD.

An important issue seems to be the lack of knowledge and training surrounding ADHD. Participants expressed extreme dissatisfaction with the quality of training they received. They do not seem fully prepared to include learners with ADHD. Overall, the teachers' responses on their understanding of ADHD suggest that the Ministry of National Education needs to look closely at their needs and create more effective professional development programs accordingly. It is worth noting that the conceptualisations of the Algerian middle school teachers, who participated in this study vary significantly, and are shaped by their experiences. Information about ADHD is obtained through reading and searching the internet, rather than from training provided by the government.

Participants also had some negative perceptions toward learners with ADHD by viewing them as 'abnormal' or a 'distraction' to other learners. They referred to learners with ADHD as bothersome, disruptive, and occasionally abnormal. They described how the behaviour of the ADHD learner interrupts both the teacher and the surrounding environment, consequently disrupting the natural progression of the lesson. The negative attitudes towards ADHD may reflect societal beliefs of what is considered normal or typical behaviour for individuals with ADHD, causing stigma toward these learners. However, if learners were given more opportunities for movement, their behaviours would have been regarded less negatively. On the other hand, teaching in a more teacher-fronted approach where learners are required to sit and listen to the teachers would not be beneficial for learners with ADHD, who tend to respond well to kinaesthetic tasks and learn best through moving (Maisel,

2022). Therefore, their learning may be enhanced by incorporating movement into the learning process. In other words, learning may not be effective for individuals with ADHD unless there is some form of physical movement involved (Turketti *et al.*, 2010) (this point will be discussed with more details in the next section).

6.2.2 How do different factors contribute to Algerian EFL middle school teachers' sense of challenge?

Participants identified a number of limitations and expressed frustration regarding different issues that hinder the successful inclusion of learners with ADHD which result from the interaction of different systems and layers of society. They conveyed to me that dealing with a learner perceived to have ADHD is challenging. Compared to the first question, participants had more elaborate views on the challenges they face on a daily basis. They delved into various obstacles they encountered with greater detail and specificity, highlighting the specific obstacles that could impede their teaching practices at various levels within their ecosystem.

On a micro level, teachers complained about the large number of learners per class which makes it difficult for teachers to provide the necessary support and make the interaction with learners with ADHD more difficult. Such a situation requires teachers to assess not only the learners' unique needs but also the demands of the classroom environment. What I suggest here is having less crowded classes and allocating more time for the English language teaching session. This leads us to highlight the need for structural changes to be enacted by policy makers. In addition, teachers' interaction with learners with ADHD seems to impact their emotional well-being, causing stress and anxiety (see section 6.2.3).

The lack of necessary support and training is another challenge for teachers. This finding corroborates the findings of previous studies (Alanazi and Al Turki, 2021; Guerra *et al.*, 2017; Moh-Jensen *et al.*, 2019). They seemed to be puzzled by this undertaking which was further illustrated in their accounts of how they felt toward these learners. This calls into question the quality and the type of training they received. It is possible to assume that the training received seems insufficient to address the heterogeneity found in classes these days, which accommodate learners with mixed abilities and needs. Thus, it places some pressure on teachers who may find themselves facing challenging situations that require effort and time

to be solved. Therefore, the demand on teachers would be more pressing when dealing with such learners. According to O'Rourke (2015), regular teachers may not feel equipped to support students with additional support needs due to insufficient knowledge and training and recommended that IE needs to take a new direction if such challenges continue to occur. This highlights the importance of providing better training to teachers to help them address the challenges they face.

Teachers raised concerns regarding the interrelatedness of different systems which might imply that they are left possibly frustrated and at loss to cope with learners with ADHD, especially in their early career. They complained about the lack of cooperation in the educational setting with parents who did not indicate a mutual responsibility. The link between home and school was perceived to be generally negative and helpless. Thus, they stressed the need to foster communication between different parties. According to Carrol and Hurry (2018), the implementation of a comprehensive school-wide program is essential in supporting students with ADHD. This approach is also recognized by article 24 of the UNCRPD as a means of providing reasonable accommodations for individuals with additional support needs. As I have previously mentioned, teachers also emphasized the importance of collegiality among teachers, as it may enhance their teaching effectiveness. This highlights the significance of establishing Communities of Practice (COP_s) where teachers can collaborate, exchange knowledge, and learn from one another. These opportunities may provide a platform to share common concerns where less experienced teachers would benefit from more experienced teachers. As Both and Kourkoutas (2016) claimed, building COP_s in inclusive settings would help to enhance the social engagement of different parties.

At a higher level, the challenges facing teachers in their practice include the mandated curriculum. Teachers expressed dissatisfaction with the quality of the curriculum, which adheres to certain benchmarked standards. Planning the lesson according to pre-existing standards might not be adequate in inclusive classrooms where learners have different needs and abilities, which may require lesson planning that goes beyond pre-established standards.

Teachers also expressed grievances about the workload they are expected to handle within a limited time frame. The opinions of the study's participants about the fundamental aspects of the curriculum suggest a perceived necessity for the Algerian government to

make changes to better reflect the classroom diversity. Further barriers were highlighted by participants including the amount of time allocated to EFL teaching ; they identified time-constraints as a barrier to a good schooling of learners with ADHD. In such circumstances, teachers might find it more challenging to strike a balance between meeting individual and group needs, making classroom management more challenging. These factors, combined with the additional demands of dealing with diverse needs, can be overwhelming and exhausting for teachers.

Of note, the findings from this study appear to demonstrate that there remains much to be done to facilitate the inclusion of learners with ADHD. To improve the education of students with ADHD, one way forward would be to enhance the professional development of teachers and tackle various institutional and wider challenges.

6.2.3 How do Algerian EFL middle school teachers describe their feelings toward learners with ADHD?

The research data set suggests that stress, anger, and frustration are common themes when it comes to dealing with learners with ADHD. Participants used different words including 'anxious', 'stressed' , and 'frustrated' to describe their interaction with learners with ADHD. This demonstrates how it is challenging and emotionally taxing for teachers to have learners with such a condition in the classroom. Their perspective was that the behaviour exhibited by students with ADHD is mostly disruptive to the teacher and other students. Even though interacting with learners with ADHD could potentially be emotionally challenging for teachers, they still cared about these students and felt a sense of duty to perform their job effectively.

It seems that teachers, in the present study, are more emotionally reactive to events involving students, whom they perceived as more disruptive in the classroom. Apart from the behavioural challenges posed by ADHD, teachers' perceived lack of knowledge about ADHD and the different factors including lack of time and class size appear to worsen the situation and increase their emotional distress. This indicates that various systems are at play, interacting to shape teachers' emotional and psychological experiences.

It is apparent that their experience of teaching these learners has had a negative emotional impact. However, some described an ability to forbear and endure difficulties in the

classroom. They also reported care toward these learners which demonstrates their commitment to helping these learners. Despite the fact that teachers' attitudes may evolve through time to become less negative, there is a need to address their challenges and care for their well-being.

6.2.4 How do they describe the impact of their experience?

Owing to the reported lack of training on what to do and how to deal with such learners, experience seems to be the only source of input for teachers in this context. I examined the research data which reflected a true introspective reflection of past experiences with regard to emotional struggle and hardship teachers experienced in their early career. Despite the pervasive challenges that teachers recounted, they seem to take an optimistic view regarding their experience as their stories proceed. They aired their viewpoints pertaining to their perceived professional growth. In addition, they seem to implement their teaching philosophies constructed throughout their experiential practice. An improved ability to manage the classroom was reported as participants could develop potential ways to manage the situation, which seems to be learnt from experience. Therefore, they appear to depend on their developed skills to cope with their current situations.

Looking back at their own experiences, teachers expressed doubt that prevailed their early year teaching experience. However, more experienced teachers reported gaining more trust in their abilities and competencies. The passage of time for these teachers captures the evolution of person characteristics through developing more confidence in teaching. The study delved into participants' narratives of their encounters, encompassing their emotional reactions to learners with ADHD. It seems that they are struggling to find ways to deal with learners with ADHD, yet they kept going despite the difficult circumstances. It must be borne in mind that teachers' well-being and emotional health is crucial and must be taken into consideration, yet it is apparent that it is neglected since participants face difficulties alone and try to find solutions themselves based on their experiential knowledge. Participants who took part in the present study demonstrated an ability and openness to change, yet they struggled with finding some management strategies. In fact, the nature of nowadays classes urges teachers to make some adaptations and requires a constant change and flexibility which may leave them feeling stressed to make the adequate changes.

Participants spoke openly about their perceived weaknesses. They also shared some insights relating to some perceived positive attributes of their experiences. The narratives of teachers reveal that they could refine their own ways of teaching. However, it is necessary to provide formal guidance to teachers to ensure that they acquire adequate knowledge about ADHD, including various inclusive strategies to effectively engage learners with this condition and address their needs.

The conclusion I want to make with regard to these findings is that the study has succeeded in providing different perspectives into what it means for a teacher to have an ADHD learner in the class. Teachers, in the present study, had a wealth of experience of working with children with ADHD that can be used to inform their professional development. Overall, there is a consensus among teachers that the teaching of learners with ADHD is a tough task that relies on good training and professional development. Many of the participants identified common responses to having an ADHD learner inside the classroom such as anger, stress, and frustration and also common challenges such as the paucity in knowledge and training regarding ADHD, in addition to other barriers to inclusion. They also agreed that being in the classroom with learners with ADHD is nerve-racking. Therefore, there have been too many challenges confronting Algerian EFL middle school teachers.

Overall, doubt, challenge, emotional outburst, continuity, and change are important aspects of teachers' experience that coloured their journey of teaching learners with ADHD. The research adds insights into teachers' journeys of serving learners with ADHD. Teachers' accounts reveal that positive environments are very influential in shaping teachers' development, whereas incapacitating environment has a negative impact on teachers' well-being. Therefore, it is crucial for different support systems to combine and interrelate. All participants concurred that there was an indispensable need for a joint-up approach if the goals for the provision of a good schooling to learners with ADHD are to be sought.

Many of the findings support previous literature, some of them contradict with the existing body of knowledge, and some make an original contribution to knowledge (see 6.3 for more details). It both supports and extends previous research to demonstrate Algerian teachers' paucity of knowledge regarding ADHD.

6.3 Contribution to knowledge

Although the present study offers a plethora of future research trajectories, it contributed to the existing body of research and produced a significant amount of information for the research community. An important strength of this thesis lies in its contribution towards an under-researched area of the experiences of Algerian EFL middle school teachers of teaching learners with ADHD that could also be of interest to other researchers and teachers across the middle school sector. As evidenced in the literature review, there is a paucity of knowledge with reference to the topic of ADHD in the Algerian context. To date, this is the first study, to the best of my knowledge, which deals with this topic in Algeria. This study, thus, has made an original contribution to the existing literature on the topic of ADHD in the Algerian context. Viewing how teachers conceptualise ADHD would help to clear any misconception regarding this condition.

Through the discussion of different discourses available in the literature of ADHD, the study challenged the medical view of looking at ADHD, advocating a more inclusive approach. It also added insights into how Algerian EFL middle school teachers make sense of ADHD, their perceived challenges, and emotions and how they evaluate the effect of their experience. By shedding light on teachers' conceptualisations of ADHD, the study would help to raise awareness of the condition and inclusive practices in the Algerian context. In addition, by understanding how teachers feel toward learners with ADHD, the study helped to answer an important question which is how it would feel to have an ADHD learner inside the classroom. By exploring the nature of teachers' emotions toward these learners and their perceived challenges, the study helped to voice teachers' experiences.

Looking at the findings through Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory (1990), the study contributed to the theorisation of teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD and has succeeded to bring the effect of different systems into light which can be responded to in future development. The study has theoretical implications regarding the understanding of teachers' experiences from a bioecological perspective. In addition, ecological influences on teachers' work are not commonly cited in the literature and less is known about them (Price and MacCallum, 2015). By understanding and describing the ecological influences on teachers' development in the present research, the study has strengthened the research by identifying environments which are crucial for teachers' development. This information can

also be implemented to create a framework for enhancing teachers' experience with learners with ADHD, as Bronfenbrenner's theory (1990) provided a useful framework that accommodated different factors that should be considered and responded to in pedagogical practice (Hayes *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, I would argue that the inclusion of learners with ADHD requires a greater consideration of the ecological systems and teachers' individual traits. Therefore, it might be necessary to determine environmental conditions under which teachers' outcomes are stronger or weaker. Understanding the circumstances that might hinder or enhance teachers' performance would be fundamental for moving teachers' development forward. In addition, the study through stressing the critical role of teachers in inclusive education of learners with ADHD shifts attention to their main role and draws an image of how the environment would be more supportive for their needs (see section 6.6, for more details).

Overall, the study has also added insights into ADHD in the Algerian context and how different factors shaped the experience of accommodating such learners in Algerian mainstream schools. It is worth mentioning that the study presented findings which might be germane to middle school context, for example, the collective staff responsibility, class size, knowledge, and training which might help to create a supportive network inside the school. However, more research is needed to determine the transferability of the findings to other areas and subjects.

This study has also contributed to the IPA methodology as it is still in its infancy (Larkin *et al.*, 2013). It demonstrated how such a design has the potential of eliciting multiple perspectives about a phenomenon. It also contributed to IPA approach by combining SSI_s and FGD_s which is a novel approach in this field. Despite the criticism about the limitations of FGD_s, it continues to offer much food for thought as it has been used in different studies (Blake *et al.*, 2007; Dunne and Quayle, 2001; Flowers *et al.*, 2001; Love, Vetere and Davis, 2020; Montague *et al.*, 2020; Phillips, Montague, and Archer, 2017; Randazzo, Farmer and Lamb, 2015).

The majority of the criticism regarding the utilization of FGDs in IPA has centred around the challenge of extracting individualized accounts within the collective context of the group discussion (Palmer *et al.*, 2010). I have shown in the methodology chapter that I have used an additional iterative loop (Tomkins and Eatough, 2010) and the hermeneutic cycle (Smith,

Flowers, and Larkin, 2009) to ensure that individual idiosyncrasies are equally presented. FGDs are a useful tool to identify commonalities and differences among participants as Phillips, Montague and Archer (2016) expressed it: FGDs are a useful tool that helps the researcher to stay committed to the hermeneutic cycle where parts represent expressions of individual experience in the wider context of the group (whole). In addition, Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2022) declared: the meaning of the word (part) becomes clearer in the context of the whole sentence. Therefore, FGDs enabled participants to link their experiences to the broader context, allowing them to see how they relate or differ from other participants.

It is important to note that the evaluation of the quality of an IPA study should be based on the thoroughness and rigor of the analysis, rather than the specific tool or software used to conduct the analysis. While the tool may assist in the analysis, it is ultimately the researcher's skill and expertise in conducting the analysis and interpreting the data that determines the quality of the study (Phillips, Montague, and Archer, 2016). According to Smith (2004), data is deemed appropriate for IPA analysis if participants are able to provide rich and intimate descriptions of their experiences. I have shown how such a combination was successful in providing rich insights about participants' journeys who talked openly about their feelings and perceived challenges. They disagreed with other teachers and were given equal chances to express their viewpoints. More importantly, the participants confided in me with their stories and spoke candidly about their emotions. In return, I assured them of their confidentiality via the use of pseudonyms to hide their real identities. Consequently, we can draw the conclusion that the use of FGDs and SSIs, in the present research, helped to enrich my data by developing a more complex analysis. I would argue in common with Flowers *et al.* (2001) who found that the group dynamics in their study added to the weight of their analysis which would not be otherwise achieved. Participants' narratives were full of interesting reflections and novel explanations, which appeared for the first time in the discussions or were more elaborated. In addition, the narratives and reflections shared by the participants in the current study were engaging and captivating, as they contained a wealth of intriguing insights and personal reflections about their own experiences. The use of FGDs in this IPA study succeeded to reveal aspects of teachers' experiences within the larger context, highlighting common concerns.

The study would be advantageous to both teachers and learners with ADHD. By featuring the voices of Algerian EFL teachers at the middle school level, as well as their obstacles, the study helped to raise awareness of teachers' requirements which can be catered for by those in higher positions. The study has implications for the Ministry of National Education, curriculum designers and other stakeholders (see section 6.5 for more details).

6.4 Limitations

Having presented the contribution that my research study has made to the existing literature and the methodology chosen, it is also necessary to present limitations of my study that can be addressed in future research. Therefore, there are some limitations that ought to be acknowledged before moving to make any recommendations.

Given the limited existing research on IPA in the field of education, it was challenging to rely on previous studies as a reference for designing my own research. Moreover, conducting a study on inclusive education within the Algerian context is a relatively novel research direction, making it difficult to directly compare the findings of my study with previous studies conducted in the same context. However, this helped to make an original contribution to the literature on teachers' experiences of teaching learners with ADHD in that context.

The study included nine participants. This is within the recommended sample size of IPA studies (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). The findings are more representative of that group, yet generalisations cannot be made to other people who do not share the same characteristics. They may not be true reflections of most Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experience of learners with ADHD and may be representative of that specific population only. In addition, having interviewed EFL teachers, applicability of the research findings to other contexts, Arabic, and mathematics, for example, is therefore unknown. Research is needed to investigate the experience of teachers of other subjects. Consequently, more diverse participants may provide new information and lead to new directions.

Only two schools were used in this study, so findings might be unique to these schools and cannot necessarily be generalised across a wider context. The results represent the unique experiences of unique participants in a unique context, representing Algerian EFL middle

school teachers' experiences of teaching EFL to learners with ADHD and might be applicable in one geographical area. Therefore, the data concerns a specific context and uses the researchers' knowledge of the context to inform the meaning-making process. More schools can be included in future research so that generalisation can be made, although this is not necessarily an issue in IPA as it does not claim to create general or grand theories (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Some future research could generate data that can be analysed quantitatively and can be generalisable across a wider context.

A final limitation of the present study was that it relied mostly on the retrospective accounts of participants. It is possible the passage of time could have clouded their memories somewhat. They may have been affected by the passage of time, potentially leading to some inaccuracies in their accounts. Another limitation of the study is that the data were based solely on self-reported information, which carries the risk of recall bias. This means that some teachers may have remembered and reported experiences that they perceived as particularly incongruent with their needs, while overlooking situations that had a lesser impact. As a result, it is possible that strong experiences may have influenced participants' responses. Furthermore, the information provided about schools and other stakeholders was self-reported by individuals, which could result in an underestimation of certain contextual factors while overemphasizing others.

Since I previously lined up my study with Heideggerian phenomenology which admits researchers' biases in the study, I should acknowledge at this stage that my research may have been biased and influenced by own beliefs as a previous middle school teacher. Since reflective practices constitute a nexus in IPA, it was not possible to bracket my pre-conceptions and judgements about the phenomenon. As someone who used to be an Algerian student studying EFL and a former middle school teacher, I have a deep understanding of the culture and context of research and I realized that it was difficult to set aside my own pre-existing beliefs and ideas about the topic. Instead of traveling the road of bracketing my own assumptions, I tried to acknowledge and keep my own assumptions on check via using a reflexive diary. My insider knowledge about the experience of teaching learners with ADHD helped me to form in-depth interpretations of that journey. Thus, my own experience could have biased my examination of participants' experiences.

Overall, in addition to the potential bias in participants' accounts, there may be some unconscious biases as well as the experience-based perceptions that I consciously drew on when analysing the data.

6.5 Implications

The implications of the present study can be significant for various stakeholders involved in education in Algeria. Some potential implications may include:

Teacher professional development: the research has implications for the ministry of national education. The study findings can inform the development of targeted training programs and workshops for Algerian teachers to enhance their understanding of ADHD and provide effective strategies for supporting learners with ADHD in the classroom.

Classroom accommodations: by shedding light on the specific challenges faced by Algerian EFL middle school teachers in accommodating the needs of learners with ADHD, the findings can inform the development of guidelines or policies that promote inclusive practices and provide recommendations for creating supportive learning environments for learners with ADHD in Algerian classrooms.

The findings offer valuable insights into the interaction between teachers and learners, which schools can utilize to address organizational issues.

Teacher-parent collaboration: understanding the experiences of teachers in working with learners who have ADHD can facilitate stronger collaboration between parents of these learners and teachers.

The study has implications for other stakeholders including school psychologists, guiding their collaborative efforts with teachers. The findings can encourage open communication, shared understanding, and collaborative problem-solving approaches to support learners with ADHD effectively.

Policy and advocacy: the study can serve as a basis for advocacy efforts to promote inclusive education and support services for students with ADHD in the country. Establishing an open channel of communication between teachers and higher-level decision-makers would be advantageous for educators.

The findings also have implications for curriculum designers. By considering the experiences of teachers in teaching learners with ADHD in the EFL classroom, curriculum designers can develop more responsive and inclusive curricula that effectively meet the needs of all learners, including those with ADHD.

The findings of this study also have implications for researchers with an interest in the inclusion of learners with ADHD.

Overall, the study's implications can contribute to improving teachers' experiences and professional development, in addition to the outcomes of learners with ADHD in Algeria, fostering a more inclusive and supportive educational system.

6.6 Implications for teachers

The study investigating Algerian EFL (English as a Foreign Language) middle school teachers' experiences in working with learners with ADHD has significant implications for other teachers, both in Algeria and beyond.

The study will help to deepen teachers' understanding of ADHD and its impact on learning and behaviour within a classroom setting. This knowledge can help to clear any potential misconception teachers have about ADHD, therefore raising their awareness and enhancing the understanding of ADHD in the educational setting.

Findings from this study can provide insights into effective teaching strategies that can be employed to support ADHD learners. The study offered valuable ideas on how to tailor teaching approaches, materials, and classroom environment to maximize learning outcomes for these students.

The study highlighted the necessity for specialized training and professional development programs for teachers to equip them with the skills and knowledge required to effectively teach and manage students with ADHD.

Encouragement of inclusive educational practices may result from this study. Teachers could become more motivated to embrace inclusivity and create classrooms that are supportive and accommodating for all students, including those with ADHD, fostering a more inclusive and equitable learning environment.

The research underscored the importance of collaboration among teachers, psychologists, parents, and other professionals involved in the education of students with ADHD. Teachers may be encouraged to work in multidisciplinary teams to design individualized education plans (IEPs) and provide holistic support to ADHD learners.

Given that the study focuses on Algerian EFL teachers, it shed light on culturally specific challenges and opportunities in managing ADHD in this context. This understanding can guide teachers in Algeria and similar cultural settings to implement interventions that align with their cultural norms and values.

Reflective practice and commitment to inclusion can serve as a foundation for teacher agency and involvement in policy development. It can be a starting point or a fundamental aspect of empowering teachers to have a say and actively contribute to the development of educational policies. In essence, it highlights that emotional experiences and efforts can fuel teachers' engagement in policy discussions and decisions.

In summary, the study's implications extend to improved teaching practices, better support for ADHD learners, enhanced professional development opportunities, a shift towards inclusivity, and culturally sensitive approaches in educational settings. These outcomes can collectively contribute to a more effective and compassionate educational experience for students with ADHD.

6.7 Recommendations

The study I undertook provided an opportunity to explore the experiences of middle school EFL teachers who have been working with learners with ADHD. The use of data that emerged from my study can be useful in illuminating the challenges and needs of Algerian EFL middle school teachers, in this context. Despite these promising results, there are still some questions unanswered and some recommendation which I need to highlight in this part of the thesis. The findings of this study could be followed up by future research studies as discussed in the following section.

6.7.1 Recommendation for future research

The study identified multiple areas for future investigation. Potential studies might include other parties including learners , parents, psychologists and policy makers to gauge their

level of awareness of ADHD and view how they can collaborate to foster the education of these learners.

Since IPA is still in its infancy, more research can be conducted to investigate the experiences of EFL middle school learners with ADHD since young learners are rarely given opportunities to talk about their experiences in school (Sargeant and Gillet-swain, 2015; Tancredi and Graham, 2020). Eliciting the views of middle school learners with ADHD is crucial since this promotes what Sargeant and Gillet-swain (2019) called “voice-inclusive practice” (p. 271) that allows learners’ voices to be heard and fosters student-centred approaches to education. Altogether, the voices of teachers and young learners regarding ADHD can be acted upon and used to inform the practices and the pedagogy implemented for these learners.

In subsequent research, it would be beneficial to extend the theoretical framework to investigate the professional development and growth needs of teachers within a different setting.

Including more schools in future research from different contexts is recommended to allow for a comparison of data between different geographical areas. Conducting a similar study within a secondary school would also be illuminating by providing different perspectives into how secondary school teachers view ADHD.

The participants conveyed their discontent with the calibre of their training. Further investigation is required to delve deeper into the specifics of pre-service training. The study has shown that experience and attitude are related since participants reported experiencing less stress as they developed more professional experience. More research is needed to explore this. In addition, it would be of interest to study educators’ causal beliefs about ADHD since their beliefs about conceptualisations and causation were not discussed in depth.

The study concluded that a teacher-centred approach to teaching may have contributed to their negative perception towards learners with ADHD. However, further research is necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the teaching approach and the learning environment is likely to affect the attitudes and perceptions of teachers towards learners with ADHD.

The participants reported feeling dissatisfied with their interactions with the parents of learners with ADHD, who often exhibited resistance and a lack of understanding. Additional research could explore the extent of parents' knowledge about ADHD, gauging their awareness of the condition. Future research may also involve psychologists to enrich the understanding of the topic of ADHD. Incorporating multiple perspectives will enhance the breadth of research and contribute to a comprehensive understanding of ADHD within the Algerian context, allowing for a more holistic depiction of the topic.

To further advance the field, it would be valuable for future research to replicate this study using a larger sample, encompassing additional schools.

6.7.2 Recommendations based on Bronfenbrenner's Theory

The study has demonstrated the potential use of Bronfenbrenner's theory for the developing teacher, so future research might use this bioecological theory to investigate and explain the processes occurring in the teachers' workplace, focusing on what factors might contribute to teachers' development and reduce the challenge of working with learners with additional support needs, in their own contexts. Lerner (2005) claimed that Bronfenbrenner's vision considers "what was and what could be the best for human being" (p. XIII). Based on the above discussion, I have argued that different factors should be addressed to enhance the work life of teachers so that they can contribute effectively to the inclusion of learners with ADHD and can work more efficiently within and between each of the systems to achieve positive outcomes. Therefore, looking at the data through Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory suggests that teachers need to be supported to develop more efficiently through effective training and different forms of CPD opportunities including personal reflection and establishing educational practice partnership. It is essential to recognize that the choice of this specific framework to depict teachers' experiences was guided by their own needs, which were expressed during interviews and group discussions. There was a general agreement among teachers regarding the significance of establishing partnerships between various stakeholders, including the influence of internal and external factors.

The study produced valuable insights on improving the experience of Algerian EFL middle school teachers in accommodating learners with ADHD. Providing more guidance for early

career teachers on how to enhance the communication between teachers and learners is crucial. Findings suggest that teachers need more support and training to effectively manage the challenges of working with students with ADHD. Teacher education programmes should include inclusive lesson plans that acknowledge diversity of learners, addressing content on ADHD and other specific learning disabilities. By improving teachers' understanding and awareness of ADHD, as well as providing them with practical strategies for involving and supporting learners, it would be possible to improve outcomes for these learners and reduce the stress and frustration experienced by teachers. In addition, more opportunities for peer-learning and collaboration between colleagues (via building COPs, for example) and other stakeholders might contribute to the development of teachers. Therefore, if different stakeholders worked in liaison with these teachers, there would be more awareness of the condition under study. Different stakeholders need to be made aware of inclusive principles to be able to wholeheartedly embrace the ideology of inclusion. Therefore, it might be incumbent on all stakeholders to take part in the inclusion of learners with ADHD, despite the existing challenges since they can help teachers to have a healthier development.

With teachers facing considerable stress and strain, it is important that their emotional well-being is also taken care of. Stark, Daulat and King (2022) claim that teachers' mental health and well-being should be of great importance. In addition, different stakeholders, local and national authorities need to recognise the stress and fatigue teachers may experience due in part to the challenging environments in which they work, as emotional well-being is important for teachers' performance (Frenzel *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, as teachers, in the present study, expressed doubt and lack of self-efficacy in their early career, it seems crucial to focus efforts on promoting teachers' self-efficacy via providing more opportunities to develop their skills.

Bronfenbrenner's theory emphasises individual's participation in their own development. This implies that teachers' personal characteristics and individual needs should be catered for so that they can contribute effectively to their course of development and act as agents of change. It seems sensible to take on board the needs of teachers and their challenges, as well as ensure their access to appropriate services and resources to develop their practice. Meerman *et al.* (2017) suggest that framing classroom challenges in terms of teacher needs

places the responsibility and agency back on the teachers and their pedagogical strategies. This approach highlights the role of teachers in addressing problems within the classroom.

At a microsystem level, there is a need to rethink the structure of the classroom. Reducing class size may help teachers to feel less intense emotional reaction to events in the classroom and increase their potentials to pay equal attention to all learners. This decision can be carried out by policy makers to enable teachers to deal effectively with the heterogeneity of the classroom. In addition, offering formal opportunities for teachers to collaborate may be essential, as it provides a forum to learn from each other and assess their own teaching practices, while reaching a consensus on how to address various challenges.

It appears reasonable to assume that if the Ministry of National Education allocated more resources towards adequately preparing teachers to handle the challenges of the classroom, the difficulties associated with teaching this particular group of learners would have been less challenging. Teachers should be provided with an adequate knowledge of ADHD through continuous support and guidance. Due to the changing nature of the environment and the heterogeneity of the classroom, it is necessary to help teachers cope with the classroom challenges through continuous assistance, addressing the different factors which interact to affect their functioning and development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

The lack of knowledge about ADHD among teachers underscores the immediate need to evaluate the existing initial teacher-training program for new teachers and training programs for experienced teachers. In addition, more input with respect to ADHD and additional support needs education is needed to redress the current low levels of knowledge that lecturers in the present study have reported. Providing more opportunities for professional growth would help teachers to increase their knowledge of ADHD as further in-service training has been found effective to improve teachers' understanding of ADHD (Latouche and Gasoigne, 2019). It should be noted that such training does not need to be prescriptive as it is time for the normative perceptions of education, that is firmly entrenched in the Algerian context, to be challenged. One way of addressing this could be by implementing the voices and the concerns of teachers so that the training would be more informative and educative. In addition, opportunities for critical self-reflection could be

provided so that teachers can “distance themselves from their immediate actions in order to explore and evaluate them” (Biesta and Tedder, 2007, p. 146).

Improving a consistent communication between teachers and parents is also fundamental. Providing psychoeducation for parents and teachers on how to deal with different learners could help them to collaborate more effectively. It would be more feasible if psychologists work closely with teachers and parents to help them deal with learners with ADHD and engage them in the learning process since expert guidance is necessary in such a situation. It is necessary to bring together various stakeholders so that they can engage in mutual learning and exchange of ideas. This is essential as the successful execution of policy principles necessitates collaborative partnership between teachers, parents, schools, school principals, mental health coordinators and other professionals (Botha and Kourtoukas, 2016; Nel *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, a wide-spread effort needs to be initiated via bringing different stakeholders together.

Disability studies scholars call for a shift in educational practices and curriculum development to embrace the principles of inclusive education (Buffington-Adams and Vaughan, 2019). Hence, the curriculum needs to be adjusted to be more inclusive of learners’ needs and embrace diversity as one size does no longer fit all, yet before making any adjustment teachers’ needs and voices need to be heard and implemented. Their views need to be taken properly into account since their experiences can provide a useful reference to improve the education of learners with ADHD.

Teachers reflected profoundly on the impact of their education on their current understanding and teaching practices in different ways. These reflections point to the importance of providing formal opportunities for teachers to reflect on their own practices and experiences. The organisation needs to show them interest and confidence, allowing them to thrive with new opportunities and act upon their own interests and those of the organisation (Christensen, 2016). This might include opportunities for critical self-reflection so that they can explore and evaluate their teaching practices. This would help teachers to participate effectively to their own development. In addition, the individual’s participation in their own environment increases the mutual interaction between the developing teacher and their surroundings. Taking into account the temporal aspect of teachers’ experiences helps us to understand what teachers can bring to developing more inclusive educational

setting. Besides, an understanding of their experiences may help to shape more effective training that caters for their needs and continuing concerns .

6.7.3 Recommendations for the current system of EFL

The status quo of English language teaching in Algerian middle schools needs to be transformed in order to be more inclusive of learners with ADHD, while also enhancing the effectiveness of language teaching and learning. The current system can be improved through different steps:

- The materials and textbooks used for teaching EFL need to be re-evaluated in order to provide more flexibility for teachers and involve them in creating the curriculum. Policy makers may benefit from the inclusion of teachers' voices regarding curriculum design.
- It is important to raise teachers' knowledge of the different ELT methodologies as this might be helpful to create a more inclusive environment. Providing training for teachers on different English Language Teaching (ELT) methodologies, such as the TBLT or PBL could result in more positive outcomes for language learners, including those with ADHD.
- Shifting from traditional 'sit and listen' teaching methods to more interactive and participatory approaches can be beneficial for all learners including those with ADHD who would thrive in environments which allow movement through participatory and active learning. This change would promote inclusivity in EFL education.
- Increasing the amount of time dedicated to English Language Teaching (ELT) would give teachers the opportunity to better address the unique needs of each individual learner and provide equal attention to all learners.

6.8 Personal reflection

In keeping with IPA fundamental principles, I now lay bare my personal reflection which summarises how the research impacted me personally and academically and how my pre-conceptions influenced the research. This will assist in reflecting on the researcher's position and aid the reader's comprehension of the research. I utilized my insider perspective to thoroughly acquaint myself with the data, which significantly informed my interpretive inquiry. Now, I really think that because I have used my knowledge of the

context that a richer interpretation of findings was achieved. I rejected the notion of Husserlian bracketing and I followed Heideggerian hermeneutics, thus divulging the researcher's beliefs and how they influenced the research process. I must acknowledge the fact that I influenced my study in several ways and my interpretations were involved in the meaning-making of participants' experience. Since I share different characteristics with the population of the present research, especially the experience of teaching in middle school, I could not rule out the presence of my own beliefs and value within the interpretation of data. I also have to acknowledge that I actively sought out and highlighted new perspectives that challenged my own preconceptions and assumptions, allowing new themes to emerge. Engaging in reflexivity allowed me to remain vigilant about the impact of my own preconceived ideas, ensuring that I did not obscure or overlook the realities conveyed by the participants.

No doubt, the study has contributed to my life as a researcher and as an educator. In terms of my professional development as a researcher, this was my first foray into qualitative research and IPA methodology which honed my skills on this type of research. Specifically, this project provided me with an opportunity to delve into qualitative research and familiarize myself with the intricacies of the IPA methodology. Through this process, I was able to gain a deeper understanding of the nuances involved in this type of research. Overall, the experience was highly valuable for my professional development as a researcher.

Academically speaking, I challenged myself as a researcher and decided to use FGD_s within an IPA framework although this combination has long been debated (for more details see 3.6 and 6.3). The use of FGD_s within the approach of IPA is not a simplistic journey, but one that requires an in-depth engagement and hard work on the part of the researcher. Obviously, I had some doubts at the beginning of my research, but I decided to take the pledge and embark on my study using FGD_s and SSI_s as research tools. I found myself honour-bound to do justice to both IPA and FGD_s, which is a quite challenging and stressful commitment. Thus, I experienced anxiety at every level of the data analysis.

This doubt has eventually resulted in some fulfilling results since I see that I succeeded in providing rich insights derived from individual interviews and group discussions, shining light on different features of the experiential phenomenon. In addition, the present study

contributed to my understanding of the debate surrounding disability and ADHD between the medical and the social paradigm which remains a bone of contention. This change in pre-conceptions has happened as a result of my engagement with my participants and through reading the literature on ADHD. The medical model is based on an ableist thinking which according to Graham *et al.* (2020) focuses on the person's ability to execute tasks and how impairment may be limiting their activity. Therefore, it focuses on their weaknesses that are caused by the impairment which dwells in the person's body. Instead, the focus should be on addressing environmental barriers and creating a more inclusive and accessible education system that can support the needs of all students, regardless of their abilities. In other words, people should avoid being trapped within the silos of the medical view and look beyond what a child with additional support needs can or cannot do.

There was an aura of challenge and reward that characterised the research process. At every stage of the research, I had some doubts as to some decisions that I have to make. The use of Bronfenbrenner's theory and its applicability to the context of adult development was intriguing as its original purpose was for understanding children's development. However, I decided to take the risk and apply it to the context of my study which focuses primarily on teachers. It was used in conjunction with other models of disability and revealed how various elements in the context can foster teachers' development. By doing so, the study helped to provide a fresh perspective of looking at teachers' development through the PPCT model, therefore validating and extending its use for adults. Efforts need to be made to improve the teaching experience of learners with ADHD and to find strategies that address teachers' needs more systemically. The ecological environment in which teachers are developing need to respond to their various needs, mitigating the challenge of accommodating learners with ADHD.

My hope would be that the education of these learners moves toward a more humanistic approach by considering learners' and teachers' experiences and emphasising their needs. The study has demonstrated that teachers also have special requirements related to their professional development and emotional well-being. Teachers of learners with additional support needs including ADHD need to feel supported and fully equipped to address the requirements of these learners. I also hope that my findings will be used to improve and inform the practice of teaching learners with ADHD. Maybe it is timely to teach cultural

acceptance of some behaviours to others via implementing more inclusive mandates. This would help to wash away any misconception and judgment of certain behaviours.

My journey was filled with different challenges that ultimately contributed to my professional and personal growth. I learned how to be more patient since the PhD journey is a long process that requires persistence and hard work. My final word here is that it has been an inspirational experience full of rewarding results. I believe that my study is just a steppingstone along the path to many upcoming research that investigates this area which has long been unexplored in the Algerian context.

7. References

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8. Appendices

Appendix A : Participants' personal profiles

Pseudonym	Gender
Ahmed	male
Imene	female
Laila	female
Amina	female
Fouad	male
Jalil	male
Ali	male
Mohamed	male
Amel	female

FGD₁	FGD₂
Ahmed	Amina
Laila	Amel
Imene	Fouad

<p>Ahmed: is an EFL middle school teacher (aged 45) from school A, with a strong passion for helping learners with ADHD. He has been a middle school teacher for 15 years. 1st and 4th middle school learners are now under his tutelage. He conceptualises ADHD as a complex and a heterogeneous disorder. He expressed willingness to adapt the educational context to accommodate learners with ADHD.</p>	<p>Imene is a young (28 years old) EFL middle school teacher from school A. She has five years' experience teaching at middle school. She views ADHD as a social phenomenon and expressed the role of positive relationship in regulating , altering the learner's disruptive behaviour and dealing with the challenges in teaching learners with ADHD.</p>
<p>Laila: Is a middle-aged teacher (38-year-old) from school A.</p> <p>She has been teaching for 10 years. She is a mom of three children. She conceptualises ADHD as a complex disorder, stemming from neurobiological and social causes.</p>	<p>Amina: is a young middle school teacher at school B. She is a graduate of a training school located in an urban city. After studying four years at this special school, she was directly recruited as a 'middle school teacher'. She has five-year experience of teaching 1st, 2nd, and 3rd MS learners.</p>
<p>Fouad: is a young middle school teacher (29-year-old) in charge of 1st MS and 2nd MS at school B. He has been teaching for six years. He is originally Kabyle from a rural city and speaks three languages (French, English, and Berber). He moved with his parents when he was a kid to the city where he is teaching now.</p>	<p>Jalil: is a well-experienced middle-aged teacher aged 56-year-old at school A. He has been teaching EFL middle school learners for 25 years at school B. When he got older, he decided to teach in some private schools with less learners per class.</p>

<p>He views that his young age helped him to build a strong relationship with his pupils.</p>	
<p>Ali: is a middle school teacher aged 46, with an experience of 13 years in teaching middle school learners at school A.</p>	<p>Mohamed: is a middle school teacher who has been teaching middle school learners for ten years at school A.</p> <p>He lived in London for a while where he did his masters. After graduating, he went back to Algeria and was offered a job as a middle school teacher.</p>
<p>Amel: is a young and a novice middle school teacher, aged 28 years old, at school B. She is in the early years of her teaching career with an experience of four years.</p>	

School of Education & Social Sciences

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: Algerian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School Teachers' Experiences of teaching ADHD learners: an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

Introduction

This research project is run by **Roumaissa Mabrouk**, PhD student in the school of Education, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

My research investigates EFL middle school teachers' experiences of working with learners attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) to:

- (1) Develop an in-depth understanding of EFL middle school teachers' experiences and their impact on teachers.
- (2) Investigate teachers' conceptualisation of ADHD.
- (3) Explore teachers' feelings toward learners with ADHD.
- (4) Uncover any challenges that teachers might face when including learners with ADHD.

Who are we?

The principal researcher who will conduct this study is: Roumaissa Mabrouk, a PhD student within the school of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), with sufficient knowledge of conducting interviews.

Do you have to take a part?

Taking part in this research project is completely voluntary and if you choose to be involved, you will have the right to withdraw at any point of time during the data collection without penalty of any form.

What will you do in this research project?

You will be required to take part in an interview (approx. 30 min) about your experiences of teaching middle school EFL learners with ADHD. The interview includes some questions about your experiences regarding teaching EFL to learners with ADHD, including your feelings, conceptualisations, and challenges that you might face when including learners with ADHD.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part since you have been identified as an EFL middle school teacher with a previous experience on teaching learners with ADHD.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking some time of your time for the completion of the interviews and focus group activities.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

Data provided by participants will be entirely confidential and all answers will be undertaken anonymously. Completed data will be securely stored within the university.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What will happen next?

If you are perfectly willing to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign the consent form to confirm this. An interview will be conducted at a time convenient to you. With your permission, the interview will be recorded and transcribed. After the interview, there will be a possibility to take part in focus groups, if you are interested.

The project is extremely grateful for your involvement and collaboration. Thanks, are also extended to those who refuse participation for taking some of your precious time reading the documents.

Once the project is done, you will be debriefed after participation. You will be emailed with a brief account of the research findings that detail your experience with teaching EFL middle school learners with ADHD. This investigation was granted ethical approval by the School of Education Ethics Committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Professor Donald Gillies

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Room: 3.023

Researcher Contact Details:

Roumaissa Mabrouk

School of Education & Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

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E-mail address:

E-mail: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

School of Education & Social Sciences

Paisley Campus

Consent form

Title of the research project: Algerian English as Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School Teachers' Experiences of ADHD: an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Name of the researcher: *Roumaissa Mabrouk*

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

- 3- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

- 4- Please tick as appropriate

I am willing to take part in the interview where the researcher will be recording

I am willing to take part in a focus group which will be recorded

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

School of Education & Social Sciences

Paisley Campus

Participant De-briefing Sheet

'Algerian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School Teachers' Experiences of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD): An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)'

Thank you for being involved in this research study. Your participation will be helpful in understanding the experiences of middle school teachers of working alongside learners with ADHD.

The information provided by you in your interview/ FGD will now be anonymously transcribed and written up to be included in the research findings.

If you would like to know more about the topic investigated, you can have a look at the following articles:

1. Sayal, K., Prasad, V., Daley, D., Ford, T. and Coghill, D. (2018) 'ADHD in children and young people: prevalence, care pathways, and service provision', *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 5(2), pp.175-186.
2. Martinez-Badía, J., & Martinez-Raga, J. (2015) 'Who says this is a modern disorder? The early history of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder', *World journal of psychiatry*, 5(4), pp.379–386.
3. Boutebal, S.E. and Yahi, S. (2018) 'Inclusion of the children with disabilities among school in Algeria', *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 9(10), pp.26-31.

- If you would like to receive a copy of the overall research findings, please contact us:

Professor Donald Gillies

Researcher Contact Details:

Dean of the School of Education & Social Sciences

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Personal details withheld.

Appendix C: Interview schedule

Title: Algerian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School Teachers' Experiences of ADHD: an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Introduction and Consent

- Thank the interviewee for their time.
- Interview will last about 30 minutes.
- Introduce myself (background, current role)
- State the main interest of my research : investigating teachers' experiences (there is no right or wrong answer)
- Reiterate confidentiality and the right to withdraw.
- Reiterate that participants will be tape recorded
- Turning on the tape recorder

Research Questions

1. Can you tell me a little bit about your current role in school? what do you like most about your job?
2. When I say ADHD, what do you understand by this term?
3. In which ways has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?
4. How do you find teaching learners with ADHD?
5. What do you feel toward learners with ADHD?

To conclude

Is there anything else you would like to share as far as your experience? Would you like add anything?

Debrief

- Thank the participant for their collaboration
- Highlight again the information in the Participant Information Sheet about what will happen to the results and who to contact for further information.
- Time to process and reflect on the interview. How did they find it? Do they have any additional questions?

- Ask about whether they would like to receive information about the findings. How would they prefer this, face-to-face or electronic (see debriefing sheet)

Appendix D: Coded Interview transcriptions

Transcription coding: parts in the transcripts were highlighted using three different colours (yellow, orange, and pink) to identify three types of exploratory notes/ codes.

Descriptive coding: focused on describing the content of what participants said. These were highlighted in yellow.

Linguistic coding: focused on the language use by participants. This was noted by an orange colour.

Conceptual coding: focused on interpretations of what participants said, including their language use. This is highlighted by a pink colour and usually takes the interrogative form.

Emergent theme	Transcript Excerpt	Exploratory Comments (coding)
<p>pick in being a teacher</p> <p>attached to courses</p>	<p>Roumaïssa: Hello I'm Roumaïssa Mabrouk, a PhD student at the school of education and social sciences</p> <p>My research study entitled: Investigating EFL middle school teachers' experiences of ADHD: An interpretative Phenomenological Analysis</p> <p>Today I'm conducting my second interview with one of the participants Can you tell me a little bit about your current role in school and what do you like most about your job?</p> <p>Imene: I can't say I like my job ... I'm in love with my job because English is... I fall in love with English since I was 8-year-old , so I like it so much and I have chosen this job by love</p> <p>I like it so much , I'm so proud of being a teacher...I'm so happy to teach people different age ...at different levels ...I'm so happy to make people love English just the way I did</p> <p>Um... you said what do you like most about your job ...well I like that by the end of the level when your pupils finish their level and are going to get their certificates...they kept complimenting me and they say that i'm an amazing teacher and they are so proud of being my pupils I like when they share with me their personal lives, their problems,etc</p>	<p>Description of the res! v de a main interest</p> <p>love my job</p> <p>Describe relationship social bond with course</p>

<p>Defining ADHD by</p> <p>main features of ADHD</p> <p>normative discussion</p>	<p>R: When I say ADHD what do, you understand it by this term?</p> <p>I: Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) means problems that learners face or in other words pupils who are not, maybe normal, different from others , who are hyperactive ...who are inattentive ... learners with ADHD disturb some teachers and their classmates (silence) we can notice the difference between attentive learners and inattentive learners...this can be remarkable while teaching ...when pupils behave...when they use body language ...they use facial expressions... they move...they talk too much ... all these terms are hidden under the umbrella of ADHD</p> <p>As a teacher I can say that these learners have difficulty sitting in one place for a while. They have difficulties in ...not understanding but concentrating ...what else they have problems with their peers...</p> <p>R: You mentioned that these learners are abnormal, can you explain why?</p> <p>I: You can see that they are abnormal when you compare them to the group. Most of the learners, they do sit and concentrate when you explain the lesson... I know they are just adolescents or even kids and they need to move...I can understand that...but this type of learners even when other learners are concentrating and listening to the teachers...These learners, on the other hand,</p>	<p>Factual/legit to define ADHD</p> <p>normative? abnormal? discussion? remarkable? not suitable behavior</p> <p>Describe the behavior of ADHD causes</p> <p>abnormal? a few medical discussion?</p> <p>social norms</p> <p>most? exceptional teachers</p>
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<p>disruption of digital activities</p> <p>not fitting the 100% unacceptable behaviour lack of focus</p> <p>scope for individual attention</p>	<p>can't... they are doing things as playing they try to get things from their school bags</p> <p>R: yeah, I got you ...so compared to others, you see that their behaviour is abnormal !</p> <p>I: yes, but in activities that require movement, they are the first one to finish... it depends on the activity you are giving to them...but in most activities that require concentration they are inattentive...they are impulsive most of the time...I sometimes feel that they can't control their behaviour ...they want to give you the answer, sometimes, even when you did not finish the question.</p> <p>R: so, do you see that their behaviour is not accepted in formal settings as schools?</p> <p>I: yes of course this is a place where they should study...they should not be playing for example...we can involve them in some play activities, but this is up to the teacher to decide this...</p> <p>I'm aware that we are teaching mixed ability class, there are different levels of understanding and different modes of learning that needs time...one hour is not enough to involve all these learners</p> <p>R: In which ways has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?</p> <p>I: well, on the basis of my experience since I saw many...um a particular number of learners with ADHD ...</p> <p>And if you ask me about coping strategies, I always use 'discussion' ... I try to discuss the problem with them individually, I never</p>	<p>awareness of the strategies used by pupils?</p> <p>should: required to comply with school rules</p> <p>awareness of the relevance of the classroom.</p> <p>description of coping strategies</p>
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<p>understanding sense of empathy</p> <p>Description of past experience</p> <p>sense of achievement & success in lessons</p> <p>perpetually searches for support</p>	<p>make this kind of pupils feel that they have a problem, or they are different, especially in front of others... I always avoid embarrassing him/her... to be honest I feel sorry for them that's why I chose to discuss and talk , but not only face to face because... my Facebook account is not really personal... I use it to help my pupils because sometimes you find that a pupil can't talk face to face... so I chose to talk to them in messenger or via phone...they call me and sometimes we hang out together ; for instance, one of my pupils whose name xxx was so hyperactive, he always has problems with his flatmates. After discussing with him, he opened up for me and now I know how to let him concentrate</p> <p>Um, honestly, I found this a great idea because they all share with me their problems and I can say , I played a very remarkable role in their livesand by the end of the discussion I feel that I succeeded to solve their problems and I felt so proud because learners trusted me</p> <p>R: Do you receive any other support?</p> <p>I: um... to be honest with you we don't...actually when I was in my first year of teaching, I ask some colleagues when I can't find a solution to any problem, I face... the problem keeps in your mind even when you go home...you think of issues you faced in the classroom even when you leave this context...</p>	<p>→ ?</p> <p>achieve a sense of empathy</p> <p>Using Facebook: chat's mostly in a relationship with a pupil</p> <p>an aggregator</p> <p>Description of lack of support</p>
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<p>Reflecting back on his first experience</p> <p>collaboration with parents</p> <p>struggle</p>	<p>R: it seems that this experience overwhelmed you?</p> <p>I: yes, it is... I can't deny the fact that dealing with learners who show these negative behaviours is tiring, but this difficulty decreases through time</p> <p>R: so, can you say something about how has your experience helped you to understand ADHD?</p> <p>I: at the beginning it was difficult. I remember the first ADHD learner was a boy whose name . xxx, he was so hyperactive, and he used to stay at the back of the class, he stopped writing the lesson, he no longer focuses , he talks, and he uses his body language in a way to show that I can talk to my teacher the way I like and he uses his hands and he shouts... . . . I tried to discuss the problem with him many times ... In this case, parents know more than we do...they know what the child has been through, and they know how their child behave , so collaboration with parents is highly needed in this situation. Parents can help you access some information that will help you to deal with some children. They have been living with their child for long...they know...they know...sometimes better than we do</p> <p>R: so, what was your feeling when you first met that pupil with ADHD?</p> <p>I: it was (silence)...my first experience umm... it was kind of different and difficult.</p>	<p>tiring overwhelmed scary to what extent?</p> <p>challenging experience a problem</p> <p>to emphasize importance of the importance of collaboration</p> <p>difficult she had expectation</p>
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<p>Negotiating different ways to deal with ADHD learner</p> <p>personal communication</p> <p>story of changes a pupil</p>	<p>... I was thinking about this boy even I go home... I panicked what should I do' maybe I was not good enough... I talked with one of my colleagues and we negotiated ways that might be successful to involve these learners... from time to time we organise some meetings to share our experiences ... and now I developed my own ways... you know... to deal with such learners... through practice...</p> <p>I also discussed the problem with his parents , I found that he was like that even home...and their parents . at the beginning, they were stubborn and did not want to collaborate. He is a spoiled boy . . . but they end up helping me, in addition to other colleagues of course, to find a solution to their kid's problem...I should also mention that personal effort and search is needed in this situation...maybe the teacher needs to read more about this category to find tips that help him to manage the class in the presence of these learners....</p> <p>R: so how do you evaluate your experience of teaching ADHD learners?</p> <p>I: it's a good experience ... maybe you can't see this from the start... but after some time, you will discover you that you developed the ability to solve problems...how to face different difficulties and how to deal with different learners...when you have, for example, hyperactive learner... you may use</p>	<p>seeking external support</p> <p>developed up own way? lack of guidance = good</p> <p>the impact of collaboration / dependence on trust</p> <p>to what extent time Description of past a parent experience</p>
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<p>Experiences asked only recourse</p> <p>reflection back on past experiences</p> <p>finds away in the dark</p> <p>content not taught H/Vang</p>	<p>the knowledge you acquired via your experience to react in a good way yeah... I developed my own way of teaching so that if I face this problem in the future I would know how to react and deal with the situation ...xxx was a good experience that motivated me to change my method of teaching with this type of learners</p> <p>Through these difficult experiences that challenge you, you move from how I can do it? To how I can make it better.</p> <p>R: You mentioned that you felt rewarding results after some time, can you explain more?</p> <p>I: yes, I can't tell you that now I'm not facing any difficulty in teaching these learners. However, I could find some ways to teach them to let them concentrate...it's a question of time and experience...experience teaches you 'the know-how'...of course you cannot make it right from the start but you are continuously trying to make it work or make it better</p> <p>R: Can you describe the training you received before starting teaching?</p> <p>I: Actually, it was only theoretical...they teach us how to organise the lesson...we dealt with classroom management, but not very deeply...how to manage time...how to assess pupils' learning... it was more about the content of the lesson...for example we were trained how to use a method based on three levels (PDP): pre-listening, while-</p>	<p>lack of guidance</p> <p>learn from experiences Experiences as an opportunity away to adapt</p> <p>development with us was</p> <p>Disruption of H/Vang</p>
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<p>clear method process of bag</p> <p>lack of opportunities to write</p> <p>top down approach</p>	<p>listening, and post listening. The first stage include tasks that prepare students by getting them interested in the topic through presenting a set of activities. ...while listening allows the learners to go deeper into the lesson. The final stage expect from the learner to use what have been acquired in previous stages via some writing tasks ...there is also another method PPU (Presentation, Practice and Production)...this one is more linked to grammar and vocabulary...it starts by setting up the situation moving to practising the new language in filling gaps activities, synonyms and antonyms and even conjugating verbs, then they are encouraged to use the target language in formal writing...I think these methods are the most used ones...however those with inattention and hyperactivity issues don't listen to the teacher while he presenting the lesson...this becomes problematic</p> <p>R: can you explain how do you organise or structure the lesson? Do you follow any guidelines?</p> <p>I: we do have a guide to follow ...we usually start the lesson with a song, a game to get the learner's attention. Basically, we ask them to read a passage from the book that have [sic] our objectives set ... we end the lesson by learners having to write a small passage asking learners to use the things that they have learned during the lesson...</p>	<p>describing the process of teaching writing task what about speaking</p> <p>focus on short writing A.P.U.C.S</p> <p>a guide to follow below I present read write about speaking</p>
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<p>presumably what will be done</p> <p>Workload</p> <p>lack of time</p> <p>no prior training on ADHD</p> <p>cultural modes of being</p>	<p>R: What challenges did you face while teaching these learners? And why?</p> <p>I: The ministry put the guidelines of the curriculum, how the lesson should be structured and what objectives should be met... the lesson is divided into two parts: the first part is more theoretical where the teacher has to deliver the content of the lesson...the second part is a set of activities to evaluate the learners' understanding which is too much to be done in one session...sometimes I don't have the chance to look at all learners' answers because I run out of time...Time is our enemy...you feel stressed to meet the expectations, to assess all learners work...um...this is so tiring...you know... let me tell you something we were not introduced to this ADHD in the training we had, I knew I will be teaching learners with special needs like those with physical or sight impairment...that's all... because I saw this even when I was in university. I also remember that trainers mentioned pupils with physical impairments...that's all...for conditions as autism, hyperactivity and attention problems I read or search, sometimes ask colleagues to find out what is suitable</p> <p>R: do you want to add or suggest anything?</p> <p>I: As a teacher, I always say to my pupils ...everything in teaching starts by love</p>	<p>diff details reported on teacher expectations? responsible to what is expected</p> <p>lack of time need for personal effort</p>
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<p>the importance of being a close bond between teachers & learners</p> <p>Need for collaboration between us</p>	<p>...whenever you love something, you do it better</p> <p>A: A teacher should show love to the pupils, all kinds of pupils including ADHD learners</p> <p>I try to treat them like their mom, and I try to fix any problem they face while learning</p> <p>The first thing that pops to my mind whenever I face a problem is 'discussion'</p> <p>I sit with my pupils like i'm sitting with you and I discuss and believe me although I have short experience in teaching, I can say that my experience helped me a lot in facing such problems</p> <p>I should also add that if there are some formal meetings between teachers where they can discuss their experience and areas where they feel they lack knowledge would be helpful for us, teachers, though this is not common in our school ...it would help teachers in a way or another</p> <p>We sometimes meet outside the teaching hours, we discuss our experiences together, but we would like to have formal meetings where the focus is not just pupils' learning but what we as teachers suffer from...what we face as challenges...</p> <p>R: I would like to thank you for taking time to take part in my interview</p> <p>I: Most welcome, and I wish you best of luck</p>	<p>→ Teachers need to discuss</p> <p>Need to shift attitude to collaboration</p>
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Appendix E: Clustering emergent themes to draw super-ordinate themes.

The generation of superordinate theme through subsumption

Superordinate theme	Emergent themes
Voicing concerns	Distractibility Crowded classes Bridging the gap between theory and practice Teacher-parent tension Workload

The generation of superordinate theme through abstraction

Emergent themes	Superordinate theme
Seeking parents' help Investing in teacher-pupil interaction Colligability	Negotiating different systems

The generation of superordinate theme through contextualisation

Emergent themes	Superordinate theme
Anxiety Self-blame: feeling of inadequacy Tension Annoyance Distraction	Retrospective accounts of the first encounter with an ADHD learner

The generation of superordinate theme through function

Emergent themes	Superordinate theme
Lecture-based training External benchmarks Anxiety Time constraint Self-blame: feeling of inadequacy Tension in teacher-pupil interaction	A long journey against hardship

Appendix F: Focus Group Discussion (FGD) schedule

Thank participants for accepting to take part in the group discussions.

1. If we start thinking about what ADHD means. How do you conceptualise ADHD?

Probes: a medical disorder/ a social disorder/ others, please specify

2. Do you think that learners with additional support needs should be educated in mainstream school or special schools? And why?
3. Can you describe your experience of teaching learners with ADHD?
4. What kind of challenges do you face when including learners with ADHD?
5. According to you, what kind of support mitigates teachers' negative feelings and challenges experienced?
6. How do you evaluate the impact of your experience? And Why?

Other points for discussion:

Teachers' needs

Teachers' feelings

Suggestions

Further probes:

Can you explain why?

Can you give an example of...

Appendix G: Coded Focus Group Discussion (FGD) transcriptions

Emergent Theme	Focus Group Discussion (1) Pseudonyms: 1. Ahmed 2. Laila 3. Imene	Exploratory comments
<p>The right to withdraw</p> <p>Medicalisation ADHD</p> <p>more prevalent in young pupils</p>	<p>Roumaissa: Morning, I would like to thank you for accepting to take part in today's discussion. As I explained in the interviews, my topic investigates Algerian EFL middle school teachers' experiences of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)</p> <p>If we start thinking about what ADHD means. How do you conceptualise ADHD?</p> <p>Probes: a medical disorder a social disorder others, please specify</p> <p>Ahmed: I would say it's a behaviour symptom where learners can't stay still for a long time and this is the nature of most classes or what we call mixed ability or heterogeneous classes. Some are quite; some are hard workers, etc. The smart teacher will always find ways to deal with any category, including those with ADHD during the teaching process</p> <p>I think that the disorder is more prevalent in 1 MS, so it's more prevalent in first years of the middle school.</p> <p>Personally, I see that there are many factors that participate to the development of ADHD. The conditions of</p>	<p>Describing catering thought to withdraw</p> <p>Description of the behaviour of ADHD classes symptoms can't stay still? categorically hyperactivity + the nature of not classes does he tolerate that behaviour?</p> <p>Description of problem disorder → a medical term</p> <p>Description of causes</p>

<p>Factors that cause ADHD</p> <p>The context</p> <p>Ability/ inability</p> <p>Unchangeable/ unalterable condition</p> <p>Socialisation ADHD</p> <p>Hereditary</p>	<p>the learner's schooling and the methods of teaching that are highly demanding for the learner might be responsible for ADHD</p> <p>Laila: (nods her head) Yes, I agree with you. The new educational system is so demanding, asking the child to sit for a long time, without speaking or moving, must be so boring for the pupil.</p> <p>Ahmed: severe instructions</p> <p>Imene: inattention means inability to keep attention for a long time</p> <p>Hyperactivity is related to the learner's behaviour... it depends... it depends</p> <p>ADHD is an attitude that we can't do anything about... yes we can create ways to deal with it, but we can't change it since it relates to the learner's nature.</p> <p>Ahmed: it is both for me a medical and a social condition. Why?</p> <p>A social condition since society plays a role in causing ADHD... based on my experience with one of the middle school learners. When I tried to delve deeper into one of my learner's disorder, her mother told me that he is like his father when he was young</p> <p>R: Do you think that learners with ADHD should be educated in mainstream schools or general schools?</p> <p>Ahmed: in public schools</p> <p>Laila: if the disorder symptoms are above normal, we need to put the learner in</p>	<p>→ agreement</p> <p>Description of its educational system asking the child to sit for a long time? categorically?</p> <p>recognition of teacher's desire to work</p> <p>making sense of ADHD</p> <p>Description of behaviour of ADHD classes</p> <p>disorder symptoms/ above normal</p>
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<p>Recognis Influences</p>	<p>special schools, but if the teacher can manage the situation, the learner with ADHD can be placed in public schools, but using a special method, giving him/her the chance to move because learners with ADHD are not given the opportunity to exercise and express their inner energy.</p>	<p>Description of personal opinion Special needs?</p>
<p>A moment of reflection</p>	<p>Interviewer: can you describe your experience of teaching ADHD learners? Ahmed: (laughs) I still remember my first years of teaching ADHD learners in 1990 where I used a stick to punish learners whenever I notice someone who is hyperactive and inattentive, but I found no positive effect of this strategy</p>	<p>How is the behaviour reward How about it?</p>
<p>Connecting Past & Present experiences</p>	<p>Via time, I switched to another more method: reward to motivate learners to pay attention (silence) my experience has had a positive impact on my development as a teacher Laila: my experience with ADHD learners was not that easy at the beginning... though it helped me to become more patient. I learned to be patient through time, I learned how to deal with learners with ADHD (silence) I learned to react to this behaviour in a thoughtful manner with more understanding... experience helps you to build more trust between you and your learners... you can develop an understanding of the job demands</p>	<p>Develops patience</p>

<p>A difficult Abruptly to face challenges</p>	<p>Imene: I would say a tough task, a stressful journey. Although the teacher feels stressed to teach these learners. However, it's a good experience that teaches us how to solve problems, how to face the ongoing challenges and how to deal with different learners...</p>	<p>Tough task Description of the experience of teaching ADHD learners</p>
<p>A lonely journey Lack of support</p>	<p>R: what kind of challenges do you face when including learners with ADHD? Laila: (in a very low tone) unfortunately we face the problem alone and solve it alone and we try to find the solution by ourselves to manage and control the situation (silence) we receive no help neither from the ministry nor from the administration</p>	<p>We → Together</p>
<p>Disabilities with various workload</p>	<p>Ahmed: before there was some CPD sessions (silence) we still have some training days to help the teacher to deal with new situations These learners interrupt and distract others so I feel anxious and sometimes sorry for them Laila: (in a low tone) unfortunately, I see that these training sessions are more theoretical than practical (terminology and concepts) Imene: I share my colleagues' views on the lack of training. I also see that the workload and the different responsibilities that the teacher has may overload him/her. I, for example, sometimes feel</p>	<p>Description of the behaviour of ADHD learners Disabilities? Lack of the awareness concern</p>

<p>Don't seem to overwhelm by school work</p> <p>Workload</p> <p>Management strategies</p> <p>time constraint</p> <p>Engage learners</p>	<p>lost between delivering the content of the lesson, which is sometimes too much to be achieved in one session, and focusing on individual learners and gauge their understanding of the lesson.</p> <p>Ahmed: I totally agree with you ... different things do not allow us to use innovative strategies including overloaded program with many responsibilities and works assigned to the teacher.</p> <p>R: How do you manage ADHD learners' behaviours?</p> <p>Laila: sometimes, I devote all the session for games to break the routine</p> <p>Ahmed: for me, I can't find time to use games. If I do, I will not finish the program. For me, I sometimes start the lesson by a joke to keep learners' attention ... I also reward these learners to reinforce good behaviour</p> <p>Imene: for me, I try to engage learners in some activities like disturbing [sic] the copybooks to their classmates, worksheets, etc. I also use L1 to attract their attention. These learners need to be engaged in some activities as: football, basketball, etc.</p> <p>R: According to you, what kind of support</p>	<p>Don't need for extra time structural changes?</p> <p>Barriers to teaching</p> <p>Reactive strategies</p> <p>Lack of time</p> <p>Reactive or proactive strategies</p> <p>acknowledging Barriers Need to move?</p>
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<p>Recognizing Influences</p> <p>Moment of reflection</p> <p>Connecting Past & Present experiences</p>	<p>special schools, but if the teacher can manage the situation, the learner with ADHD can be placed in public schools, but using a special method, giving him/her the chance to move because learners with ADHD are not given the opportunity to exercise and express their inner energy.</p> <p>Interviewer: can you describe your experience of teaching ADHD learners?</p> <p>Ahmed: (laughs) I still remember my first years of teaching ADHD learners in 1990 where I used a stick to punish learners whenever I notice someone who is hyperactive and inattentive, but I found no positive effect of this strategy</p> <p>Via time, I switched to another more method: reward to motivate learners to pay attention (silence) my experience has had a positive impact on my development as a teacher</p> <p>Laila: my experience with ADHD learners was not that easy at the beginning... though it helped me to become more patient. I learned to be patient through time, I learned how to deal with learners with ADHD (silence) I learned to react to this behaviour in a thoughtful manner with more understanding ... experience helps you to build more trust between you and your learners... you can develop an understanding of the job demands</p>	<p>Description of personal opinion Special method?</p> <p>How is the behaviour reward</p> <p>→ How is it?</p> <p>Developing patience</p>
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<p>need for external support</p> <p>need for networking</p>	<p>mitigates teachers' negative feelings and challenges experienced?</p> <p>Laila: we need to be provided with a supportive environment that addresses teachers' needs</p> <p>Teachers should seek the psychologist's help</p> <p>Ahmed: a psychologist is needed</p> <p>Coordination with other teachers to discuss potential solutions (silence)</p> <p>discussing the problem with the learner is also needed</p> <p>Imene: teachers are in need of some training sessions so that they can face the continuing challenges... these sessions must target the teachers' practical needs</p> <p>R: I would like to thank you for your collaboration</p>	<p>the needs are not met</p> <p>need for CPD</p>
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Appendix H: Additional iterative loop

Appendix I: List of individual superordinate themes across cases interviews and FGDs

Imene	Mohamed	Laila	Fouad	Ali	Ahmed
Problematising ADHD	ADHD as a complex condition	ADHD as a medical condition	Medicalising ADHD	ADHD as an abnormal condition to be treated.	Learners with ADHD as a distraction
Negotiating different systems	Behavioural and educational implications of ADHD	Developing habit	The demand of teacher-pupil interaction	Nature vs nurture	An emotional experience
Reflecting on the first encounter	Anxiety			An emotional tiring experience.	
Feeling of inadequacy: shortage of knowledge	Voicing Concerns	A shared responsibility	Care and commitment to help learners with ADHD.	Perpetually badgering for support	The challenges of dealing with learners with ADHD
A challenge that makes me better prepared			A need for more knowledge	Evaluating management strategies	

Jalil	Amel	Amina
Making sense of ADHD through individual and societal barriers	Inadequate knowledge about ADHD	Normality- fitting in
A strange behaviour	Learners with ADHD as disturbance	A challenging experience

<p>Getting support: working with parents</p> <p>An emotional demanding experience</p> <p>Thirst for new knowledge</p> <p>Lack of inclusive principles</p>	<p>An emotional taxing experience</p>	<p>The emotional impact of teaching learners with ADHD</p>
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Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

FGD1	FGD2
<p>Connecting past and present experiences</p> <p>ADHD as a multifactorial disorder</p> <p>A sense of struggle</p> <p>Emotional distress</p> <p>Need for extra help/ training.</p> <p>Workload</p>	<p>Refusing the medical origin of ADHD</p> <p>A challenging experience</p> <p>Need for training to bridge the gap between theory and practice.</p> <p>Varied psychological make-up.</p> <p>Addressing the behaviour of learners with ADHD</p>

